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APPLIED RESEARCH. GLOBAL SOLUTIONS

Istanbul, Turkey - January 14, 2026

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**APPLIED RESEARCH.
GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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CONTENTS

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

- Ethnobotany-ecological and ethnomedical materials medicinal plants of the badhyz flora
Akmyradov Allamyrat, Perdayeva Aybolek 8
- Influence of phytohormones on physiological and biochemical processes of wheat grain (*Triticum L.*)
Emomalizoda Sayyod Emomali, Khamiddin Nor Khamidzoda, Rajabzoda Sirojiddin Ikrom, Nurov Umedzhon Dzhahalovich 13
- Modification of the duodenal microbiota of laying hens
Musin Almaz Gaznavievich 18
- Quality of dietary eggs
Musin Almaz Gaznavievich, Gadiev Rinat Ravilovich, Mustafin Azat Sagitovich, Khaziev Danis Damirovich 24

MEDICAL SCIENCES

- Features of the circadian rhythm of diastolic blood pressure in patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury in childhood
Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna, Rahimova Suraye Ruzmetovna, Nasimov Sobir Tahirovich 29
- Digital Screening Platform for Occupational Lung Diseases: Validation of an Artificial Intelligence System for Predictive Diagnosis of Pneumoconioses (A Case Study of Kuzbass)
Bondarev O. I., Surkov A. M., Bondareva I. A. 40
- Features of the circadian rhythm of pulse arterial pressure in patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury in childhood
Muhitdinova Hura Nuritdinovna, Nazarov Bahtiyor Mahmujonovich, Fathulayeva Dildora Murojon kizi 45
- The role of hormonal dysfunction in the pathogenesis of erosive gastroduodenitis in girls during puberty
Panova Irina Vitalievna, Dombayan Svetlana Khristoforovna, Eliseeva Nina Dmitrievna 54

Bioinspired technologies in solving complex problems of endodontics <i>Rozhkova Elena Nikolaevna, Postnikov Mikhail Alexandrovich, Lyamin Artem Viktorovich, Ippolitov Yuriy Alekseevich, Kharitonov Dmitry Yuryevich, Stepanov Ilya Vyacheslavovich, Ismatullin Danir Damirovich</i>	60
A therapist's view on infectious pancarditis <i>Sapunova Daria Alexandrovna</i>	69
Artificial intelligence in the system of prioritizing medical evacuation of children: a concept of a hybrid model for an interregional network of surgical care centers <i>Verevina Marina Leonidovna</i>	75
Trophic disorders of the antenatal period as a factor in the delay of the structural and functional maturation of the bronchopulmonary system <i>Tolokolnikova Ekaterina Vyacheslavovna, Bryksina Evgeniya Yurievna, Letifov Gadzhi Mutalibovich, Davydova Nadezhda Anatolyevna</i>	81

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Prospects for using melon crops in wine production in the Orenburg region <i>Tsintsadze Oksana Evgenievna, Arkhipova Nadezhda Alexandrovna, Pavlova Oksana Gennadievna, Yartsev Svyatoslav Sergeevich</i>	88
The use of jerusalem artichoke juice in production non-alcoholic carbonated beverages of functional orientation <i>Volkova Alla Viktorovna</i>	93

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

Mathematical modeling of a hybrid renewable energy generation system <i>Teona Guladievna Tedoradze, Paul Amadi Ikenna, Camogni Ange Rosi</i>	98
Optimisation of low-yield well control with submersible electric centrifugal pumps in periodic operation mode <i>Krasnov Andrey Nikolaevich, Prakhova Marina Yuryevna, Al-Qadasi Omar Khaled A. A., Vasil'ev Andrey Nikolaevich</i>	115
Decision-making algorithm in a cognitive dynamic diagnostic and stabilization system <i>Chernyadyev Ivan Valerievich, Muler Vladislav Dmitrievich, Bondarchuk Victoria Valerievna</i>	124

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

The conceptual essence of the sustainable development paradigm <i>Perederieva Svetlana Aleksandrovna</i>	131
Building a Green Corridor: China-Türkiye Partnership in Renewable Energy <i>Nikitin Egor Nikolaevich</i>	136
Changes in economic behavior in the face of declining incomes: behavioral and adaptation aspects <i>Isakova Anastasia Romanovna, Razumovskaya Elena Aleksandrovna</i>	145
Approaches to the management of innovation activities in the spheres of economic activity <i>Farzaliyev Elshad Abdulla</i>	152
Marketing as a tool for competitive pressure in the pharmaceutical market and a factor in price reduction <i>Lagoda Nikita Aleksandrovich</i>	158

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ETHNOBOTANY-ECOLOGICAL AND ETHNOMEDICAL MATERIALS MEDICINAL PLANTS OF THE BADHYZ FLORA

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of ethnobotanical, ecological, and ethnomedical research on the Badkhyz Upland, which occupies the southeastern part of Turkmenistan. Currently, there are approximately 1,100 species of higher plants in the region. Currently, more than 600 species of medicinal plants from the Badhyz flora are used in traditional medicine for various ailments. Some of these plants are of interest as medicinal raw materials for industrial harvesting, while others serve as an invaluable gene pool and can be used for introduction into culture.*

Keywords: *natural resources, Badhyz, endemic, Turkmen folk medicine, decoctions.*

The Badhyz Upland, with its characteristic vegetation cover, occupies the south-eastern edge of Turkmenistan. Currently, there are about 1,100 species of higher plants here. Approximately 75 endemic species grow on the Badhyzh Upland, at least 60 of which are found on the territory belonging to Turkmenistan [1; 2]. Currently, more than 600 species of medicinal plants from the Badhyzh flora are used in folk medicine to treat various diseases.

The purpose of the study. To study the bioecological characteristics and medical, ecological and ethnobotanical aspects of certain medicinal plants, using standard methods to determine their natural reserves growing in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve and adjacent territories.

Materials and research methods

During expeditions organised to the Badhyz State Nature Reserve and adjacent territories in 2020–2025, the bioecological characteristics were studied of certain

medicinal plants, and their natural reserves were determined using standard methods [4]. Information on the use of these plants in traditional medicine was collected through oral sociological surveys of the local population (Ethnobotanical and Ethnomedical Questionnaires) [6]. Below is information on medicinal plants studied by the authors based on their own observations.

The results of the study

Malacocarpus crithmifolius (Retz.) S. A. Mey. is a semi-shrub of the Peganaceae family (Tiegh.) with a height of 80–120 cm. The flowers are solitary, located on shoots opposite the leaves. The fruit is berry-like, brownish-red and rounded. It grows at an altitude of 800–1200 m above sea level, on clayey and gravelly soils, sandy-saline sites, rocks, pebble beds, and cliffs. It blooms in May–July and bears fruit in June–August. The plant is found in Badkhyz: Nardivanly, Gyazgyadyk, Serhetabad [2; 4]. The soft-fruited plant is one of the rare plants of Badkhyz. Its reserves are insufficient for medicinal purposes. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [3].

In folk medicine, decoctions of the leaves and fruits of the soft-fruited plant are used for colds and stomach diseases. In Turkmen folk medicine, decoctions and syrups of the plant's fruits are used for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. In traditional medicine, the phytoncidal properties of medicinal preparations based on the leaves and fruits have been identified.

Ephedra intermedia (*Ephedra intermedia* Schrenk et S. A. Meu.) is an evergreen shrub of the Ephedraceae family (*Ephedraceae* Dumort.) with a height of 50–100 cm. The leaves are scaly. The fruits are red, fleshy, juicy and sweet. It grows at an altitude of 600–1200 m above sea level, on the slopes of the foothills, on rocks, on bumpy sands, gravelly and rocky slopes. The plant is found in Badkhyz: Gyazgyadyk, Pulikhatum, Pynkhancheshme, Kerlek, Akarcheshme, Kepele, Kyzyljar [2; 4]. The middle juniper is not one of the rare plants of Badkhyz. There are sufficient reserves for medicinal purposes.

Among the medicinal plants of our ancestors, juniper is popular among the local population; it is one of the most popular and was widely used for various diseases and for fumigating rooms. It was believed that fresh juniper preserves life, gives a person health and strength, and its «divine» drink drives away disease and death. As a result of pharmacological research, it has been established that leucoanthocyanidins are physiologically active and possess P-vitamin properties.

Ornithogalum arianum Li psky ex Vved. is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Iris family (*Iridaceae* Juss.) with a height of 10–25 cm. It blooms and bears fruit in April–June. It grows at an altitude of 250–1200 m above sea level. The plant is found in Badkhyz: Serhetabad, Childukhtar [2; 5]. *Ornithogalum arianum* is a rare

herbaceous plant. Its natural reserves are insignificant for medicinal purposes. It is protected in the Badhyz State Nature Reserve.

In Turkmen folk medicine, Aryan bird's milk is used for joint pain, osteochondrosis, radiculitis, gout, as a wound-healing agent, for boils, bruises, sprains, headaches, warts, boils, and flu accompanied by coughing. Its bulbs are used for colds and heart failure; its leaves are used for diseases of the digestive tract.

Eminium lehmannii (Bunge) O. Kuntze is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Araceae family (*Araceae* Juss.) with a height of 15–40 cm. The tuber is flattened and spherical. The fruits are white. It grows at an altitude of 100–300 m above sea level on sandy loam soils. It blooms in April and bears fruit in June. The plant is found in Badhyzh: Eroylanduz [2; 5]. Endemic to the Middle Apas, insufficient data. Protected in the Bathkiz State Nature Reserve.

In Turkmen folk medicine, a mixture of powdered tubers and fat tail fat is used externally for rheumatism and radiculitis, as well as decoctions and infusions of tubers are used for skin diseases, psoriasis, boils and dermatomycoses.

Merendera jolantae Czerniak is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Liliaceae* Juss. family, 10–15 cm tall. The bulb is ovoid and flattened. The flowers are white, rarely pale pink. It grows at an altitude of 400–1200 m above sea level on shallow slopes. It blooms and bears fruit in February–May. The plant is found in Badhyzh: Gyazgyadyk, Yeroylanduz, Kyzyljar [2; 5]. Iolanta's merender is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyzh. Its reserves for medicinal purposes are insignificant.

In Turkmen folk medicine, decoctions, water and alcohol infusions of corms are prescribed for malignant neoplasms, gout, polyarthritis, psoriasis, and also as a hypotensive, laxative and antitumour agent.

Eremurus inderiensis (Stev.) Regel is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Liliaceae* family, 60–80 cm tall. The roots are thin and fleshy. It grows at an altitude of 200–600 m above sea level, on sandy takyr-like and light grey soils, often in clusters. It blooms in April–May and bears fruit in May–June. The plant is found in Badhyzh: Gyazgyadyk, Kyzyljar [2; 5]. *Eremurus inderiensis* is not one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badhyzh. Natural reserves are sufficient for medicinal purposes.

In Turkmen folk medicine, decoctions and tinctures of the roots are used as a tonic, sedative, and for colds; decoctions and infusions of the herb are used as a carminative and antitumour agent for throat cancer. In scientific medicine, the roots of the plant are a source of eremuran.

Ungernia badhyysi Botsch.— bathyz gaýraýy. Köplenç. Bathyz State Nature Reserve and adjacent territories: Serhetabat, Gyzyljar, Akarcheshme, Kepele, Kerlek, Pynhancheshme. Gyazgyadyk. Bulbous polycarpic (Badhyzh-Afgan type). Perennial herb PCh: in folk medicine [1; 10; 32; 38].

Ungernia badhyysi (*Ungernia badhyysi* Botsch.) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Amaryllidaceae family (Amaryllidaceae Jaume) with a height of 20–40

cm. It grows at an altitude of 400–1200 m above sea level, in river valleys and on shallow slopes. It blooms in July–September and bears fruit in September–October. The plant is found in Badkhyz: Serhetabad, Kyzyljr, Akarcheshme, Kepele, Kerlek, Pynkhancheshme, Gyazgyadyk. Endemic to Turkmenistan [1; 2; 5]. *Ungeria badkhyzskaya* is not one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are sufficient for medicinal purposes. It is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve.

In Turkmen folk medicine, the bulbs are used as a sedative for nervous disorders; externally, a tincture made from the bulbs and leaves is used for concussions, rheumatism, diseases of the nervous system, bladder and urinary tract.

Dark purple gladiolus (*Gladiolus atroviolaceus* Boiss.) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Iris family (*Iridaceae* Juss.) 30–40 cm tall. The corms are surrounded by strong fibrous remnants of old leaves. The corolla is black-purple. It grows at an altitude of 600–1200 m above sea level on shallow, gravelly slopes. It flowers and fruits in May–August. The plant is found in Badkhyz: Serhetabad, Gyazgyadyk, Nardivanly. Endemic to Turkmenistan [1; 2; 5]. Dark purple spikenard is not one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are sufficient for medicinal purposes.

In Turkmen folk medicine, crushed bulbs are used for poultices for toothache and applied to wounds and ulcers to promote healing.

Smyrniun cordifolium Boiss (*S. androssovii* Korov.) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Apiaceae* Lindl. family, 30–50 cm tall. It blooms in April and bears fruit in May. It grows at an altitude of 400–800 m above sea level. The plant is found near the Kushka River and the village of Serkhetchi, on the Gyazgedik Ridge. This is the only habitat of the species in all of Central Asia. Endemic to Badkhyz [1; 5]. *Smirnia cordifolia* is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insignificant for medicinal purposes. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve. Listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [3].

In Turkmen folk medicine, the herb and decoctions and infusions of the fruits of *Smirnia cordifolia* are used for skin diseases, inflammatory processes, rheumatism, and joint damage.

Bryonia monoica Aitch. et Hemsl is a perennial herbaceous plant of the *Cucurbitaceae* Juss. family with a vine length of 2–4 m. It flowers and bears fruit in April–June. It grows at an altitude of 400–800 m above sea level. The plant is found in Yarylangala. In April 2024, we discovered and recorded new habitats of the species in the Nardivanli and Dam-dam gorges for the first time [6]. Monocarpic pasque flower is one of the rare herbaceous plants of Badkhyz. Natural reserves are insignificant for medicinal purposes. It is recommended to introduce it into cultivation. It is protected in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve. It is listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024) [3].

In Turkmen folk medicine, decoctions, infusions, and syrups made from the root of the monoecious peristupnya are used for chronic gout, rheumatism, neuralgia, and joint damage. The herb is used as a haemostatic agent for uterine bleeding, an analgesic, laxative and anthelmintic; the fruits are used for rheumatism, fainting spells, haemorrhoids and headaches.

Conclusions

Malacocarpus crithmifolius, *Smyrniun cordifolium* and *Bryonia monoica* are listed in the Red Book of Turkmenistan (2024). It is necessary to monitor the status of natural populations of these plants, study the bioecology of species both in nature and in cultivation, and search for new habitats.

Scientific data on new habitats of *Bryonia monoica* are presented for the first time. They can be used in future editions of Flora of Turkmenistan, Identification Guide to Plants of Turkmenistan, Identification Guide to Plants of Central Asia, and Red Book of Turkmenistan.

Medicinal plants growing in the Badkhyz State Nature Reserve and adjacent territories can serve as environmentally friendly medicinal raw materials for the manufacture of preparations used for diseases of the kidneys and urinary tract, heart and blood vessels, gastrointestinal tract, liver, gallbladder, skin, and rheumatism. In addition, they can be widely used in a number of areas of modern medicine, such as cardiology, urology, dermatology, gastroenterology, oncology, ophthalmology and pulmonology.

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INFLUENCE OF PHYTOHORMONES ON PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PROCESSES OF WHEAT GRAIN (TRITICUM L.)

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The article presents the results of a study on the influence of phytohormones (RGB, IUK, and GK) at different concentrations on the dynamics of mass increase of a single wheat grain of the Navruz and Vatan varieties. It was found that phytohormones activate physiological processes (water uptake, cell growth) and biochemical processes (enzyme activation, hydrolysis of storage compounds), thereby accelerating seed germination. The most pronounced effect was observed at concentrations of 0.01–0.1%. Differences between the varieties are explained by their physiological and genetic characteristics.

Keywords: *wheat, phytohormones, germination, swelling, physiological processes, biochemical processes, grain mass.*

Introduction. Wheat (*Triticum L.*) is one of the most important cereal crops worldwide, playing a key role in ensuring food security. Enhancing its germination and initial development is a crucial factor in achieving high yields. The seed germination stage is a sensitive phase in plant ontogenesis, during which complex physiological and biochemical processes take place.

Seed germination begins with water uptake and proceeds with the activation of metabolism, enzyme synthesis, and the utilization of endosperm resources. In this process, phytohormones serve a critical role as growth regulators. They

can modify cellular activity, control the rate of germination, and affect seed mass increase even at very low concentrations.

Despite extensive knowledge regarding the role of phytohormones, their influence on the dynamics of mass increase in wheat grains, dependent on variety and concentration, remains a significant scientific challenge. Thus, the study of this issue holds both theoretical and practical significance.

Literature Review. According to the literature, seed germination is divided into three phases: the imbibition phase, the latent phase, and the active growth phase (Bewley et al., 2013). During the first phase, water penetrates the cells, and the colloidal structure of the protoplasm is restored. In the second phase, activation of respiration and protein synthesis is observed. The third phase is characterized by active cell growth and root emergence.

Phytohormones, including auxins, gibberellins, and cytokinins, exert a direct effect on these processes. Gibberellins stimulate the synthesis of α -amylase in the aleurone layer, promoting the hydrolysis of starch into soluble sugars (Taiz et al., 2015). Auxins enhance membrane permeability, thereby accelerating the uptake of water and ions (Davies, 2010).

Researchers highlight that the effect of phytohormones is optimal: low concentrations stimulate the processes, whereas high concentrations may have an inhibitory effect (Arteca, 2014). This pattern has been confirmed in numerous cereal crops.

Materials and Methods. The objects of this study were wheat seeds of the Navruz and Vatan varieties. For the experiment, the phytohormones GBA (gibberellin solution), IAA (indoleacetic acid), and GA (gibberellic acid) were used at concentrations of 0.001 %, 0.01 %, and 0.1 %. Water was used as the control sample.

The seeds were stored under laboratory conditions, and the average weight of a single grain was measured at intervals of 8, 16, 24, 32, 40, 48, 56, and 64 hours. Moreover, seed weight was measured before and after swelling. The results were analyzed using standard statistical methods.

Results and Discussion. The increase in wheat grain mass is primarily attributed to water uptake (swelling) and the activation of physiological and biochemical processes. During the initial hours, the mass increase is mainly due to tissue swelling; however, from 16 to 24 hours onward, enzyme activation, degradation of stored substances, and increased osmotic pressure play the principal roles.

The dynamics of changes in the amount of absorbed water during the growth of two wheat varieties (Navruz and Vatan), depending on the duration of treatment over 64 hours, were investigated and presented.

Differences in the rate and intensity, as well as the retardation of water absorption, are presumed to partially reflect the nature of biochemical processes occurring during the swelling phase at a specific time or experimental period (Asoev et al., 2019).

Swelling of seeds was observed during water diffusion and the hydrostatic process. In this case, the activity of enzymes, including biosynthetic enzymes of nucleic acids, stimulates the regeneration and accumulation of organic compounds, which leads to the regulation of osmotic water absorption. These two processes generally constitute a single physical phenomenon; thus, the osmotic hydrolysis of reserve compounds and the regeneration of compounds during seed germination are closely interrelated. The process of seed swelling, their sowing quality, and the ratio of hydrostatic to osmotic flows are of significant importance in this context, and their assessment requires a specialized approach and comprehensive methodological investigation. This enables consideration of the transition time from hydrostatic water absorption to osmotic uptake, which in most cases constitutes an important parameter for evaluation. Seed quality is associated with a more rapid transition of water uptake from hydrostatic to osmotic processes, which in turn leads to improved crop quality.

The rapid transition from hydrostatic to osmotic processes may vary depending on the genotypic characteristics of different cultivars. Therefore, unlike the hygroscopic absorption of water during the osmotic process, in many cases, the regular influx of water into seeds depends on the water demand level during germination, as observed empirically.

Temperature can influence not only the germination process itself but also the quantity of water absorbed by the seeds.

Dry seeds contain only bound water and must imbibe water to swell in order to germinate; that is, they must absorb a certain amount of water necessary to activate enzymes and establish conditions favorable for biochemical reactions.

Phytohormones accelerate seed mass increase compared to the water control, particularly at concentrations of 0.01–0.1%, which favor water uptake and the initiation of germination. Their effects vary depending on the wheat variety, reflecting the physiological and genetic characteristics of the cultivar. In general, phytohormones stimulate the early stages of germination and promote a more consistent increase in seed mass (Table 1).

Water absorption in the seeds of the Navruz and Vatan varieties varies depending on the measurement time at different concentrations of the IAA solution.

For both Navruz and Vatan varieties, a gradual increase in seed mass is observed during the first 24 hours of germination at all concentrations, followed by fluctuations in water absorption thereafter. Water absorption in the Vatan variety does not significantly vary depending on the concentration of IAA; however, at a concentration of 0.1%, this parameter is occasionally not observed during continuous measurement.

The data in the table indicate that, in all variants, mass increase occurs gradually. During the first 8–16 hours, the increase is relatively slow and primarily due to water absorption. This stage is predominantly physiological, while biochemical changes remain limited.

Table 1.
Dynamics of the mass increase of a single wheat grain depending on
phytohormone concentration, g.

Experimental variants	Concentration (%)	Time (hours)								Average weight of one grain, g.	
		8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	Before swelling	After swelling
Navruz variety											
Water (control sample)		0.532	0.541	0.564	0.599	0.608	0.624	0.684	0.714	0.422	0.608
Gibberellic acid (GA3)	0.001	0.533	0.549	0.583	0.622	0.654	0.667	0.688	0.705	0.422	0.625
	0.01	0.529	0.549	0.658	0.523	0.654	0.697	0.702	0.733	0.422	0.630
	0.1	0.531	0.549	0.613	0.637	0.641	0.678	0.687	0.724	0.422	0.633
Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)	0.001	0.534	0.549	0.558	0.623	0.605	0.664	0.697	0.704	0.422	0.616
	0.01	0.530	0.546	0.571	0.624	0.648	0.664	0.679	0.711	0.422	0.621
	0.1	0.543	0.562	0.575	0.62	0.658	0.675	0.685	0.721	0.422	0.629
Cytokinin (CK)	0.001	0.492	0.512	0.542	0.585	0.613	0.634	0.654	0.669	0.422	0.587
	0.01	0.528	0.539	0.584	0.603	0.651	0.658	0.686	0.702	0.422	0.618
	0.1	0.533	0.549	0.584	0.619	0.624	0.665	0.596	0.705	0.422	0.609
Vatan variety											
Water (control sample)		0.522	0.535	0.564	0.574	0.592	0.634	0.674	0.699	0.419	0.599
Gibberellic acid (GA3)	0.001	0.503	0.529	0.575	0.623	0.645	0.687	0.693	0.714	0.419	0.621
	0.01	0.523	0.539	0.588	0.599	0.614	0.695	0.702	0.724	0.419	0.623
	0.1	0.533	0.569	0.585	0.603	0.619	0.667	0.761	0.703	0.419	0.619
Indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)	0.001	0.537	0.549	0.557	0.603	0.639	0.664	0.696	0.710	0.419	0.619
	0.01	0.539	0.548	0.564	0.578	0.613	0.634	0.679	0.717	0.419	0.609
	0.1	0.546	0.562	0.574	0.586	0.597	0.625	0.684	0.713	0.419	0.610
Cytokinin (CK)	0.001	0.490	0.510	0.532	0.570	0.587	0.634	0.653	0.673	0.419	0.581
	0.01	0.538	0.43	0.584	0.603	0.621	0.658	0.687	0.712	0.419	0.618
	0.1	0.530	0.539	0.554	0.599	0.609	0.660	0.698	0.714	0.419	0.612

Between 24 and 40 hours, the rate of mass increase accelerates. This is associated with the activation of respiration, increased ATP synthesis, and enzyme activation. At this stage, the effect of phytohormones is clearly evident compared to the control.

In most cases, phytohormones resulted in an increase in the mass of individual grains compared to the control sample. The greatest efficacy was observed at

concentrations of 0.01–0.1%. This result aligns with the literature data and confirms the law of the optimal effect of phytohormones.

In certain variants (for example, GA 0.001%), growth was slower, likely due to an insufficient hormone concentration. In some cases, at high concentrations, a decrease in effectiveness was observed, which may indicate an inhibitory effect.

Varietal studies indicate that the Navruz variety demonstrated greater mass in most variants. This is physiologically explained by its high water absorption capacity, elevated enzymatic activity, and efficient utilization of endosperm resources. The Vatan variety also demonstrated a positive response; however, the growth rates were relatively lower, which can be explained by genetic characteristics.

In conclusion, the study demonstrated that the increase in the mass of a single wheat grain results from the integration of physiological (water absorption, cell growth) and biochemical (enzyme activation, degradation of stored substances) processes. Phytohormones at optimal concentrations accelerate these processes and stimulate seed germination. Differences between varieties depend on their physiological and genetic characteristics.

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MODIFICATION OF THE DUODENAL MICROBIOTA OF LAYING HENS

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Abstract. *The effects of steaming complete laying hens' feed and adding compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, E) to the formula to correct heat-induced losses were studied. Experiments conducted on Super Nick laying hens revealed significant changes in the quantitative composition of the resident microflora of the duodenum.*

Keywords: *fat-soluble vitamins, steaming of compound feed, poultry gastrointestinal microbiota, duodenum, egg-laying poultry farming, laying hens.*

Introduction

The modern intensification of poultry farming requires the development of new technological solutions aimed at maximizing the genetic potential of poultry while ensuring optimal health and producing high-quality products. One of the key factors in this area is the optimization of compound feed rations, which would both provide the body with nutrients and manage the physiological and immunological status of poultry [1]. A key role here is played by the functional composition and diversity of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) microbiota of poultry, which represents a complex ecosystem of microorganisms that influence feed digestion, the endogenous synthesis of certain vitamins, the integrity of the intestinal barrier, and the systemic immune status of the host organism. Being the first microbial community to contact feed hydrolyzed in the stomach, it plays a significant role in the absorption of nutrients, the development of colonization resistance, and the modulation of systemic immunity [2, 3].

In modern feed production, in addition to calculating the optimal vitamin balance in the diet, it is necessary to account for and predict potential secondary vitamin losses arising from various feed production factors, particularly heat treatment (steam treatment).

Heat treatment improves feed digestibility and ensures the biological safety of poultry farms, reducing the risk of infectious disease spread. However, the downside

is the partial inactivation of heat-labile vitamin molecules in the feed matrix. It is important to note that reference data on vitamin losses are only estimates, as the actual preservation of biologically active substances is determined by the unique combination of feed formulation and the specific processing technology [4, 5].

The relevance of this study is due to the practical importance of monitoring and predicting heat-induced losses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, E) that occur in feed during steam treatment. A study was conducted to examine the influence of the factor of artificially created deficiency of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, E) in the diet, caused by heat treatment of feed, on the microbiological parameters of laying hens (the composition of the gastrointestinal microbiota).

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on laying hens (*Gallus gallus domesticus*, layers, cross *Super Nick*) in the experimental poultry house of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Bashkir State Agrarian University, Ufa, Republic of Bashkortostan. For this stage of the experiment, three groups of 21 laying hens each were formed at 245 days of age, with a nine-month study period. The feeding regimen for the experimental birds included three diets: the control group consumed a basic feed without heat treatment; the first experimental group consumed a feed that had been heat-treated; and the second experimental group consumed a heat-treated feed with additional levels of vitamins A, D3, and E to compensate for their losses.

The experimental birds were housed in standard windowless poultry houses. The rearing and housing conditions, microclimate parameters, lighting regime, stocking density, and feeding space corresponded to generally accepted industry standards.

A study of the duodenal microbiota of laying hens was conducted at the L. K. Ernst Federal Research Center for Animal Husbandry (Podolsk, Moscow Region). Duodenal samples were collected at slaughter and necropsy on the final day of the experiment.

Statistical analysis of the results was performed using Microsoft Office Excel. Normality of distribution was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test, and the significance of differences between groups was assessed using the Student t-test.

Results and discussion

The microbiota of the small intestine of poultry is an integrated system, highly sensitive to fluctuations in the composition and quality of the diet. Since this is the region where active interaction between chyme and resident microflora begins, monitoring its composition is crucial for preventing dysbiosis and the development of pathogenic microflora [3]. The figures below show the dynamics of changes in the quantitative composition of the main groups of microorganisms that make up

the microbiota of the duodenum of laying hens. The analysis revealed the main functional groups of microorganisms: lactobacilli (*gen. Lactobacillus*, Figure 1), enterococci (*gen. Enterococcus*, Figure 2), lactose-positive (*gen. Escherichia*, lac+, Figure 3) and lactose-negative *Escherichia coli* (*gen. Escherichia*, lac-, Figure 4).

Figure 1. Lactobacillus content in duodenal microbiota of laying hens

Figure 2. Enterococcus content in duodenal microbiota of laying hens

Figure 3. Lactose-negative E.coli content in duodenal microbiota of laying hens

Figure 4. Lactose-positive E.coli content in duodenal microbiota of laying hens

As can be seen from the presented data, lactobacilli are the dominant genus in the control and experimental groups, which confirms their key role in the normal flora of the gastrointestinal tract of poultry. According to the intergroup dynamics, an exponential increase in the number of normal microflora representatives can be observed in the experimental groups compared to the control: lactobacilli (from

1.5*10³ CFU/g in the control to 13*10³ CFU/g in the Treatment 2), enterococci (from 1*10³ CFU/g in the control to 2.5*10³ CFU/g in the Treatment 2), lactose-positive *E. coli* (from 0.1*10² CFU/g in the control to 3.5*10² CFU/g in the Treatment 2). At the same time, negative intergroup dynamics were recorded in terms of the quantitative ratio of lactose-negative *E. coli*; its quantity decreased from 5.0*10² CFU/g in the control to 0.5*10² CFU/g in the Treatment 2.

Thus, the study results confirm the significant effectiveness of heat treatment of compound feed in combination with adjustments to fat-soluble vitamin levels on the composition and quantitative parameters of the duodenal microbiota of laying hens, which may indicate a pronounced prebiotic effect of the experimental factors. Moreover, the feeding strategy implemented in this experiment resulted in a significant increase in the abundance of dominant and associated beneficial bacteria (lactobacilli, enterococci, and lactose-positive *E. coli*) and a significant suppression of opportunistic lactose-negative *E. coli*. This likely confirms the fact that steam treatment of feed increases the availability of nutrients for lactobacilli, while fat-soluble vitamins, with their immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties, may contribute to the formation of a more favorable intestinal mucosal environment for symbiotic microflora. Therefore, it can be concluded that heat treatment of feed is the primary factor improving the availability of nutrients and the sanitary quality of feed [6].

Conclusions

The proposed feeding strategy, which combines steam treatment of compound feed with the introduction of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins, has a significant positive effect, leading to an improvement in the duodenal microbiota of laying hens. This approach can be recommended to poultry nutritionists as a way to enhance the body's natural resistance and, consequently, increase the productivity of laying hens.

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QUALITY OF DIETARY EGGS

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Abstract. *The effect of steaming laying hens' feed and adding compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, and E) to the formula to correct heat-induced vitamin loss on the yolk vitamin profile and protein quality of edible chicken eggs was studied. The study was conducted on Super Nick laying hens. The experiments revealed significant changes in the vitamin A content and Haugh units measurement in the yolk of laying hens' eggs.*

Key words: *fat-soluble vitamins, vitamin A, dietary eggs, Haugh units, steam treatment of the feed, laying hens.*

Introduction

Modern industrial poultry farming plays a key role in the country's agro-industrial complex, ensuring its food security. One of the most significant and stable segments of this sector is the production of commercial eggs. A key factor determining egg productivity is the range of feeding and housing conditions implemented at poultry farms [1].

The quality of commercial eggs, as one of the key elements of a poultry farm's production chain, is an integral indicator demonstrating the effectiveness of management practices implemented at all stages of the product life cycle. In this case, an important factor influencing egg production is the complex of feeding and housing conditions for poultry, which, in particular, is very sensitive to a lack

of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, E) in feed. It is associated with a number of its biological characteristics — a high level of metabolism, rapid movement of feed through the gastrointestinal tract, insufficient synthesis of endogenous vitamins in the body when kept in closed cages, etc. [2, 3].

The relevance of this study is based on the need to monitor and predict the loss of fat-soluble vitamins in feed during steam treatment caused by exposure to high-temperature steam. **The aim** of the experiment was to study the effect of this factor on vitamin A levels in egg yolks and to determine the Hough units in the eggs of Super Nick laying hens.

Materials and methods

The subjects of our study were laying hens, cross Super Nick, kept in the experimental poultry house of the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Bashkir State Agrarian University, Ufa, Republic of Bashkortostan. Three groups of 21 laying hens each, 35 weeks old, were randomly assigned to three groups. The experiment was conducted from January to September 2025. The control group consumed a basal diet (loose feed without heat treatment). The first experimental group was fed heat-treated compound feed. The second experimental group received the same high-temperature steam-treated compound feed as the first experimental group, but with additional vitamins A, D3, and E to compensate for their losses during heat treatment. The determination of compensatory levels of fat-soluble vitamins was based on the results of pilot tests previously obtained in the laboratory at the AVNutriSmart LLC premix plant in Orenburg, Russia.

During the preparatory phase of the experiment (the first 7 days), all birds were fed a basic diet. Upon transition to the recording period, the control group remained on the same diet, while the experimental groups were switched to feed that had undergone heat treatment according to the corresponding experimental modifications.

The vitamin A (retinol) content in quail and chicken egg yolks was determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) at the AVNutriSmart LLC production laboratory. Haugh units were measured using the formula $HU = 100 \times \text{Log}_{10}(H - 1.7W^{0.37} + 7.6)$, where: HU — Haugh unit; H — measured albumen height (in millimeters); W — egg weight (in grams).

The data obtained during the study were statistically processed using Microsoft Office Excel. The Shapiro-Wilk test was also performed to analyze the distribution for normality. The Student's t-test was used to assess the significance of differences between groups.

Results and discussion

Assessing the vitamin A content in the yolk serves as an integral marker of its absorption and storage in the bird’s body, which is directly related to the functioning of the gastrointestinal tract. In this experiment, the vitamin A content in the yolks of laying hens was analyzed to investigate the nature and extent of its accumulation depending on the effects of experimental feeding factors (Figure 1).

b - *p≤ 0.01

Figure 1. Vitamin A (retinol) content in egg yolk

As can be seen from the information presented in the figure, the content of vitamin A (retinol) in the yolk of eggs of laying hens from the experimental group consuming non-thermally processed feed was 9.08 mg/kg, while in the group consuming only thermally processed feed (Treatment 1); a tendency towards a slight, statistically insignificant decrease in the level of this vitamin to 8.52 mg/kg (−6.17% compared to the control) was noted, which may indicate the degradation of some vitamin A during the heat treatment of the feed mixture and, accordingly, its insufficient intake by the poultry body. In the Treatment 2 group, consuming thermally processed feed with the introduction of additional doses of fat-soluble vitamins, the content of vitamin A was 9.86 mg/kg (+8.59% compared to the control, p≤0.01). Thus, based on the nature of the intergroup dynamics of vitamin A content in egg yolk, there may be observed a dose-dependent positive response of the laying hens’ body to the introduction of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins into the diet of the Treatment 2 group.

One of the parameters characterizing egg freshness is the Haugh unit. All other factors being equal (bird age, genetics, farm management characteristics, etc.), the Haugh unit is significantly affected by the diet composition [4, 5]. As can be seen

from the data presented in the Figure 2, this measurement demonstrates positive dynamics from the control to the experimental group 2, achieving a statistically significant positive difference compared to the control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

Figure. 2. Haugh units measurement

In this case, the positive dynamics of Haugh units correlates with an improvement in the vitamin profile of the yolk and the introduction of additional doses of fat-soluble vitamins into the diet, which have a positive effect on the synthesis of protein components in the poultry ovary and oviduct (vitamin D3), the health of the mucous membranes of the poultry digestive tract (vitamin A), and resistance to oxidative processes in the body (vitamin E).

Conclusions

Experimental studies have shown that heat treatment (steam treatment) of compound feed with the addition of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D3, E) has a significant positive effect on the vitamin profile of the yolk and the freshness of chicken eggs. Thus, the combined use of heat treatment of feed with dietary optimization through the introduction of compensatory doses of fat-soluble vitamins substantiates an effective concept for maintaining vitamin balance in modern feed production conditions.

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FEATURES OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY IN CHILDHOOD

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Abstract. Data from monitoring children receiving inpatient treatment at the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care (RNCEPM) between 2016 and 2021 for SCTBI (Group 1), and between 2022 and 2024 (Group 2), were analyzed. Children in Group 1 were admitted to the clinic due to RTI (23 cases) and falls from height (11 cases); in Group 2, RTI accounted for 32 cases, with polytrauma observed in 5 children. Despite the absence of significant differences in injury severity, the extent of acute cerebrovascular accident, and mean parameters of the phase structure of CR DBP on admission, a significant improvement in intensive therapy outcomes was observed, reflecting increased treatment efficacy in the majority of children with SCCTBI in Group 2 (2022–2024). More effective treatment of children in group 2 was demonstrated by a reduction in the number of patients in the ICU to three by day 11, whereas in group 1 this reduction occurred only by day 22. In group 2, a more effective conservative intensive therapy was observed, resulting in a reduction of the duration of conservative intensive therapy by 11 days in subgroup 1. For patients undergoing extracranial surgeries, the duration of ICU stay in group 2 was reduced by 9 days.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, diastolic blood pressure, severe combined traumatic brain injury, children.

Relevance. Currently, mechanisms of secondary brain injury developing under the influence of intracranial and extracranial factors are considered potentially reversible. Most authors consider that early detection and elimination of these mechanisms constitute the primary goal in the treatment of patients with traumatic brain injury. Indications for urgent neurosurgical intervention in severe TBI include the presence of epidural, intracerebral, or subdural hematomas, tension pneumocephalus, obstructive hydrocephalus, depressed skull fracture, and penetrating cranio-cerebral injury resulting in brain compression. This is demonstrated on CT by a midline shift of brain structures and compression of the basal cisterns. Clinically, these correspond to various, including pathognomonic, generalized and focal cerebral symptoms. The presented results and conducted studies enhance the effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy in children with SCCTBI, do not exhaust the potential for improving prognosis, reduce the degree of disability among injured children, and facilitate their reintegration into the social environment following severe traumatic illness [1–5]. In this context, we sought to analyze and provide a comparative evaluation of comprehensive intensive therapy during different time periods, from 2016 to 2021 and from 2022 to 2024, when substantial organizational measures were undertaken to reorganize the emergency service, aimed at minimizing the interval from the moment of injury to the provision of urgent specialized care, with the nearly simultaneous implementation of necessary resuscitative and surgical procedures.

Objective of the study. To study and assess the characteristics of the circadian rhythm of diastolic blood pressure in surgically treated pediatric patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods. Data from monitoring of children hospitalized at the RNCEPM with SCTBI from 2016 to 2021 (Group 1) and from 2022 to 2024 (Group 2) were analyzed. Children in Group 1 were admitted due to RTI (23 cases) and falls from height (11 cases); in Group 2, RTI accounted for 32 cases and polytrauma for 5 children. In both groups, an analysis of indicators was performed in three subgroups: the first subgroup comprised patients who received conservative therapy due to the absence of indications for surgical intervention; the second subgroup included children who underwent extracranial surgeries; and the third subgroup consisted of patients who underwent both cranial and extracranial surgeries within the first 24 hours after admission to the clinic. In the first group, 13 patients in the first subgroup received conservative therapy based on indications; in the second subgroup, 16 children underwent extracranial corrective surgical procedures within the first hours based on indications; and in the third subgroup, 8 patients underwent simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions upon admission, involving a neurosurgeon, a general surgeon, and a traumatologist. In the second group, conservative therapy was administered to

13 children, extracranial surgeries were performed on 16 patients, and combined cranial and extracranial surgeries were carried out in 8 children. No significant age differences were identified between the groups (Table 1). In group 1, boys predominated in subgroups 3 and 2, constituting 29% and 26%, respectively. Conversely, in group 1, girls predominated, comprising 23%. In group 2, boys were more numerous in subgroups 1, 2, and 3, accounting for 24%, 24%, and 19%, respectively. Thus, in nearly all subgroups, boys slightly predominated in number. No statistically significant differences in injury severity or the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency upon admission to the clinic were observed between the subgroups of group 1. A slight tendency toward reduced severity of traumatic injuries was noted across the subgroups of group 2. Specifically, the differences amounted to 25% in subgroup 1 (>0.05), 44% in subgroup 2 ($p<0.05$), and 27% in subgroup 3 ($p<0.05$). With clinical improvement, including stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and recovery of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department. The findings indicate the absence of significant differences in the severity of acute cerebrovascular accident according to the Glasgow scale between groups and subgroups. The observed difference in injury severity according to the ISS scale in the 2nd and 3rd subgroups of group 2 can be explained by the effectiveness of implementing prehospital care according to the ‘golden hour’ principle, minimizing prehospital time in trauma cases.

Table 1. Comparative assessment of patients depending on injury severity

Parameters studied	Group 1 (2016–2021)			Group 2 (2022–2024)		
	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3
Number of biochemical parameters	32% (11)	38% (13)	30% (10)	37% (13)	42% (16)	21% (8)
Age, years	8,6±3,1	9,1±4,3	8,2±3,4	10,3±3,9	10,1±4,4	11,5±3,8
Boys	11% (4)	26% (9)	29% (10)	24% (9)	24% (9)	19% (7)
Girls	23% (7)	11% (4)	0	10% (4)	19% (7)	4% (1)
Days in ICU	17,9±5,7	12,3±6,8	20,8±8,8	11,5±9,3	8,3±6,8	8,3±2,4
ISS, points	33,7±5,8	40,5±6,5	41,3±4,6	25,2±3,4	22,3±2,8*	29,9±3,4*
SGL, points	7,9±3,5	7,5±0,8	6,6±0,6	7,4±1,0	8,2±1,0	6,5±0,6

* Difference from the value in Group 1 is statistically significant.

Monitoring was performed by comprehensive hourly recording of body temperature, hemodynamic, and respiratory parameters. Mechanical respiratory

support was initiated with artificial lung ventilation (ALV) for a short period, followed by transition to SIMV.

Results and Their Discussion. One of the objective indicators of peripheral hemodynamic status is the DBP value. Alterations in cardiac function during acute severe stress conditions are directly dependent on the functional state of peripheral vessels. It has been demonstrated that the longer the compensatory vasopressor state persists, the more profound, including irreversible, impairments develop in all organs and tissues, particularly in the brain. We attempted to study and evaluate the differences in changes of the circadian rhythm of DBP in both groups of patients with SCCTBI.

Table 2. Comparative assessment of the mean values of the phase structure of CR DBP during 2016–21 and 2022–24.

	Mesor		Acrophase		Bathypphase		Amplitude		Range of fluctuations	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
Subgroup 1, 7 days	63±2	63±3	68±2	71±4	58±3	57±3	5±2	8±4	11±2	14±5
Subgroup 2, 7 days	63±2	62±2	70±3	67±3	59±3	54±5	7±3	5±1	11±4	14±5
Subgroup 3, 7 days	65±2	62±4	73±4	71±7	58±3	55±5	8±3	9±5	15±3	17±5
Subgroup 1, 30 days	64±2	66±3	70±3	76±5	57±5	57±4	6±2	10±3	13±4	19±6
Subgroup 2, 30 days	67±4	63±2	75±6	70±3	61±3	55±3	8±3	7±2	15±6	15±4
Three subgroups, 30 days	68±3	68±6	75±4	83±9	61±3	54±6	7±2	15±6	14±3	29±11

No significant differences in CR DBP parameters were identified between the groups. In group 2, there was a trend toward a 100% increase in the amplitude of CR DBP ($p > 0.05$) and a 93% increase in daily DBP fluctuations in the third subgroup compared to the second subgroup during 30 days of intensive therapy in the ICU ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2). This observation reflects the preservation of compensatory mechanisms in response to CTBI in the most severely affected patients of group 2 within the third subgroup over the course of 30 days of comprehensive intensive therapy.

With conservative therapy in children of the 2nd group, by the 4th day the number of patients in the ICU decreased by 15%, and by the 11th day by 76%. Whereas in the 1st group, only by the 8th day were 27% of children transferred to specialized departments. Three patients remained in the ICU in the 1st group up to 22 days, and in the 2nd group up to 11 days. After 26 days, only one child remained in the ICU in each group (Fig. 1). Thus, the 2nd group demonstrates more effective conservative intensive therapy, which allowed a reduction in the duration of conservative intensive therapy by 11 days. During extracranial surgeries, two patients remained in intensive therapy for up to 30 days, whereas

the length of stay in the ICU for patients in Group 2 was reduced by 9 days (Fig. 2). In the most severe Group 3, one child remained in the ICU for up to 30 days due to the development of apallic syndrome (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. Number of patients by days in the ICU: 1st subgroup

Fig. 2. Extracranial surgeries of children with SCCTBI (2nd subgroup).

Fig. 3. Number of children in the ICU after cranial and extracranial surgeries (3rd subgroup).

However, the observed difference indicated more effective treatment in children of Group 2, as evidenced by the reduction in the number of patients in the ICU to three by day 11, whereas in Group 1 this reduction occurred only by day 22 (Fig. 3). Thus, despite the absence of significant differences in injury severity, acute cerebrovascular accident severity, and average phase structure indices of the CR DBP upon admission, there was a substantial improvement in the outcomes of intensive therapy, demonstrating increased treatment efficacy in the majority of children affected by SCCTBI. No significant differences were observed between groups or subgroups in the dynamics of intensive therapy in the ICU with respect to the mesor of CR DBP in SCCTBI in children (Table 3), indicating effective stabilization of the peripheral hemodynamic response to SCCTBI during both conservative therapy and extracranial as well as combined craniocerebral and extracranial surgeries in children.

Table 3. Dynamics of the mesor of CR DBP in Group 1 and Group 2

Days	Group 1 (2016–2021)			Group 2 (2022–2024)		
	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3
1	61±3	61±6	62±4	61±4	68±3	64±4
2	60±2	57±2	59±2	57±2	63±2	59±2
3	62±2	62±2	62±2	60±2	64±2	55±3
4	65±1	65±2	65±2	65±2	62±2	60±3

Days	Group 1 (2016–2021)			Group 2 (2022–2024)		
	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3	Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Subgroup 3
5	64±2	67±2	65±3	65±2	64±3	69±2
6	66±2	62±3	64±1	63±3	65±2	68±4
7	65±2	66±4	65±2	63±2	68±2	62±4
8	65±3	65±3	63±1	63±2	68±3	66±6
9	64±1	63±2	65±2	63±3	72±4	71±6
10	64±2	64±4	62±3	62±4	72±3	73±6
11	65±2	63±3	63±3	59±3	70±3	76±8
12	65±2	64±4	66±2	69±5	69±3	69±3
13	62±2	61±4	63±3	65±3	67±4	73±5
14	63±2	65±4	66±2	64±2	69±2	78±6
15	65±2	64±4	68±1	63±3	70±2	83±5
16	64±2	65±6	69±3	64±2	70±2	70±3
17	66±2	66±5	66±2	64±3	66±2	65±4
18	66±3	69±4	70±3	65±3	68±2	68±5
19	67±3	66±4	77±4	63±3	64±2	60±10
20	66±2	66±4	76±3	60±3	63±3	56±5
21	62±3	69±4	65±4	65±9	64±3	62±7
22	68±3	73±6	68±2		62±4	76±10
23	62±3	67±7	72±3		67±2	66±11
24	58±2	68±5	70±5		65±3	60±9
25	62±3	65±5	73±4		67±2	75±11
26	68±4	73±4	74±7		68±3	58±9
27	58±6	73±7	73±3		77±4	70±8
28	59±6	73±4	71±3		74±5	84±16
29	57±7	72±5	69±3		73±4	
30	70±2		70±5		81±2	

Table 4.CR DBP in Group 1.Table 5.CR DBP in Group 2.

Hours	Subgroup 1 7 days	Subgroup 2 7 days	Subgroup 3 7 days	Subgroup 1 30 days	Subgroup 2 30 days	Subgroup 3 30 days
8	65±3	64±3	67±2	64±4	69±6	70±5
9	65±3	64±4	67±3	63±3	68±5	68±4
10	65±2	64±3	66±3	64±3	69±4	67±4
11	65±2	65±5	66±5	64±3	67±5	68±4
12	65±2	63±3	67±6	65±3	68±6	69±5
13	63±4	64±4	66±3	63±4	67±5	68±4
14	64±3	62±2	65±3	64±3	68±5	67±4
15	63±3	63±3	65±2	63±4	67±4	68±4

Hours	Subgroup 1 7 days	Subgroup 2 7 days	Subgroup 3 7 days	Subgroup 1 30 days	Subgroup 2 30 days	Subgroup 3 30 days
16	63±3	65±3	64±2	64±3	67±3	68±4
17	62±4	63±3	65±1	63±4	68±6	68±3
18	64±4	63±3	66±3	65±3	69±5	70±4
19	63±3	62±2	65±2	65±3	68±5	69±4
20	63±2	62±3	66±2	64±3	67±4	69±4
21	64±2	63±2	65±4	63±4	67±4	69±5
22	62±1	65±3	63±2	63±3	68±4	68±4
23	62±2	63±2	64±3	62±3	67±4	67±5
24	63±2	63±1	64±3	61±4	67±5	68±4
1	62±3	63±3	63±4	62±4	68±5	67±5
2	62±2	63±3	63±3	63±2	67±4	66±5
3	63±2	63±2	64±2	62±4	67±5	66±4
4	62±2	63±2	65±2	63±4	67±5	67±4
5	62±1	63±2	63±2	62±4	67±4	68±5
6	64±1	63±3	65±2	63±3	67±4	68±5
7	63±2	62±4	64±2	65±3	66±5	68±5

Table 5. CR DBP in Group 2.

Hours	Subgroup 1 7 days	Subgroup 2 7 days	Subgroup 3 7 days	Subgroup 1 30 days	Subgroup 2 30 days	Subgroup 3 30 days
8	63±3	64±3	62±7	67±5	64±3	66±10
9	64±3	63±2	60±8	68±5	64±3	68±9
10	63±4	63±2	63±5	67±4	65±3	67±10
11	63±3	64±3	65±7	67±5	64±3	70±11
12	64±3	60±7	61±4	68±5	63±5	68±7
13	67±5	63±5	60±2	67±5	63±4	68±9
14	65±3	63±5	60±6	67±4	64±5	70±9
15	65±3	62±3	62±4	66±6	62±4	68±7
16	64±3	62±2	62±4	65±4	61±3	69±8
17	62±3	62±3	63±5	66±5	61±3	69±8
18	64±4	63±3	62±7	68±4	64±3	71±10
19	63±6	63±4	62±7	67±7	63±4	68±8
20	62±5	62±3	62±5	66±6	64±4	68±9
21	64±5	62±2	62±7	68±6	63±3	66±10
22	61±3	61±3	62±6	66±5	62±3	68±10
23	63±4	61±2	63±4	65±4	61±3	68±8
24	63±5	61±3	64±5	66±5	62±3	70±10
1	62±6	58±2	63±5	64±5	62±5	66±9
2	61±4	61±2	62±4	64±6	62±4	65±8

Hours	Subgroup 1 7 days	Subgroup 2 7 days	Subgroup 3 7 days	Subgroup 1 30 days	Subgroup 2 30 days	Subgroup 3 30 days
3	62±4	62±2	63±4	63±5	63±3	68±10
4	62±3	63±2	63±4	63±4	64±3	66±8
5	62±3	64±2	64±4	65±5	65±4	66±7
6	63±4	63±4	63±5	65±4	65±4	64±8
7	61±4	63±3	62±3	65±6	64±4	65±6

No significant differences in the circadian rhythm of DBP were observed between Group 1 and Group 2, as well as among subgroups (Tables 4 and 5).

Fig. 4. Circadian rhythm of DBP in Group 1 over 7 days.

Fig. 5. Mean CR DBP in Group 2 over 7 days.

Fig. 5. Circadian rhythm of DBP in the 1st group in the ICU.

Fig. 6. Average circadian rhythm of DBP in the 2nd group in the ICU.

During the first 7 days of intensive therapy in patients of Group 1, a normal acrophase projection of the CR DBP was identified in the 3rd subgroup, which persisted throughout ICU treatment (Figs. 4 and 5). DBP fluctuations in the 3rd

subgroup during the first 7 days and the entire treatment period were 6 mm Hg. In the 2nd subgroup, DBP fluctuations were the greatest-7 mm Hg. The 1st subgroup exhibited the lowest amplitude of DBP waves over 24 hours.

During 30 days of intensive therapy, peri-circadian fluctuations of DBP occurred at a relatively low-amplitude level in the 1st subgroup (61–65 mm Hg), and at 63–68 mm Hg in the 2nd group. In the 2nd subgroup of Group 1, DBP ranged from 66 to 69 mm Hg, while in Group 2 it ranged from 61 to 65 mm Hg (Figs. 5 and 6).

Fig. 7. Group 1 over 7 days.

Fig. 8. Group 1 over 30 days in the ICU.

During the first 7 days of the acute period in the 1st subgroup of Group 1, a direct correlation between DBP and SBP (0.72) was observed, as well as an inverse correlation between SBP and the number of patients in the ICU by days of observation (-0.7); there was a tendency toward increased SBP associated with hyperthermic response (0.57). In the 2nd subgroup, following extracranial surgeries during the first 7 days, the direct correlation between SBP and DBP strengthened (0.92), whereas in the 3rd subgroup it disappeared entirely (0.06). This finding can be explained by the disruption or loss of central regulatory mechanisms linking cardiac activity and peripheral vascular tone in brain injury caused by CTBI (Fig. 7). It is noteworthy that the prolongation of comprehensive intensive therapy was accompanied by an almost complete disappearance of the correlation between SBP and DBP in the 1st and 2nd subgroups, along with the emergence of a tendency toward a direct relationship between SBP and DBP (0.57) (Fig. 8). Attention should also be drawn to the emergence of an inverse correlation between DBP and body temperature in the 3rd subgroup (-0.78) and a direct correlation between body temperature and the number of patients in the 1st and 3rd subgroups (0.64 and 0.65, respectively), which is associated with prolonged intensive therapy in the context of a hyperthermic response.

In group 2, a strong direct correlation between SBP and DBP in all subgroups (0.76; 0.74; and 0.94, respectively) indicated a direct functional link between central and peripheral hemodynamics during the first 7 days, which was maintained in the third subgroup of injured children, unlike the patients in group 1 (Figures 9 and 10). Strong correlations between SBP and DBP were preserved throughout the entire treatment period in the ICU (0.92; 0.92; and 0.79, respectively). In the second group of children who received conservative therapy within the first seven days, the difference from the corresponding indicators in the first group also consisted of a strong negative correlation between DBP and the number of patients (-0.72), as well as between SBP and the number of patients (-0.87), which can be explained by the positive effect of increased SBP and DBP on the condition of the injured; these correlations decreased (-0.62 and -0.7, respectively) with more prolonged intensive therapy.

Fig. 9. Group 2 over the course of 7 days.

Fig. 10. Group 2 during ICU treatment.

Conclusion. In the absence of significant differences in injury severity, the extent of acute cerebrovascular accident, and average parameters of the phase structure of CR DBP upon admission, a significant improvement in intensive therapy outcomes was observed, reflecting increased treatment efficacy in the majority of children with SCCTBI in Group 2 (2022–2024). The more effective treatment of children in Group

2 was demonstrated by the reduction in ICU patients to 3 by day 11, compared to only day 22 in Group 1. In group 2, more effective conservative intensive therapy was observed, enabling a reduction in the duration of conservative intensive therapy by 11 days in subgroup 1. For patients undergoing extracranial surgeries, the duration of ICU stay in group 2 was reduced by 9 days.

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DIGITAL SCREENING PLATFORM FOR OCCUPATIONAL LUNG DISEASES: VALIDATION OF AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SYSTEM FOR PREDICTIVE DIAGNOSIS OF PNEUMOCONIOSES (A CASE STUDY OF KUZBASS)

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Abstract

Background. *The problem of occupational respiratory diseases, especially pneumoconioses, remains highly relevant for industrial regions with a developed mining industry. Kuzbass demonstrates significant indicators in the Russian Federation: the level of occupational morbidity exceeds the national average, with up to 73% of the pathology structure consisting of lung diseases caused by exposure to fibrogenic dust [1,2,3]. Existing diagnostic methods are subjective,*

characterized by high variability, and detect the disease at the stage of irreversible changes, necessitating the development of fundamentally new approaches to predictive screening [4].

Objective. Development, validation, and assessment of the clinical effectiveness of a specialized artificial intelligence (AI) system for objective quantitative analysis of morphological specimens for the early detection and dynamic monitoring of dust-induced lung pathology in miners.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective-prospective comparative study was conducted. Histological ($n=60$) and cytological ($n=18$) samples from coal industry workers in Kuzbass with confirmed underground work experience of 15–35 years were analyzed. Histological material was obtained from autopsies following man-made disasters, and cytological material was from oncology dispensary archives after excluding oncopathology. Three methods were compared: 1) manual assessment by five pathomorphologists; 2) semi-automatic morphometry using the BioVision Series 4 system; 3) automated analysis by an AI model based on the U-Net + ResNet-34 architecture, generating quantitative biomarkers (Dust Accumulation Index — DAI, Histological Fibrosis Index — HFI, Epithelial Dystrophy Coefficient — EDC).

Results. The AI system demonstrated superiority in key parameters: analysis time decreased from 25 ± 6 to 7 ± 1 minutes, and the coefficient of variation decreased from 18–22% to 2–3%. The algorithm's sensitivity to micro-lesions of fibrosis ($<0.5\text{ mm}^2$) was 94% compared to 41% in routine assessment. Agreement between the AI and expert consensus ($\kappa=0.96$) was significantly higher than inter-expert concordance ($\kappa=0.42$). The biomarkers DAI, HFI, and EDC showed a strong inverse correlation with FEV1 (r from -0.71 to -0.79 ; $p<0.001$). Integration of the parameters into a prognostic model allowed for stratification of the risk of pneumoconiosis progression with an AUC of 0.91.

Conclusion. The validated AI system represents a ready-made solution for «digital occupational examination,» enabling a transition to predictive diagnostics and objective monitoring of occupational risks in coal mining regions.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), pneumoconiosis, occupational lung diseases, digital pathology, predictive diagnostics, deep learning, Kuzbass, morphometry.

Introduction

Kemerovo region (Kuzbass) is an area with a high level of occupational morbidity, consistently exceeding the national average. Up to 73% of the pathology structure consists of chronic respiratory diseases, primarily pneumoconioses, with hundreds of new cases registered annually. Traditional diagnostics, based on subjective assessment of radiographs and morphological specimens, is characterized

by high variability (up to 18–22%) and detects fibrosis at irreversible stages. An acute shortage of specialists in remote mining settlements exacerbates the problem. The digital transformation of pathology using artificial intelligence (AI) represents a strategic direction for creating objective, quantitative, and early diagnostic solutions [5]. However, the development and validation of specialized AI systems for diagnosing occupational lung diseases, adapted to regional conditions, remain a relevant and unsolved task.

Materials and Methods

A prospective comparative study was performed using archival biomaterial. The study was approved by the local ethics committee. Two groups were formed:

1. Histological analysis group (n=60). Lung tissue samples obtained from pathological examinations (autopsy) following man-made disasters at coal mining enterprises were used. The material represented various stages of dust-induced pathology.

2. Cytological analysis group (n=18). Cytological specimens (sputum, BAL) provided by the regional oncology dispensary were used. The final diagnosis excluded oncopathology and confirmed occupational disease. All patients had confirmed long-term underground work experience (15–35 years).

3. Methods of comparative analysis. For each histological sample, an independent analysis was performed using three methods:

4. Manual histological assessment (comparison standard). Five pathomorphologists independently evaluated the sections using a modified semi-quantitative scale (0–3 points). A consensus conclusion was made when ≥ 3 assessments coincided.

5. Semi-automatic computer morphometry. Analysis was performed using the BioVision Series 4 system (Austria), integrated with an Olympus CX-31 microscope and a Videolink digital camera. The software provided automatic segmentation and stereological analysis with measurement of diameter, area, perimeter, curvature coefficient, and calculated volume of dust particles.

6. Automated AI analysis. A neural network model based on the U-Net (semantic segmentation) + ResNet-34 (classification) architecture, fine-tuned on archival histological sections, was applied. The algorithm automatically calculated the Histological Fibrosis Index (HFI), the average area of fibrotic foci, and the density of dust deposits. For cytological specimens, a separate model calculated the Dust Accumulation Index (DAI) and the Epithelial Dystrophy Coefficient (EDC).

7. Statistical analysis. Cohen's Kappa coefficient (κ) was used to assess agreement, Bland-Altman analysis for method comparison, and Spearman's correlation coefficient (r) to determine the relationship with FEV1. The work was performed in R v.4.3.1. The significance level was $p < 0.05$.

Results

The AI system showed significant superiority in efficiency. The time to analyze one histological specimen was reduced by 3.5 times — from 25 ± 6 to 7 ± 1 minutes. The coefficient of variation of the results decreased from 18–22% in routine assessment to 2–3% when using AI. The algorithm's sensitivity for detecting micro-lesions of fibrosis with an area of less than 0.5 mm^2 reached 94%, significantly exceeding the rates of visual expert assessment (41%) and semi-automatic morphometry (63%).

Inter-expert agreement among the five pathomorphologists remained at a moderate level ($\kappa=0.42$), while the agreement between the AI and the consensus conclusion of three senior experts was almost perfect ($\kappa=0.96$).

The quantitative biomarkers generated by the system demonstrated high diagnostic value. The Dust Accumulation Index (DAI), Histological Fibrosis Index (HFI), and Epithelial Dystrophy Coefficient (EDC) showed a statistically significant strong inverse correlation with the key indicator of external respiratory function — FEV1 (r from -0.71 to -0.79 ; $p < 0.001$), as well as a direct correlation with the length of underground work. Changes in the indices were recorded at preclinical stages, long before a significant decrease in FEV1. Integration of cytological (DAI, EDC) and histological (HFI) parameters into a single prognostic model allowed for high-accuracy ($\text{AUC}=0.91$) stratification of the individual risk of pneumoconiosis progression.

Conclusion

1. The developed and validated specialized AI system proves its clinical effectiveness and significant superiority over traditional methods in diagnosing dust-induced lung pathology, providing highly accurate, rapid, and objective quantitative assessment of morphological changes.

2. The system generates new reproducible digital biomarkers (DAI, HFI, EDC) that reliably correlate with external respiratory function and work experience, enabling the detection of preclinical signs of dust load and initial fibrosis, thereby shifting diagnostics into a predictive domain.

3. The comprehensive AI approach integrating cytological and histological data creates a basis for personalized prevention and timely correction of working conditions due to the high accuracy of stratifying the risk of pneumoconiosis progression ($\text{AUC}=0.91$).

4. The practical implementation of the system in the form of a «digital occupational examination» represents a ready-made solution for Kuzbass, capable of compensating for personnel shortages, ensuring diagnostic standardization, and becoming a tool for objective monitoring of the effectiveness of occupational health and safety measures.

5. The implementation of this AI technology is a necessary step in transitioning from delayed radiological diagnosis to a system of occupational risk management based on early detection and prevention. Pilot implementation in Kuzbass can serve as a model for scaling to other industrial regions of Russia.

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FEATURES OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM OF PULSE ARTERIAL PRESSURE IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE COMBINED TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURY IN CHILDHOOD

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Abstract. Monitoring data from children hospitalized at the RSCEMC between 2016 and 2021 for severe combined traumatic brain injury (Group 1), and from 2022 to 2024 (Group 2) were analyzed. Children in Group 1 were admitted due to road traffic accidents (23 cases) and falls from height (11 cases); in Group 2, road traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, and combined trauma affected 5 children. In the absence of significant differences in injury severity, the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency, and average indicators of the phase structure of the circadian rhythm of arterial diastolic pressure (CR APP) upon admission, a significant improvement in intensive therapy outcomes was observed, reflecting increased treatment efficacy in the majority of pediatric patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury in the second group (2022–2024). In the first group, during the initial 7 days of the post-traumatic period, a statistically significant increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of arterial pulse pressure was detected in the second and third subgroups, corresponding to the cardiac functional response to injury severity. In the subsequent days of treatment in the ICU, the identified upward trend persisted. An increasing trend in the amplitude of CR APP was observed in Group 1, Subgroup 2 at the 24th 24 hours, and a less pronounced increase was noted in Subgroup 3 compared to Subgroups 1 and 2 at the 28th 24 hours. The statistically significant increase in the mesor of CR APP observed in Subgroup 3 of Groups 1 and 2 on the 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 9th 24

hours, as well as the significant increase in the mesor of CR APP in Subgroup 3 of Group 2 from the 2nd to the 16th 24 hours of the postoperative period, reflected a comparatively more pronounced cardiovascular stress response and underscored the necessity for more effective stress-protective therapy in patients of Subgroup 3.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, diastolic blood pressure, severe combined traumatic brain injury, pediatric patients.

Relevance. Currently, mechanisms of secondary brain injury, developing under the influence of intracranial and extracranial factors, are considered potentially reversible. Most authors agree that early detection and elimination of these mechanisms represent the primary objective in the treatment of patients with traumatic brain injury. Indications for urgent neurosurgical intervention in severe traumatic brain injury include the presence of epidural, intracerebral, or subdural hematomas, tension pneumocephalus, occlusive hydrocephalus, depressed skull fractures, and penetrating craniocerebral injuries causing brain compression. This manifests on CT as displacement of the midline brain structures and compression of the basal cisterns. Clinically, this corresponds to various generalized cerebral and focal symptoms, including pathognomonic ones. The presented results, together with ongoing research, enhance the effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy for children with severe combined traumatic brain injury (SCTBI), retain potential for further prognostic improvement, reduce the degree of disability among injured children, and support their reintegration into the social environment following severe traumatic illness [1–5]. In this context, we sought to analyze and comparatively evaluate comprehensive intensive therapy across different time periods, namely 2016–2021 and 2022–2024, during which significant organizational measures were implemented to reorganize the emergency service. These measures aimed to minimize the time from injury to the delivery of urgent specialized care, with necessary resuscitative and surgical interventions performed nearly simultaneously.

Objective of the study. To investigate and assess the features of the circadian rhythm of arterial pulse pressure in operated pediatric patients with severe combined traumatic brain injury.

Materials and methods. Monitoring data from children receiving inpatient treatment at RNCMP for SCTBI between 2016 and 2021 (Group 1) and from 2022 to 2024 (Group 2) were analyzed. Children in Group 1 were admitted due to road traffic accidents (23 cases) and falls from height (11 cases); in Group 2, road traffic accidents accounted for 32 cases, and combined trauma affected 5 children. In both groups, analyses were conducted across three subgroups: subgroup 1, where conservative therapy was administered due to the absence of indications for surgical intervention; subgroup 2, comprising children who underwent

extracranial surgeries; and subgroup 3, including patients who underwent both cranial and extracranial surgeries within the first 24 hours after admission to the clinic. Patients in Group 1, Subgroup 1 (n=13), received conservative therapy as indicated; children in Subgroup 2 (n=16) underwent extracranial surgical corrective procedures within the initial hours as indicated; 8 patients in Subgroup 3 underwent simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgical interventions involving a neurosurgeon, general surgeon, and traumatologist upon admission. In Group 2, 13 children received conservative therapy; extracranial surgeries were performed in 16 patients; simultaneous cranial and extracranial surgeries were conducted in 8 children. No significant age differences were observed between the groups. In nearly all subgroups, boys predominated in number. No statistically significant differences in injury severity or in the degree of acute cerebral insufficiency at hospital admission were identified between the subgroups of the first group. A slight tendency toward a reduction in the severity of traumatic injuries was observed within the subgroups of the second group. Thus, the differences in the first subgroup were 25% ($p>0.05$), in the second — 44% ($p<0.05$), and in the third — 27% ($p<0.05$). With the improvement of the condition, stabilization of hemodynamics and respiration, and recovery of reflexes and consciousness, patients were transferred to the specialized department. The findings indicate the absence of significant differences in the severity of acute cerebral insufficiency according to the Glasgow Coma Scale between groups and subgroups. The observed difference in injury severity according to the ISS scale between subgroups 2 and 3 of group 2 can be explained by the effectiveness of maximal reduction of prehospital time in trauma cases.

Monitoring was performed through comprehensive hourly recording of body temperature, hemodynamic parameters, and respiration. Mechanical respiratory support was initiated with short-term artificial lung ventilation (ALV), followed by transition to SIMV.

Results and Discussion.

Table 1.

Comparative evaluation of phase structure parameters of the mean circadian rhythm during the periods before 2021 (Group 1) and 2022–2024 (Group 2).

Subgroups	Mesor		Acrophase		Bathyphase		Amplitude		Range of fluctuations	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
1 (7 days)	45±0,5	47±1	49±1	52±2	41±1	42±1	4±1	5±1	8±2	10±2
2 (7 days)	49±1*	42±1*	55±2*	46±1*	44±2	37±1	6±1	4±0,3	11±3	9±1

Subgroups	Mesor		Acrophase		Bathypphase		Amplitude		Range of fluctuations	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2	Group 1	Group 2
3 (7 days)	48±2*	49±3	54±3*	55±3	43±3	42±5	6±1	6±1	12±2	13±4
1 (29 days)	44±2	46±2	52±4	54±3	38±3	38±4	7±4	8±3	14±6	16±5
2 (30 days)	48±3	42±2	57±5	48±2*	39±4	35±3	8±3	7±2	17±6	13±4
3 (30 days)	47±2	51±4	54±3	66±8*	41±3	38±6	7±2	15±7	14±4	28±11

*-significant relative to the indicator in subgroup 1

In group 1, during the first 7 days of the post-traumatic period, a statistically significant increase in the mesor of CR APP was observed by 8% in subgroup 2 and by 6% ($p < 0.05$, respectively) in subgroup 3, reflecting the cardiac function response to injury severity. In the subsequent days of treatment in the ICU, the identified upward trend persisted. The increase in APP during the acrophase in the first 7 days corresponded to the magnitude of the stress response in subgroups 2 and 3, measuring 12% and 10%, respectively. In group 2, conversely, a 10% reduction in the mesor of CR APP was observed in subgroup 2 ($p < 0.05$), as well as a 10% decrease in diastolic arterial pressure during the acrophase ($p < 0.05$), which can be attributed to a more aggressive stress-mitigating correction associated with surgical intervention under anesthesia and postoperative analgesia. However, subgroup 3 exhibited a trend toward an increase in the studied parameter. This finding is explained by the hemodynamic response to acute cerebral edema resulting from traumatic brain injury, which necessitated surgical intervention. Thus, the administered general anesthesia in this subgroup exerted an insufficient stress-protective effect.

Table 2.

Dynamics of mesor in groups 1 and 2 of severe combined traumatic brain injury

Days	Subgroup 1		Subgroup 2		Subgroup 3	
	Group 1	Group 2	1	2	1	2
1	45±2	45±3	50±4	43±2	44±3	42±4
2	46±2	48±1	51±2	43±2	47±3	50±3*
3	45±2	47±1	49±2	43±1	52±3*	50±2*
4	45±1	46±2	49±2	41±2	51±3*	52±2*
5	44±1	45±2	52±2	40±2	50±2*	48±2
6	45±2	47±2	50±2	41±2	47±2	49±2*
7	44±2	50±3	47±2	42±2	48±3	54±3*
8	43±2	49±3	49±2	45±3	48±3	54±6*

Days	Subgroup 1		Subgroup 2		Subgroup 3	
	Group 1	Group 2	1	2	1	2
9	44±1	47±2	44±3	43±3	52±2*	57±5*
10	47±2	46±3	47±2	42±2	46±3	58±5*
11	45±2	45±4	52±3	43±3	46±3	52±5*
12	43±1	46±4	50±3	42±3	50±3	47±4
13	42±2	49±4	49±3	41±2	48±3	56±4*
14	44±2	48±5	47±4	43±2	46±2	58±5*
15	44±2	45±4	48±2	44±3	46±3	58±5*
16	44±2	47±3	46±3	40±3	49±2	57±4*
17	44±2	49±5	40±3	41±3	50±3	46±3
18	42±3	46±2	38±4	38±2	46±2	47±4
19	46±2	43±3	55±4	39±3	45±2	49±6
20	46±2	43±3	53±4	35±6	44±3	44±4
21	45±2	44±3	52±5		49±3	51±6
22	42±3	45±4	50±3		48±4	52±8
23	50±3	44±3	49±4		42±1	52±11
24	49±2	36±4	49±4		49±3	46±8
25	49±3	43±4	45±5		46±2	47±9
26	39±5	47±5	45±6		43±2	46±7
27	42±8	43±5	46±3		49±4	49±8
28	42±4	43±5	47±4		48±3	56±11
29	44±6	48±3	49±4		48±5	
30			50±5		41±2	

*-Statistically significant relative to the day 1 indicator.

No significant deviations from the norm or differences between groups and subgroups were detected during the first 24 hours (Table 2). In subgroup 3 of group 1, a statistically significant increase in the mesor of CR APP was observed on days 3, 4, 5, and 9 by 18%, 15%, 13%, and 18%, respectively. In subgroup 3 of group 2, a significant increase in the mesor of CR APP was identified beginning from the 2nd 24-hour postoperative period by 19%, and subsequently on the 3rd, 4th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th, 10th, 11th, and 13th through 16th 24-hour periods by 19%, 24%, 16%, 28%, 35%, 37%, 24%, 33%, 37%, 37%, and 35% ($p < 0.05$, respectively). This characteristic indicates a relatively more pronounced stress response of the cardiovascular system during the first 16 24-hour periods of post-traumatic illness and underscores the need for more effective stress-protective therapy in patients of subgroup 3.

Fig. 1. Circadian rhythm of arterial pulse pressure (CR APP) over 7 days in Group 1

Fig. 2. Circadian rhythm of arterial pulse pressure (CR APP) in Group 2 during the first 7 days

In Group 1, the CR APP level during the first 7 days in Subgroup 1 (45 ± 1 mmHg) was significantly lower than in Subgroup 2 (49 ± 1 mmHg) and Subgroup 3 (48 ± 1 mmHg) by 9% and 6%, respectively ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). Meanwhile, in Group 2, the average CR APP level in Subgroup 2 remained within physiological norms at 42 ± 1 mmHg, being 16% lower than in Subgroup 3 and 12% lower than in Subgroup 1 during the first 7 days ($p < 0.05$, respectively) (Fig. 2). Notably, this parameter in Group 2, Subgroup 2 was 16% lower than the corresponding parameter in Group 1 ($p < 0.05$). Thus, a more effective improvement in the management of the early postoperative period (7 days) was observed in children of subgroup 2, as evidenced by the normalization of CR APP levels in subgroup 2 of group 2.

Fig. 3. CR APP in group 1 in the ICU.

Fig. 4. CR APP in group 2 during the ICU stay.

During intensive therapy in the ICU, the average CR APP value in children of subgroup 2 in group 2 remained close to the normal range, whereas a 16% increase in CR APP ($p < 0.05$) was detected in group 1. A tendency toward a more distinct formation of the circadian rhythm was observed in subgroup 3 of group 2, with an acrophase at 9:00 and a bathyphase at 5:00.

Fig. 5. Continuation of CR APP inversion in group 1.

Fig. 6. Inversion of CR APP in group 2.

During the first 7 days, in group 1, subgroup 1, comprising 40%, and subgroup 2, throughout the entire ICU treatment, inversion accounted for 40% (Fig. 5). In group 2, during the early post-traumatic period within the first 7 days, inversion was observed for 58% of the time in subgroup 2 and 40% of the time in subgroup 1, remaining at 40% throughout intensive therapy in the ICU (Fig. 6).

Fig. 7. Amplitude of CR APP in the 1st subgroup and s in 2 groups without surgery.

Fig. 8. Amplitude of CR APP in the 2nd subgroup.

Fig. 9. Amplitude of CR APP in the 3rd subgroup

One of the indicators of stress-induced remodeling of the circadian rhythm is an increase in the amplitude of the daily oscillations. A comparative analysis of the dynamics of the CR APP amplitude during comprehensive intensive therapy in the ICU in groups 1 and 2 revealed specific characteristics. Thus, in Group 1, Subgroup 1, under conservative therapy, the tendency for an increase in the amplitude of CR APP was most pronounced on the 28th day. In Group 1, Subgroup 2, on the 24th day, and in Subgroup 3, the least significant increase compared to Subgroups 1 and 2 was observed on the 28th day (Figures 7, 8, 9).

Conclusions. In Group 1, during the first 7 days of the post-traumatic period, a statistically significant increase in the mesor of CR APP in Subgroups 2 and 3 corresponded to the cardiac functional response to injury severity. In the subsequent days of treatment in the ICU, the identified upward trend persisted. An increasing trend in the amplitude of CR APP was observed in Group 1, Subgroup 2 at the 24th 24 hours, and a less pronounced increase was noted in Subgroup 3 compared to Subgroups 1 and 2 at the 28th 24 hours. The statistically significant increase in the mesor of CR APP observed in Subgroup 3 of Groups 1 and 2 on the 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 9th 24 hours, as well as the significant increase in the mesor of CR APP in Subgroup 3 of Group 2 from the 2nd to the 16th 24 hours of the postoperative period, reflected a comparatively more pronounced cardiovascular stress response and underscored the necessity for more effective stress-protective therapy in patients of Subgroup 3.

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THE ROLE OF HORMONAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF EROSIVE GASTRODUODENITIS IN GIRLS DURING PUBERTY

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of an examination of 70 girls aged 9–15 years with chronic gastroduodenitis in combination with gastroesophageal reflux disease. The aim of this study was to evaluate the hormonal profile (HGH, TSH, T3, T4, cortisol, insulin, testosterone, estradiol, and gastrin) across different Tanner stages of sexual maturation. It has been established that the formation of erosive mucosal lesions (34.3%) is associated with a decrease in anabolic factors (HGH, insulin, and T3) against the background of gastrin hyperproduction and activation of thyrotropic function. The most pronounced deviations were recorded during Tanner stages II–III of puberty. Recommendations have been developed to optimize therapy based on the endocrine status.*

Keywords: *chronic gastroduodenitis, girls, puberty, Tanner stages, hormonal status, erosive gastroduodenitis, insulin, gastrin.*

Introduction. Chronic inflammatory diseases of the upper gastrointestinal tract (UGIT), particularly chronic gastroduodenitis (CGD), occupy a leading position in the spectrum of pediatric gastroenterological morbidity and exhibit a persistent increasing trend [1; 2; 4; 11]. Contemporary clinical and statistical trends indicate that the pathomorphosis of CGD is characterized by an increased proportion of

combined lesions and destructive forms, which predominantly manifest during puberty [5; 6; 7].

Puberty is a phase of qualitative neuroendocrine remodeling that substantially alters the morphofunctional relationships of organs [3; 9]. Hormones of the pituitary-thyroid and adrenal axes, along with sex steroids, determine the motor, mucus-secreting, and secretory functions of the stomach, as well as the mucosal regeneration processes [2; 10]. Investigating the gender-specific characteristics of erosive gastroduodenitis (EGD) development in girls at the onset of puberty is particularly relevant due to the peculiarities of gonadal axis maturation [8].

Objective of the study. To assess the characteristics of the hormonal status in girls with chronic gastroduodenitis at various stages of sexual development and to determine the role of endocrine shifts in the pathogenesis of erosive forms of the disease.

Materials and methods. This prospective study included 70 girls aged 9–15 years with a confirmed diagnosis of chronic gastroduodenitis during the exacerbation phase. The distribution across stages of biological maturity was performed according to the classification by J. Tanner stages (I–III Tanner scale) [12]. The control group (CG) consisted of 22 practically healthy peers of comparable age.

The diagnostic protocol included:

1. Endoscopic and morphological assessment: Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGDS) was performed according to the standard protocol, evaluating the esophagus, stomach, and duodenum. Targeted biopsy of the mucous membrane was conducted to confirm the nature of the inflammation.

2. Verification of *Helicobacter pylori* (Hp): A combination of invasive methods (bacterioscopy of biopsy specimens, rapid urease test, PCR) and non-invasive methods (ELISA of serum for total antibodies) was employed.

3. Hormonal screening: Serum concentrations of somatotrophic hormone (HGH), thyrotropic hormone (TSH), triiodothyronine (T3), thyroxine (T4), cortisol, insulin, testosterone, estradiol, and gastrin were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Statistical analysis was performed using STATISTICA 10.0 software. Descriptive statistical methods included arithmetic mean (M), standard error of the mean (m), median (Me), and interquartile range ([Q25; Q75]). The significance of differences was evaluated using Student's t-test and the Mann-Whitney U test. The critical level of significance was $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion Endoscopic examination demonstrated that in the majority of girls (65.7%, n=46), the process was superficial in nature (Group 1). Erosive gastroduodenitis (EGD) was diagnosed in 34.3% (n=24, second group). A statistically significant predominance of catarrhal forms indicates a milder course of inflammation in girls compared to boys during the corresponding

developmental period. It should be noted that in all patients (100%), hCG was associated with signs of gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) manifesting as grade I reflux esophagitis.

H. pylori infection was detected in 34.3% of the patients. As expected, the presence of infection correlated with lesion severity: among *Hp*-positive girls, the incidence of erosive lesions was 58.6%. However, the frequency of *Hp* detection did not depend on the stage of sexual maturation or the type of autonomic tone ($p > 0.05$), underscoring the importance of other pathogenetic factors in the development of mucosal destruction.

Analysis of the hormonal profile (Table 1) revealed significant dysfunctional alterations in girls with erosive pathology.

Table 1.
Hormonal status of the examined girls ($M \pm m$).

Parameters	Group 1 (PGD), n=46	Group 2 (EGD), n=24	Control group, n=22
HGH (ng/mL)	1,92 ± 0,46	1,15 ± 0,43*	2,78 ± 1,03
TSH (μIU/mL)	1,63 ± 0,11	1,79 ± 0,29*	1,65 ± 0,11
T3 (nmol/L)	2,10 ± 0,07	1,98 ± 0,05*	2,24 ± 0,15
Testosterone (ng/mL)	0,23 ± 0,04	0,09 ± 0,03*	0,28 ± 0,12
Estradiol (pg/mL)	27,21 ± 4,02	40,92 ± 10,29*	26,45 ± 7,24
Insulin (μIU/mL)	7,67 ± 0,52	7,28 ± 1,10	8,09 ± 0,73
Cortisol (nmol/L)	453,52 ± 33,69	467,92 ± 17,56	441,27 ± 29,83

* — differences are statistically significant compared to the control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.
Hormonal profile of the second group (erosive gastroduodenitis) throughout puberty dynamics (Me [Q25; Q75])

Parameters	Tanner Stage II (Patients)	Tanner Stage II (Control)	Tanner Stage III (Patients)	Tanner Stage III (Control)
Insulin (μIU/mL)	4,20 [4,0–8,0]*	7,90 [7,4–14,0]	7,80 [6,0–8,2]	7,60 [7,0–8,8]
HGH (ng/mL)	0,70 [0,5–3,7]*	1,40 [0,1–11,0]	0,24 [0,1–0,3]*	1,90 [0,9–5,8]
Estradiol (pg/mL)	24,0 [22,0–39,0]*	25,0 [20,0–47,0]	48,0 [34,0–54,0]*	20,0 [5,0–45,0]
Gastrin (pmol/L)	3,55 [0,5–3,2]*	3,05 [2,5–5,5]	1,69 [1,4–3,8]*	0,32 [0,3–2,1]

* — $p < 0.05$ compared to the control group.

A key distinction in girls with EGD was a significant reduction in HGH and T3 levels. These hormones pertain to the anabolic continuum; Their deficiency slows protein synthesis and cellular proliferation, rendering the mucosal lining more susceptible to aggressive factors. Conversely, an elevated TSH level indicates stress of the thyroid axis.

Hormonal dynamics based on Tanner stages (Table 2) demonstrated that the peak of dysregulatory disturbances corresponds to Tanner stages II and III.

In girls at Tanner Stage II, there is a pronounced decrease in insulin (4.20 μ IU/mL), which, combined with low HGH, creates conditions for a 'repair failure.' Simultaneously, gastrin levels at Tanner Stages II and III significantly exceed control values, maintaining a state of hyperacidity.

The level of estradiol warrants particular attention. In Tanner stage III, girls with erosions exhibit peak levels (48.0 pg/ml). This phenomenon can be interpreted in two ways. On one hand, estrogens stimulate the production of protective mucus and enhance microcirculation (cytoprotective effect). On the other hand, their sharp increase in response to inflammation may represent an attempt by the organism to compensate for deficiencies of other anabolic factors (HGH and T3).

The obtained data facilitate the construction of a pathogenetic sequence underlying erosion formation in adolescent girls. Unlike boys, in whom testosterone and cortisol play a leading role in aggression, the key factor in girls is a deficiency of anabolic support (HGH, T3, insulin) against the background of hypergastrinemia. A decrease in HGH at all stages of puberty during erosive processes indicates depletion of the body's adaptive resources. Somatotropic hormone normally accelerates the healing of mucosal defects, and its low level becomes a limiting factor in regeneration. Elevated TSH levels with low T3 indicate the development of euthyroid sick syndrome, frequently associated with chronic inflammatory processes. A high estradiol level in the late stages of puberty (Tanner stage III) in patients with erosions likely represents a protective mechanism. However, it is insufficient to completely neutralize the aggressive effect of hydrochloric acid, the secretion of which is stimulated by elevated gastrin levels.

Conclusion. Thus, the development of erosive gastroduodenitis in girls during puberty is determined by the combined effect of *H. pylori* infection and pronounced endocrine dysfunction. Hormonal imbalance is characterized by suppression of anabolic potential (decreased HGH, insulin, and T3) and activation of aggressive factors (hypergastrinemia and elevated TSH).

The period corresponding to Tanner stages II–III is the most critical, necessitating heightened attention from pediatricians and gastroenterologists to this patient group. Incorporating hormonal status assessment into the examination protocol enables timely identification of girls at risk of developing severe

destructive disease forms and allows individualization of therapy by adding, when necessary, agents that improve trophic support and mucosal regeneration.

Based on the data obtained during the study on the significant role of hormonal dysfunction in the pathogenesis of erosive lesions of the gastroduodenal mucosa in girls during puberty, the following recommendations are proposed to optimize diagnostic and therapeutic strategies:

1. Mandatory assessment of SPR according to Tanner staging during the examination of girls with hCG to identify the risk group (Stages II–III).

2. Hormonal monitoring: in erosive forms of hCG, determination of HGH, TSH, and gastrin levels is recommended to evaluate regenerative potential.

3. Therapeutic correction: upon detection of anabolic hormone deficiency, enhancement of cytoprotective therapy with agents promoting cellular trophism is advisable.

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BIOINSPIRED TECHNOLOGIES IN SOLVING COMPLEX PROBLEMS OF ENDODONTICS

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Abstract. *Bioinspired technologies make it possible to change and control the structure and mechanical properties of synthetic composite materials, and the inclusion of certain components in the composition may endow them with specific biological properties. All this makes it possible to improve the quality of non-surgical endodontic treatment, obtain predictable results, achieve bone reconvalescence in the periradicular focus, and provide the patient with an alternative to surgical treatment, what is confirmed by the clinical case.*

Keywords: *biomimetic, hybrid biointerface, dental tissue, restoration, nanodentistry*

In recent years, as a result of technological progress, many biomimetically mineralized composite materials have been obtained. Currently, these composite materials have become the subject of active research in the field of bone tissue engineering and dental hard tissue repair. In addition to various excellent biological properties such as biocompatibility, bioactivity, suitable mechanical strength, slow degradation rate, osteoconductivity, osteoinductivity, the most important advantage of these materials is the ability to realize to a certain extent the biomimetic properties of organic and inorganic components in their structure and functions.[1].

Bioinspired technologies make it possible to change and control the structure and mechanical properties of synthetic composite materials, and the inclusion of certain components in the composition may endow them with specific biological properties.

Considering these clinical features, satisfactory results based on the use of natural and host-derived scaffolds will allow not only the clinician to obtain the predicted result, but also the patient to receive alternative treatment.

Despite the variety of potential biomaterials, such as three-dimensional polymer matrices, none of them has all the properties of an ideal framework, and the results associated with the use of these materials remain diverse and sometimes contradictory[3,4,5].

Many attempts have been made to reproduce the organomineral dental complex using biomimetic principles. In the latter case, biocomposites were created by synthesizing nano-cHAp in the presence of various polymers and amino acid components. [6,7,8,9,10,11].

A team of authors has synthesized a bioactive bonding system, the effectiveness of which has been confirmed by numerous studies and a patent of the Russian Federation. The creation of this drug is based on the fundamental principles of organomineral interaction of components in biocomposites and is used to achieve morphological uniformity and homogeneous distribution of hydroxyapatite nanocrystals in a polymer and organic matrix [12].

The technical result, which is aimed at achieving the stated

The invention is to create a universal bonding system that provides disinfection of tooth dentine, root canal dentine with the possibility of preserving the viability of the remnants of collagen fibers of dentine tubules, improving the adhesion of filling materials used to seal the root of the tooth or other carious lesions through the use of amino acids that are present in the fluid of the periodontoblastic space: histidine, lysine, arginine.

The bioactive bonding system contains:

1. Dentin conditioner, primer, adhesive, which differs in that the primer contains essential amino acids that are not synthesized by the body, but come from

food and serve for the synthesis of cationic protein: histidine — 0.01%-0.2%, lysine — 0.05%-0.4%, arginine — 0.2%-1.6% of the total weight of the primer.

2. The primer contains distilled water in an amount of 10%-50%, ethyl alcohol in an amount of 2%-20%, ethylene glycol methyl ester (MEG) in an amount of 30%-85%, urethanimethacrylate in an amount of 1%-15% of the total amount of the primer, hydrophilic monomer diglycidylmethacrylate in an amount of 1%-15% of the total weight the amount of primer to improve the hydration and permeability of dentin.

3. The adhesive contains isopropylidene — bis-[2-hydroxy-3-(4-phenoxy) propylmethacrylate] in an amount of 1%-15%, urethandimethacrylate in an amount of 40%-90%, resin solvent — ethylene glycol methyl ester in an amount of 10%-40%, light-curing components — N, N dimethylaminoethylmethacrylate in an amount of 0.2%-2%, DL-camphorquinone in an amount of 0.05%-0.6%, chemical polymerization inhibitor — dihydroxylparatoluidine in 0.5%-5%, benzoyl peroxide in the amount of 1%-15% and stabilizer of chemical and light curing — 2-oxy-4-methaoxybenzophenol in an amount of 0.01%-0.8% of the total weight of the adhesive.

At the same time, dentin conditioner contains maleic acid in an amount of 1%-6% for young and mature patients, polyacrylic acid in an amount of 0.3%-5%, citric acid in an amount of 0.5%-7%, distilled water in an amount of 50%-80% of the total weight of the conditioner, maleic acid solution in a concentration of up to 12%, which dissolves the lubricated organic layer of frequent dentin sclerosis in elderly patients, opens the dentinal tubules, thereby increasing the permeability of dentin.

The introduction of essential amino acids histidine, lysine, and arginine into the bioprimer makes it possible to saturate the dentinal tubules with the necessary acids and perform the barrier antimicrobial function of tooth tissues both in the treatment of caries and after endodontic procedures.

The bioactive bonding system has become a revolutionary solution in the treatment of refractory periodontitis and is aimed at increasing the regenerative potential of root dentin. This material has a good affinity for dentin, easily penetrates into the dentinal tubules and forms a «cationic protein» that suppresses pathogenic microflora. The complex composition of the primer restores collagen fibers in the dentin hybrid layer, forms a chemical-mechanical bond between wet dentin and bonding resins, completely isolates the prepared dentin, which significantly improves the adhesion quality of the filling material and prevents the reversal of the pathological process.

Based on the data obtained, a method for the treatment of destructive forms of periodontitis is based, the purpose of which is to cure persistent forms of apical periodontitis of single-root and multi-root teeth burdened with an iatrogenic

factor, allowing teeth to be preserved with a probability of 0.999 negative clinical statistics [14].

The method is carried out as follows. Computed tomography of the tooth area to be treated is performed, after which anesthesia and isolation of the working field are performed, the filling material is removed and the carious cavity is prepared under visual control using an operating microscope, the tooth cavity is restored by forming the lost walls, thereby creating a reservoir for irrigation solutions, after which the working length of the channels is determined with an apexlocator, then mechanical processing of the channel up to ISO size 30 by a reciprocating system in the technique of «balanced force» with tools of 6% taper, after that, antiseptic treatment of the channels is performed by sequential rinsing with irrigation solutions of 5.2% sodium hypochlorite, 9% ethidronic acid, after each portion of the solution is injected, a gutta-percha pin of 6% taper is inserted into the channels to activate the irrigation solution and the irrigant is activated by reciprocating movements, the channels are dehydrated with sterile paper pins of 6% taper, sequentially into the channels with a microapplicator components of the bioactive bonding system (conditioner, primer, adhesive) to disinfect dentin and hermetically close the dentine tubules, the channels are sealed with a sealer and thermoplasticized gutta-percha on a carrier, 1 mm of filling material is removed from the mouth of the channels with boron, 3% belodez gel is introduced into the tooth cavity and activated with ultrasound to clean the tooth cavity from the sealer, the tooth cavity is washed and dried with a puster and an adhesive protocol is performed, fill the mouth of the canal with a flowing composite, restore the integrity of the tooth with a filling material. After 12 months, treatment is monitored using cone beam computed tomography.

The invention is illustrated by figures, where FIG. 1 shows CBCT data before the treatment of periodontitis with periradicular destruction of bone tissue, FIG. 2 shows the result of anesthesia, isolation of the working field, removal of filling material, preparation of the carious cavity, restoration of the tooth cavity by forming lost walls, determination of the working length of the channels by an apexlocator, mechanical processing of the channel to the size of 30 according to ISO by a reciprocating system in the technique of «balanced force» with tools of 6% taper., in FIG. 3 antiseptic treatment of the channels by sequential rinsing with irrigation solutions of 5.2% sodium hypochlorite, 9% ethidronic acid, after administration of each portion of the solution, the introduction of a gutta-percha pin of 6% taper into the channels and activation of the irrigant by reciprocating movements, in FIG. 4 dehydration of the channels with sterile paper pins of 6% taper, in FIG. 5 sequential insertion of components of a bioactive bonding system (conditioner, primer, adhesive) into the channels by a microapplicator, sealing with a sealer and thermoplasticized gutta-percha on a carrier, in FIG. 6 the result

of extraction of 1 mm filling material from the mouth of the channels with boron, application of 3% belodez gel and its activation by ultrasound, FIG.7 conducting an adhesive protocol, filling the mouth part of the canal is a flowing composite, in FIG. 8 restoring the integrity of the tooth with a filling material, in FIG. 9 is the result of CBCT monitoring of bone tissue recovery 12 months after treatment.

Clinical example No. 1.

Patient A complained of pain when biting on the tooth 4.6. Anamnesis: about a year and a half ago, the tooth was treated for uncomplicated caries, after which pain periodically began to appear when biting on the tooth, 2 weeks before the visit, the filling fell out.

There is no concomitant pathology. The allergic history is not burdened.

At the time of treatment, there are no changes during external examination, the face is symmetrical, the mouth opens freely, noiselessly and painlessly, the skin is of normal color, the lymph nodes are not palpable.

Fig.1

In the oral cavity: Hygiene index 1.6 (satisfactory), periodontal Index 0.6 (initial and mild degree of periodontal pathology). The bite is orthognathic, the oral mucosa has no visible pathology.

Objectively: 4.6 there is filling material on the chewing and distal surfaces. The crown part is not changed in color. In area 4.6, the mucosa from the buccal surface of the marginal and alveolar gums is hyperemic, edematous, bleeding on probing, and slightly painful on palpation. The tooth is mobile, percussion is painful. On CBCT, the contents of the channels are not visualized, and the apex is not outlined radiologically. Destruction of bone tissue in the periradicular region.

After the examination, the diagnosis was made: By 04.5 chronic apical periodontitis 4.6, exacerbation. According to the proposed method, the patient underwent endodontic treatment to restore the integrity of the tooth.

Fig.2

Fig.3

Fig.4

Fig.5

Fig.6

Fig.7

Fig.8

Fig.9

Thus, this method allows for effective treatment of chronic forms of apical periodontitis of single-root and multi-root teeth burdened with bone destruction. As a result of treatment, it is possible not only to relieve the symptoms of the disease, but also to potentiate the restoration of bone tissue in the periradicular region.

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A THERAPIST'S VIEW ON INFECTIOUS PANCARDITIS

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Abstract. *The problem of timely diagnosis of infectious endocarditis in injecting drug users is associated with a small sample of observations, atypical and polymorphic signs, often characterized by both damage to the valves of the myocardium and parietal endocardium, but there is a contradiction in the clinical course of the disease. The article describes a clinical case of a rare case of infectious pancarditis, which is a combination of endocarditis, myocarditis, and pericarditis, in a young patient with drug addiction who was diagnosed postmortem. The course of the disease was initially characterized by community-acquired pneumonia.*

Keywords: *infectious pancarditis, parietal endocarditis, injecting drug user, atypical and polymorphic signs*

Introduction. Infectious endocarditis is defined as a severe inflammatory disease of infectious origin with a predominant lesion of the heart valves, sometimes of the parietal endocardium and major vessels, which proceeds in the form of sepsis with bacteremia, immune disorders and complications. A part of patients with infectious endocarditis is represented by injecting drug users, where this nosology often ends in death. Russian clinicians note that infectious endocarditis in injecting drug users is often classified as a special form: due to the diversity of manifestations and the small sample size, there is inconsistency in the clinical picture and diagnosis. In a clinical analysis of the case history of a 30-year-old patient with drug addiction, the features of the course of infectious pancarditis in an injecting drug user are described.

Clinical case. Patient E., 38 years old, was taken by an ambulance team to a multidisciplinary hospital in the Rostov region with a diagnosis of acute community-acquired pneumonia, where from 14.03.2018 to 09.04.2018 (26 days) the patient received treatment in the therapeutic department. Upon admission, there were complaints of thirst, dryness, an increase in body temperature of 39.0 °C, chest pain on the left, shortness of breath. Medical history: the patient's condition worsened within a week, and they began to experience the above-mentioned

symptoms, including persistent fever and increasing general weakness. The patient's life history includes a history of tuberculosis, viral hepatitis, injuries, surgeries, diabetes mellitus, and blood transfusions, but they deny any of these conditions. The patient is an opium addict, and their last drug injection was approximately two weeks ago. The patient's family history and allergic history are not burdened. The patient's overall condition is of moderate severity. The patient's diet is excessive. The musculoskeletal system is without visible pathology. The peripheral lymph nodes are not palpable. Absence of peripheral veins. There are traces of non-medical injections in the groin, and there are traces of multiple intravenous injections on the right. The patient's body temperature is 39.1 °C. There are no signs of edema. The respiratory system shows a clear lung sound on percussion, and the patient's breathing is harsh with moist wheezing on the right, with a respiratory rate of 18 per minute and a saturation level of 97%. The heart sounds are muffled. The patient's blood pressure is 140/80 mmHg, and their heart rate is 92 per minute. The tongue is clean and moist. The abdomen is of the correct shape, soft, and painless. The liver is not enlarged, painless, and smooth. The spleen is not palpable. The stool is formed. The kidneys are not palpable. The percussion sign is negative. The urine output is sufficient.

Diagnosis on 14.03.2018: «Outpatient right-sided pneumonia of moderate severity. Respiratory failure of grade I-0. Obesity. Drug addiction.» Treatment: intravenous antibiotic therapy with erythromycin and ceftriaxone, as well as anticoagulant and expectorant therapy.

Conclusion of echocardiography dated 16.03.2018: No pathological flows were detected. Mitral valve insufficiency grade 1. Tricuspid valve insufficiency grade 1. The heart cavities are not enlarged. The contractility indicators are normal. No vegetation was detected.

The microbiological examination of the blood showed negative results.

The patient was consulted by a psychiatrist-narcologist (a long history of intravenous use of opiate drugs up to 3–4 times a week was confirmed), and a pulmonologist, taking into account the results of the sputum analysis (the presence of *Str. pneumoniae* culture 1x10⁶) against the background of persistent fever up to 38.3 °C and moderate leukocytosis in the general blood test.

According to electrocardiograms and radiographs, during the entire period of treatment, the patient had a clear overload of the pulmonary circulation, with the dynamics of resolution of upper-lobe right-sided pneumonia. The patient was discharged from the hospital under the supervision of a general practitioner and a pulmonologist at the patient's place of residence.

On the third day, the patient sought medical attention on an outpatient basis with complaints of weakness, a temperature of 39.0 °C, and shortness of breath, but refused hospitalization. The next day, with a body temperature of 38.9 °C, he

was admitted to a hospital, where, after a clinical examination, he again refused to be hospitalized.

After 10 days of self-treatment, the patient was admitted to the hospital on 24 April 2018 with complaints of shortness of breath and a temperature of 40.2 °C. Based on the results of a clinical examination (body temperature of 36.6 °C, respiratory rate of 20 per minute, saturation of 98%, heart rate of 75 per minute, blood pressure of 130/80 mmHg, reduced breathing in the lower parts of the lungs, no wheezing, and rhythmic, muffled heart tones), and the results of a radiological examination, the patient was discharged with recommendations for treatment and consultation with a phthisiatrician for further examination.

After 10 days, the patient was admitted to the hospital with complaints of weakness, shortness of breath at rest, swelling, and no urination for 4 days. The patient was examined, tested, and consulted by a urologist and a cardiologist, and a preliminary diagnosis was made: «Acquired heart disease: aortic valve insufficiency after a bacterial endocarditis due to chronic drug addiction. Chronic heart failure III, functional class IV. Chronic anemia.»

Despite the treatment started the next day due to a sharp deterioration in health (complaints of a feeling of lack of air, shortness of breath of a mixed type at rest, swelling of the lower extremities, he was hospitalized, during a clinical examination: forced sitting position, shortness of breath of a mixed type involving auxiliary muscles, swelling of the lower extremities, pale skin, auscultation: crepitation on the right in the upper lungs, blood pressure = 140/90 mm Hg, heart rate = pulse = 135 per minute, frequency of respiratory movements 24–28 per minute, T 36.0 °C, saturation 92–88 %) the patient was consulted by an anesthesiologist-resuscitator, after which the patient was transferred to the intensive care unit, where on the night of 06.05.2018, against the background of negative dynamics due to cardiovascular and respiratory insufficiency and endotoxemia, despite resuscitation measures, the patient died.

Final clinical diagnosis: «Main: 1. Acute infectious endocarditis with formation of aortic valve insufficiency. Background: Chronic exogenous intoxication. Chronic poly-drug addiction. Complications: Chronic heart failure III. Respiratory failure III. Acute cardiovascular failure. Thromboembolic complications. Pulmonary edema, cerebral edema. Asystole. Associated conditions: Chronic viral hepatitis B? Chronic viral hepatitis C? HIV infection?»

Postmortem macroscopic examination of the myocardium: «The heart is 12.0x11.0x9.0 cm, flabby, spherical, and its cavities are markedly dilated. The epicardium in the ventricular area is covered with bright yellow adipose tissue up to 0.4 cm thick. There is a trace amount of liquid, dark red blood in the heart cavities. The inner lining of the heart is smooth, shiny, and transparent. The valve leaflets are whitish-grayish, dense, opaque, thickened, and somewhat limited in their mobility.

The closing edge is smooth, and the leaflets close completely. The left ventricle wall is 1.4 cm thick, the right ventricle is 0.8 cm thick, and the interventricular septum is 1.4 cm thick. The heart muscle is flaccid, dull, pale red-brownish, and has an uneven blood supply. The papillary muscles are thickened and shortened, and the tendon fibers are shortened and compacted.»

Conclusion on the histological preparation of the myocardium: «Focal productive peri- and endocarditis, focal purulent-productive myocarditis. Suppurative mixed thrombus in one of the myocardium veins with the formation of a perifocal microabscess. Acute venous congestion, leukostasis, fibrin and fibrin-leukocyte thrombi in the myocardium vessels. Spasm of the arterioles, focal fragmentation, tortuous deformation of cardiomyocytes, and hyper-eosinophilia of individual cardiomyocytes. Focal lipomatosis of the myocardium, perivascular and small-focal reticular cardiosclerosis, and focal hypertrophy and atrophy of cardiomyocytes.»

Discussion. The given clinical example of infectious pancarditis in an injecting drug user is of interest primarily because of the almost complete absence of such examples in the literature: pancarditis is a combination of endo-, myo- and pericardium, while infectious endocarditis in the context of injecting drug addiction is discussed more often in clinical practice. In the case under discussion, the course of the disease was initially characterized by a picture of community-acquired pneumonia, which was confirmed by X-ray. During the initial hospitalization, a sputum culture showed the presence of *Str. pneumoniae* at a concentration of 1×10^6 . Two days after the initial hospitalization, the patient underwent an echocardiographic examination, which revealed no visual signs of infectious endocarditis.

In our example, it should be noted that none of the medical records from the period of his illness from March 14, 2018, to the time of his death on May 6, 2018, contain any information about the laboratory confirmation or absence of viral hepatitis and/or HIV infection, which significantly limits the ability to analyze and draw conclusions from this clinical example of infectious pancarditis in an injecting drug user.

The fact that a patient uses intravenous drugs can be considered a «minor» but extremely significant criterion for the diagnosis of infectious endocarditis, which indicates a potential source of infection, and the presence of a fever above 38 °C already allows us to state two «minor» criteria in accordance with the modified Duke criteria for the diagnosis of infectious endocarditis [1]. In our case, during the initial hospitalization, the two «minor» criteria for Duke's infectious endocarditis were met, and an echocardiogram was performed, where the absence of valve vegetations distracted the clinicians from further examination of the patient for inflammatory myocardial disease and did not provide a basis for conducting a bacteriological blood test, limiting themselves to a bacteriological sputum test that yielded a *Str. Pneumoniae* culture.

The immediate cause of the patient's death was cardiac arrest due to ventricular fibrillation, which was confirmed by microscopic histological examination of the myocardial tissue from the cadaver, revealing focal fragmentation and twisted deformation of the cardiomyocytes.

Ventricular fibrillation is a complication of heart disease, and in this case, the patient may have had two heart conditions during his lifetime, as confirmed by autopsy and histological examination: 1) cardiomyopathy (myocardial hypertrophy: spherical shape and enlargement of the heart chambers, left ventricle thickness of 1.4 cm, right ventricle thickness of 0.8 cm, and interventricular septum thickness of 1.4 cm), pale reddish-brownish, clay-like color of the myocardium; combination of hypertrophy and atrophy of cardiomyocytes, perivascular and small-focal cardiosclerosis, and focal lipomatosis of the myocardium in the absence of coronary artery atherosclerosis, and hyper-eosinophilia of individual cardiomyocytes); and 2) chronic active pancarditis (focal mixed — macrophage, lymphocyte, neutrophil — inflammatory infiltration of the heart's membranes [epicarditis and endocarditis] and muscles [myocarditis] with focal damage to cardiomyocytes and focal replacement of muscle fibers with connective tissue, and a suppurative mixed thrombus in one of the myocardial veins with the formation of a perifocal microabscess).

The etiology of the patient's cardiomyopathy is chronic exogenous intoxication, the existence of which has been repeatedly documented in medical records over a long period of time, including confirmation from a psychiatrist-narcologist consultation. The patient's medical history includes information about the date of the last drug injection, which occurred two weeks before the patient's admission to the hospital on March 14, 2018.

The patient's etiology of pancarditis is infectious. The onset of the infectious process in the heart in this case could be under various conditions and their combinations, including as a complication of previous acute respiratory viral disease and pneumonia in March 2018, as well as in conditions of angiogenic infection, characteristic of opium intravenous drug addiction with localization of the primary focus of infection in the vascular bed, including in the area of infected deforming scarring of the skin and the wall of a large vessel in the area of long-standing multiple intravenous vascular access that occurred in the patient's groin area or with the entry of pathogens directly into the bloodstream during intravenous injections with infected syringes and non-sterile solutions.

Thus, the patient's death was caused by mutually aggravating heart diseases, such as cardiomyopathy and pancarditis, which developed as a result of chronic opioid addiction and were complicated by decompensation of chronic heart failure and ventricular fibrillation, leading to the patient's death.

Conclusion. In the given clinical example, pancarditis was postmortem verified without any changes in the heart valves. Pancarditis is a combination of epicarditis,

endocarditis, and myocarditis. In our retrospective analysis, we found that there was no valve damage during transthoracic echocardiography in the early stages of the disease, which is consistent with the findings of other researchers who have reported that drug addicts often experience infectious endocarditis as the first symptom, followed by pneumonia and damage to the parietal endocardium without involvement of the valve apparatus [2, 3].

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE SYSTEM OF PRIORITIZING MEDICAL EVACUATION OF CHILDREN: A CONCEPT OF A HYBRID MODEL FOR AN INTERREGIONAL NETWORK OF SURGICAL CARE CENTERS

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Abstract. *Relevance.* The creation of a network of interregional pediatric surgery centers in the Russian Federation requires the development of a highly efficient medical evacuation system. The key problem is an objective and dynamic assessment of the urgency of a child's condition to make decisions about the need, priority, and safety of transportation.

Objective. To provide a scientific rationale for the concept and architecture of a hybrid intelligent decision support system (DSS) based on artificial intelligence (AI) for the integral assessment of urgency and automated prioritization of the evacuation of children to federal centers.

Materials and methods. An analysis of modern scientific publications (depth of 10 years) in the fields of predictive analytics, clinical scales, medical logistics, and machine learning was conducted. Based on a systems approach, an original architecture of a hybrid model was developed.

Results. A three-component architecture of an AI model is proposed: 1) A Predictive ML module (gradient boosting ensembles) for calculating individual risks of deterioration during transport and the need for specific resources; 2) An Expert ontological module encoding clinical protocols and rules for interpretability and safety; 3) An Optimization and planning module solving the problem of dynamic routing and allocation of limited air ambulance resources. The integration of components is implemented through an algorithm for calculating a Dynamic Priority Index (DPI), which generates evidence-based recommendations for evacuation priority and the target healthcare institution.

Conclusion. The developed concept presents scientific and practical novelty, consisting in the original integration of machine learning technologies, expert systems, and operations research methods for managing the inter-hospital

transportation process. The implementation of such a system will minimize the subjective factor, optimize logistics, reduce the time to specialized care, and improve treatment outcomes for children with surgical pathology. Principles for the ethical use of the system in a «human-in-the-loop» mode are proposed.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, machine learning, medical evacuation, pediatric surgery, prioritization, decision support systems, clinical registry, predictive models, optimization.*

Introduction

The organization of timely and safe medical evacuation (ME) of children requiring high-tech surgical care is a critically important component of the interregional healthcare system. The effectiveness of ME directly determines treatment outcomes in life-threatening conditions such as congenital malformations in newborns, severe trauma, burn disease, oncological, and neurosurgical disorders [1]. However, the decision-making process concerning evacuation is currently often based on the subjective assessment of the on-duty physician and telephone consultations, which entails risks: delay in transporting unstable patients or, conversely, unwarranted risk during the transfer of children whose care could be provided on-site [2].

Standardized clinical scales (SNAPPE-II, pGCS, Baux index, etc.), although valuable tools, do not comprehensively resolve the issue. They are static, do not consider the dynamics of the patient's condition, multimorbidity, and are not integrated with logistical constraints (availability of transport, its equipment, distance, and the workload of receiving departments) [3].

In this context, the urgent task is to develop an intelligent system capable of conducting an integrated urgency assessment by synthesizing clinical data, predictive models, and contextual information. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, particularly machine learning (ML), possess the potential to develop such decision support systems (DSS) [4].

The objective of the study is to develop and scientifically substantiate a hybrid AI model concept for the dynamic prioritization of medical evacuation of pediatric patients within a unified clinical registry.

1. Materials and methods

To develop this concept, an analytical review of international and national scientific publications from 2014 to 2024 was conducted. within the PubMed, Scopus, and eLibrary databases using the keywords: «artificial intelligence in emergency medical services», «pediatric transport triage», «machine learning for resource allocation», «clinical decision support in surgery». A method of systems analysis and synthesis was employed to integrate knowledge from clinical medicine,

bioinformatics, and operations research. The model architecture was developed considering the principles of Human-Centered AI and the necessity of ensuring result interpretability.

2. Architecture of a hybrid ai model for evacuation prioritization

The proposed system constitutes a three-component hybrid architecture, wherein the strengths of each component offset the weaknesses of the others.

2.1. Predictive Machine Learning Analysis Module (Predictive ML Core)

Purpose: To process structured quantitative and categorical data for generating individualized predictions.

Input data: Vital signs, results of laboratory and instrumental examinations, and scores from standard clinical scales entered into the electronic registry.

Algorithm selection: Gradient boosting ensembles (XGBoost, CatBoost), demonstrated to be effective in managing medical data with missing values and in ranking tasks [5].

Predictive tasks of the model:

1. Binary classification: the probability of developing a life-threatening complication (respiratory or circulatory decompensation) within the next 6 to 12 hours.

2. Multiclass classification: the probability of requiring specific resources during transport or immediately upon arrival (high-frequency mechanical ventilation, inotropic support, emergency surgical intervention within the first 3 hours).

Probabilistic estimates (P), which form the basis for risk calculations.

2.2. Expert Ontological Module (Knowledge-Based Reasoning Module)

Purpose: To ensure safety, interpretability, and adherence to clinical protocols. Plays a critical role in cases of data insufficiency or rare pathologies.

Operating principle: Based on semantic ontology — a formalized knowledge model in pediatric surgery. The module contains a set of rules in the form ‘IF [condition] THEN [action/conclusion]’.

Example rule: ‘IF [Diagnosis: «Congenital diaphragmatic hernia»] AND [Indicator: «Oxygenation Index (OI) > 25»] THEN [Recommendation: «Status ‘Non-transportable’ until stabilization. Requires high-frequency mechanical ventilation and ECMO center consultation»]’.

Function: verifies and complements the outputs of the ML module by assigning categories based on absolute clinical indications and contraindications for transportation.

2.3. Dynamic Optimization and Planning Module (Operations Research & Logistics Module)

Purpose: translating medical urgency into optimal management decisions under conditions of limited resources.

Input data: integral patient priority score, patient geolocation, localization of target federal centers, availability and technical specifications of transport vehicles (type of airplane/helicopter, presence of onboard equipment for mechanical ventilation), meteorological conditions, and current workload of operating rooms and intensive care unit beds in receiving clinics.

Mathematical model: the Dynamic Vehicle Routing Problem with Priorities. The real-time algorithm determines a solution that minimizes the total weighted delivery time, where the weight corresponds to the patient's priority [6].

Outcome: a specific dispatch recommendation, including selection of the vehicle and team, identification of the final destination, route construction, and calculation of ETD/ETA.

2.4. Integration Algorithm: Calculation of the Dynamic Priority Index (DPI)

A key component of the system is the algorithm for consolidating the outputs of all modules:

$$DPI_i = \alpha * P(\text{decompensation})_i + \beta * K(\text{ontology})_i + \gamma * L(\text{logistics})_i$$

where:

DPI_i — Dynamic Priority Index for the i -th patient (ranging from 0 to 1).

$P(\text{decompensation})_i$ — probability of decompensation from the ML module.

$K(\text{ontology})_i$ — normalized weight assigned by the ontological module (e.g., 1.0 for a “red flag,” 0.5 for “yellow”).

$L(\text{logistics})_i$ — coefficient accounting for the time factor and availability of assistance (increases with waiting time).

α, β, γ — tunable weight coefficients reflecting confidence in each system component.

Based on DPI threshold values, the final priority categories are defined as: P1 (Critical), P2 (High), P3 (Planned).

3. Discussion: scientific novelty and practical prospects

The proposed concept exhibits pronounced scientific novelty of an integrative character.

1. Novelty of the object of management. Unlike most medical AI solutions focused on diagnosis or outcome prediction in hospitalized patients, this system manages a dynamic, spatially distributed process spanning the ‘region — federal center’ interaction. This necessitates consideration of a fundamentally different set of variables and constraints.

2. Methodological novelty of the architecture. The hybrid approach «ML + Ontology + Optimization» is specifically designed for environments characterized by high responsibility and data scarcity. The ontological module serves as a «safety mechanism» that prevents illogical recommendations from the ML model's «black box» and provides the level of trust essential for medical practice.

3. Practical transformational innovation. The system advocates for a transition from reactive, experience-based dispatching by individual specialists to a proactive, predictive, and optimization-based resource allocation model. It enables not only the assessment of ‘whom to transport,’ but also decisions regarding ‘which transport to use, to exactly where, and in what sequence,’ thereby maximizing overall utility for the patient flow.

Expected outcomes of implementation include reducing the ‘decision-to-departure’ time by automating routine calculations; decreasing subjective errors during triage; optimizing the utilization of the costly medical aviation resource; enhancing the preparation of the receiving party through the automatic transmission of a structured needs forecast.

Ethical and regulatory aspects constitute an integral part of the concept. The system must operate exclusively in a ‘human-in-the-loop’ mode, providing the physician-dispatcher with substantiated recommendations accompanied by explanations of the key factors influencing the decision (for example, using SHAP — Shapley Additive Explanations — technology) [7]. Protocols for the regular auditing of algorithms to identify bias and for their retraining on new data are necessary.

Conclusion

1. An original concept of a hybrid AI system for prioritizing the medical evacuation of pediatric patients has been developed and scientifically substantiated. Its architecture, combining predictive ML models, expert ontologies, and optimization algorithms, is designed to address the complex task of managing the inter-hospital transport process under multiple constraints.

2. A key component of the system is the algorithm for calculating the Dynamic Priority Index (DPI), which integrates clinical risks, protocol standards, and logistical parameters to produce objective and reproducible recommendations.

3. The implementation of such a system in the practice of interregional pediatric surgical centers will facilitate a transition to a new level of care organization based on data and predictive analytics, which, ultimately, should enhance the timeliness and quality of high-tech surgical care provided to children nationwide. The next stage of this work should be the development of a pilot prototype followed by its clinical and economic validation.

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TROPHIC DISORDERS OF THE ANTENATAL PERIOD AS A FACTOR IN THE DELAY OF THE STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL MATURATION OF THE BRONCHOPULMONARY SYSTEM

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Summary. *Delayed intrauterine fetal development due to trophic disorders of various etiologies, infectious processes, as well as genetically determined features of endocrine regulation of growth can be an antenatal reason for the delay in the functional maturation of a number of organ systems, including the bronchopulmonary system. The purpose of the study: to analyze the literature on the pathogenetic mechanisms of trophic disorders of the antenatal period and their role in delaying the structural and functional maturation of the bronchopulmonary system. Methods. Analysis of foreign and domestic publications was carried out using databases Elibrary.ru, Cyberleninka.ru, Medscape, PubMed. Results. In the current model of bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) pathogenesis, a significant role is played by body weight deficiency for this HB and prematurity, the combination of which quite often occurs in neonatal practice. One of the main reasons for their development is placental insufficiency — a clinical syndrome due to morpho-functional changes in the placenta and violation of its compensatory and adaptive mechanisms.*

Keywords: *trophic disorders, fetoplacental insufficiency, newborn, bronchopulmonary dysplasia.*

The most common chronic disease with origins in the neonatal period is the widely discussed chronic lesion of the bronchopulmonary system — BPD. It is she who continues to lead among the early and late complications of the pathological course of the neonatal period in premature babies with neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and/or pneumonia, which required the use of various methods of respiratory therapy from minimally invasive to traditional artificial lung ventilation (IVL). Thus, the frequency of BPD in children born prematurely, with a body weight of less than 1,500 grams, according to modern data, varies from 6.7% to 49%. However, wide variations in this indicator are possible, since the incidence of BPD is inversely proportional to gestational age (GW) and body weight at birth. Thus, in children with HBT less than 30 weeks and ONMT, the average frequency of BPD is 20%, and in children with ENMT, the frequency can increase to 35%-80% [1, 2, 3, 4].

The aim of the work is: to analyze the literature on the pathogenetic mechanisms of trophic disorders of the antenatal period and their role in delaying the structural and functional maturation of the bronchopulmonary system.

Materials and methods. Analysis of foreign and domestic publications was carried out using databases Elibrary.ru, Cyberleninka.ru, Medscape, PubMed. Results.

Results and its discussion. It was found that in deeply premature babies, small by gestational age, the frequency of BPD is significantly higher compared to premature newborns, corresponding to HB in mass-growth parameters, and amounts to 33–45%. This group of patients has a higher risk of developing chronic pathology of various organ systems, for example, the incidence of chronic diseases of the bronchopulmonary system increases by 1.9 times [5]. In turn, BPD during pathomorphosis can lead to hypotrophy, chronic protein-energy deficiency, slowing down the rate of postnatal physical development in premature babies small for HB.

All factors that slow down fetal growth can be divided into 4 groups according to the pathogenetic principle: demographic (age, height, weight of the mother, nationality of the mother and father, the presence of a deficiency in body weight and/or growth of the newborn for a specific HB in history, pregnancy parity 1, 4 or more); fetal (growth hormone and insulin-like growth factor-1 gene mutations, chromosomal abnormalities, fetal transfusion); maternal (chronic somatic pathology, accompanied by disseminated angiopathy, arterial hypertension, hypoxemia, infectious pathology of various organ systems, violation of the nutritional status of a pregnant woman with a deficiency of caloric index and nutrients, toxic effects of a number of drugs — anticonvulsants, anticoagulants, cytostatics, etc.); placental (malfunction of implantation and formation of placental complex with abnormal histological structure, low placenta, placental presentation and detachment, hemangiomas and placental infarctions, umbilical cord vascular pathology, malfunction of uteroplacental and fetoplacental circulation) [6, 7].

Deficiency of placental functions, occurring in 43.3–83.3% in children with ZVUR, is usually associated with chronic somatic diseases and infectious pathology, including the genitourinary sphere, in the mother. So, according to the studies, in mothers with diseases of the cardiovascular system, kidneys and urinary tract, gynecological pathology, the frequency of small children for HB varied from 60 to 85% [8]. Pathological mechanisms that slow down the growth rate of the fetus significantly reduce the growth and maturation of lung tissue, increasing the risk of developing BPD [9]. One of the necessary conditions to ensure adequate antenatal development of a child is to obtain a sufficient number of nutrients, which is ensured by the trophic function of the fetoplacental complex, the morphofunctional state of which plays a significant role in ensuring these processes [10].

In addition to trophic, the placenta has a variety of functions (excretory, barrier, endocrine, protein-synthetic, immunoregulatory), the optimal level of which is maintained by high metabolic activity in the mother-placenta-fetus system. Many functions of the fetoplacental complex ensure the growth and support the vital activity of the fetus, determining the outcome of pregnancy [11]. Infectious damage to the placenta, microthrombus formation in the capillary network due to both the infectious process and thrombophilic conditions significantly reduce the speed and volume of fetoplacental blood flow [12]. Morphologically, with hematogenous dissemination of infection in the placenta, villusitis and deciduitis are visualized with further spread of the infectious process to the chorial plate and amniotic membrane, and with an ascending type of infection, chorioamnionitis and intervillitis develop at the initial stages. Studies have shown that signs of both hematogenic and ascending infection occur in the placenta with ZVUR in a high percentage of cases (47.8% of full-term newborns with ZVUR) [13]. Signs of hematogenous dissemination of the process, represented by its characteristic manifestation — deciduitis, occur on average from 33% to 55%, with a predominance of parietal choriodeciduitis and umbilical vein phlebitis in premature babies, which indicated a more pronounced increase in the infectious process with hematogenous and ascending spread to the membranes of the placenta and further in babies born prematurely [14]. Therefore, an infectious factor affecting the structures of the fetoplacental complex plays an important role in fetal growth retardation and premature birth [15]. The action of damaging factors of various origins leads to the development of chronic FPN, with pathological and dissociated immaturity of chorionic villi. With the pathological type of immaturity, the predominance of intermediate villi is noted, and with dissociated — in addition to intermediate villi, terminal villi are found [16]. Characteristic morphological features of chronic FPN are involutive-dystrophic changes in the villous chorion in the form of: calcification, impaired blood circulation in villi, such as reduced vascularization, heart attacks, interstitial fibrosis in villi [17]. An important diagnostic criterion for the critical state

of the fetus is the data of Doppler examination of the cerebral vessels of the fetus with the determination of the blood flow rate in the anterior and middle cerebral arteries. Thus, a sharp decrease in speed indicators after the previous increase indicates the transition of chronic FPN to a critical stage with a high risk of antenatal fetal death [18]. Signs of acute decompensation of fetoplacental insufficiency, which leads to critical fetal hypoxia and is an indication for emergency delivery, are placental vascular paresis, hematomas, and reversible blood flow [19].

Postnatal consequences of pronounced hemodynamic disorders in the fetoplacental complex are neonatal asphyxia, impaired early neonatal adaptation with the development of hemodynamic, cerebral, gastrointestinal, respiratory disorders with a change in metabolic status, renal and endocrine dysfunction [20]. But in most cases, a wide range of compensatory-adaptive reactions of the placental complex allows, with short-term pathological influences of a moderate nature, to provide blood flow parameters that preserve the viability of the fetus, supporting growth and further development. However, the presence of chronic insufficiency of fetoplacental blood flow, as a rule, is accompanied by fetal growth retardation due to nutritional deficiency and intrauterine hypoxia [21].

It has been established that the combination of prematurity and low body weight for HBW significantly increases the incidence rate in the neonatal period, which may be associated with an interdependent combination of gestational immaturity and the structural and functional state of newborns with body weight deficiency. The risk of disability in children small for HB is almost 2 times increased. Moreover, the main disabling cause is the pathology of the central nervous system [22]. The course of the neonatal period in most cases is complicated by impaired postnatal adaptation with the development of post-hypoxic multiorgan dysfunctions, RDS, instability of hemodynamics, pathology of cerebral status, hypothermia, necrotizing enterocolitis, electrolytes (hypocalcemia, hypomagnesemia, hypophosphatemia), metabolic disorders, hypo- or hyperglycemia, hyperbilirubinemia [23]. By the end of the first month of life, there is a high risk of developing immunodeficiency states, chronic pathology of various organ systems, including BPD [24]. Body weight deficiency is accompanied by impaired endocrine system function, but primary endocrine dysfunction with pathology of the synthesis of growth hormone, insulin-like growth factor-1 (regulates growth processes in the fetal period) and insulin-like growth factor-2 (regulates growth processes in the embryonic period) has a pronounced effect on antenatal growth and development. It was found that deficiency of insulin-like growth factor-1 in small children for HB is accompanied by impaired cell proliferation of muscle, cartilage, bone and other tissues with a delay in the rate of morphofunctional maturation. In the absence of congenital pathology of insulin-like growth factor 1 synthesis or receptor expression to it, impaired production may be associated with chronic nutritional deficiency due

to FPN, which causes a decrease in the synthesis of insulin-like growth factor-1, insulin and inhibition of pancreatic β cell proliferation [25]. Hormonal imbalance in children small for HB includes adrenal dysfunction. Immaturity of the adrenal cortex in premature newborns or children who have undergone chronic intrauterine hypoxia and antenatal nutritional deficiency leads to hypocorticism of the neonatal period, which is one of the pathogenetic mechanisms of impaired neonatal adaptation. The peculiarities of hormonal regulation in case of impaired intrauterine development are preserved in the postnatal period. Thus, in premature infants with a decrease in the level of insulin-like growth factor-1, there is a slower rate of increase in mass-growth indicators and morphofunctional maturation of individual organ systems, mainly in the first months of life [26]. In the general population of patients of this category, there are two options for impaired postnatal physical development processes: with deficiency or excess body weight. According to the results of a number of studies, the rate of postnatal growth growth in children born with very low body weight and extremely low body weight has been reduced, and by 3–4 years up to 50% of them are deficient in weight and/or growth [25]. Against the background of such features of morphofunctional development, the pathology of various systems of organs of perinatal genesis can acquire a prolonged character due to the low rates of regeneration, growth and formation of functional activity.

Conclusion. The problem of the effect of antenatal nutritional deficiency on the growth and development of the bronchopulmonary system and the frequency of BPD formation, despite individual studies, continues to be poorly understood. It was noted that chronic antenatal deficiency of plastic components due to FPN can lead not only to a delay in the rate of increase in mass-growth indicators, but also have a significant impact on the processes of cell proliferation, growth and development of vascular structures of the lungs, components of air ducts and gas exchange pathways.

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PROSPECTS FOR USING MELON CROPS IN WINE PRODUCTION IN THE ORENBURG REGION

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At present, industrial melon cultivation in the Orenburg region is primarily concentrated in the southeastern part of the region. The center of watermelon production in the Orenburg region is Sol-Iletsk. The natural and climatic conditions of the region allow for achieving high taste and quality characteristics of this crop and obtaining significant economic benefits from its cultivation. In terms of area occupied by melon crops, the city of Sol-Iletsk is currently one of the largest Russian centers for watermelon cultivation.

Watermelons of various varieties can be used in wine production. This issue has become increasingly relevant in recent years. Therefore, our research analyzed the most widespread watermelon varieties in the Orenburg region that can be used in the production of wine products [1].

The outcome of our research is a food product — wine made from watermelons and melons cultivated in the Orenburg region, Sol-Iletsk.

The melon variety ‘Ethiopka’ and the watermelon variety ‘Kholodok’ were used.

The Ethiopka melon variety was developed by Russian breeders. This self-pollinating variety primarily exhibits a male flowering type. The Ethiopka melon demonstrated the highest results in both fruit size and overall yield. To date, the Ethiopka melon is gaining popularity almost worldwide. Breeders in many countries are working to improve this variety and develop various melon varieties.

Main characteristics of the melon variety Ethiopka:

- mid-early variety;
- ripening period of 72–85 days (from the date of mass emergence);
- fruit weight 3–5 kg (individual fruits can reach approximately 7 kg);
- fruits are round-oval in shape, distinctly segmented into «sections»;
- fruit surface is rough with pronounced netting;
- fruits have a honey-like flavor with elevated sugar content [2].

Watermelon fruits contain up to 4% seeds. With an average watermelon yield of 60 centners per hectare, seed collection ranges from 0.4 to 2.1 centners per hectare. Watermelon seeds are a secondary oil-containing product during the processing of watermelons at canning factories.

The Coldok watermelon variety is characterized by low caloric content and a high concentration of essential micronutrients. This variety differs from other representatives of its species by its exceptional hardiness in cultivation, considerable shelf life, and refined taste. This variety of watermelon can be cultivated both in greenhouses and in open field conditions. The leaves are bright green. The fruits can have a slightly elongated spherical shape, reaching a weight of 4 to 4.5 kg.

The rind is green with a netted pattern, with moderate thickness. The flesh of the ripe ‘Kholodok’ watermelon variety is red, granular, juicy, with a pink tint and a slightly sweet taste. The place of origin of this variety is Russia, Volgograd region.

The Kholodok variety is high-yielding; under favorable weather conditions, it is possible to harvest no less than 30 t per hectare, and up to 7 kg of watermelon per 1 sq. m [3].

A classical technology was applied for wine production, with the differences restricted to the wine formulation. The production stages included: raw material preparation; must preparation; fermentation initiation; first filtration cycle; quiet fermentation; beverage maturation; product clarification; bottling. Wine packaging and bottle aging. It is crucial to maintain stable temperature and humidity throughout the entire storage period: $t = +14...+16$ °C, humidity in the storage area maintained between 60 and 80%. Shelf life: 9 to 14 months. Previous research has established that the recommended wine aging period exceeds 3 months. [4].

Imagine — each bottle contains a unique flavor. Specialized tasting glasses were used for the wine tasting. It is recommended to fill the glass carefully with wine, without causing foaming, up to 50 cm³. The organoleptic analysis begins with the assessment of clarity [5].

A tasting glass, lightly filled, is placed between the light source and the eye, but not on the same line, and examined. Good wine should be transparent, free from sediment and foreign particles, with a color ranging from light yellow to dark red. The wine was transparent, clear, and sparkling [6]. Tasting is conducted indoors at a temperature of 15–18 oC, as stipulated by the regulations for wine tasting and

GOST 32051–2013 ‘Winemaking Products.’ Methods of Organoleptic Analysis. Tasting is an activity or event aimed at evaluating various characteristics of the product: gustatory, aromatic, and structural. Tasting is performed in a bright, evenly illuminated, well-ventilated, and clean room at a temperature of 15–16 °C. The optimal time to conduct a tasting is 10 a.m. The wine tasting was conducted by ten tasters. It is not recommended to begin tasting immediately before or immediately after a meal; smoking, eating, and drinking should be avoided for thirty minutes prior to the testing [7].

According to the article “The Use of Melon in Wine Production,” organoleptic assessments were carried out on two formulations by three tasters.

Following the tasting evaluation, a general impression of the analyzed product is formulated.

Wine samples No. 1 and No. 3 received the highest score of 1 point for typicality (full compliance with the wine type); regarding clarity, sample No. 2 stands out with 0.5 points (crystal clear). The highest scores were observed for samples No. 2 and No. 3 in the wine bouquet category-3.0 points — indicating that the melon wine’s bouquet is delicate, harmonious, and typologically appropriate.

The highest taste score was recorded for sample No. 1 (4 points), while the lowest was for sample No. 2 (2.7 points).

The sensory evaluation established that the wine produced according to recipe No. 1 (total score 7.1) and No. 2 (total score 7.6) qualifies as good wine. The wine produced according to recipe No. 3 (total score 8.3) qualifies as excellent wine.

Data analysis indicates that both variants of melon wine exhibit not only an attractive appearance and pleasant aroma and taste but also physico-chemical parameters within the normal range.

The mass concentration of titratable acids, recalculated as malic acid, in fruit wines, taking into account permissible deviations, is no less than 4.0 g/dm³. In the investigated samples, the permissible values range from 8.5 to 15 g/dm³.

The mass concentration of sugars in fruit wines, considering allowable deviations, is as follows, g/dm³: dry — no more than 4.0; semi-dry — more than 4.0 and less than 30.0 g/dm³. Thus, the melon wine obtained according to the presented recipes and technology is classified as dry.

The wine was produced from melon with an alcohol content by volume of 14.1% for sample No. 1, 10.5% for sample No. 2, and 9.6% for sample No. 3 [8].

According to the results presented in the article ‘Perspectives for Using Watermelon in Wine Production’, following the assessment of organoleptic parameters, the watermelon wine is clear and free of sediment due to timely filtration during aging. The wine maturation was conducted over a two-month period.

According to the data presented in the table, we obtained a semi-dry watermelon table wine [9].

The Orenburg region is one of the leading regions in Russia for melon crop production; therefore, processing products that are not fully marketed in fresh form is highly relevant to the regional economy. The authors consider it expedient to produce and market this product due to the lack of competition.

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THE USE OF JERUSALEM ARTICHOKE JUICE IN PRODUCTION NON-ALCOHOLIC CARBONATED BEVERAGES OF FUNCTIONAL ORIENTATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the feasibility and potential application of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the production of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages with a functional orientation. The use of inulin-containing raw materials in beverages of this group is substantiated. It has been established that the optimal proportion of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the production of non-alcoholic carbonated functional beverages is 50% of the total mass of the finished product. At the same time, besides the functional value, the beverage exhibits high organoleptic properties.*

Keywords: *juice, Jerusalem artichoke, inulin, non-alcoholic carbonated beverage, functional beverage, quality.*

The ‘Rome Declaration on World Food Security’ (1996) affirms the obligation of every state to guarantee the right of every individual to access safe and nutritious food products in accordance with the right to adequate food and the right to be free from hunger [6]. A key element of food security is food independence, defined as a country’s ability to independently supply itself with essential food products. Achieving this requires efficient utilization of national resources, advancement of agricultural production, and the adoption of innovative technologies within the agro-industrial complex. Trends over the past decade indicate a shift in consumer preference from traditional carbonated soft drinks with high sugar content to more natural and functional alternatives [2, 5]. New consumer demands regarding diet and beverage choices are driving changes in the range of food products produced. Food industry enterprises increasingly aim to manufacture products that are not only palatable and nutritious but also possess specific functional properties. The non-alcoholic beverage sector is no exception.

Jerusalem artichoke (earth pear) is a tuber long utilized in dietary nutrition. It is rich in inulin — a natural prebiotic that supports digestion and promotes

intestinal health. It also contains numerous vitamins and minerals — for example, potassium, magnesium, and vitamin C. Jerusalem artichoke juice is an intriguing and beneficial product that can form the basis for a new direction in the production of non-alcoholic beverages. It complies with contemporary requirements: natural, functional, and suitable for healthy nutrition and local production. Its primary advantage is a low glycemic index [1, 3, 4, 7, 8]. This indicates that it does not induce a rapid increase in blood glucose levels, making it suitable for individuals with diabetes, those managing their weight, or anyone aiming for proper nutrition. Such beverages can occupy a niche on store shelves, particularly if formulation development and marketing are conducted competently.

Given the trend toward a healthy lifestyle and reduced sugar consumption, beverages based on Jerusalem artichoke present an excellent alternative to conventional juices and sodas, highlighting the relevance of producing beverages based on Jerusalem artichoke juice.

In light of the above, the objective of our study was to determine the optimal dosage of Jerusalem artichoke juice in producing non-alcoholic functional beverages to obtain a product characterized by high physiological and organoleptic qualities.

The experimental design included the use of Jerusalem artichoke juice at concentrations of 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60% of the total mass of the finished product. The variant with the lowest juice content was designated as the control. It was also considered that in studies by various authors, the use of Jerusalem artichoke juice as an additive (rather than as the main ingredient) in the production of various beverages is recommended at these specific concentrations [3, 7, 8]. Natural juice obtained from fresh Jerusalem artichoke tubers, subjected to thermal treatment followed by filtration, was used as raw material. The quality of the final product was assessed using generally accepted methods.

Inulin is highly soluble in water; consequently, the blend was transparent, homogeneous, and exhibited a consistency typical of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages. Because inulin is prone to caramelization during heat treatment, the initial phase of this process favorably influenced the development of the color, taste, and aroma of the final product. Simultaneously, it was taken into account that at temperatures exceeding 700 °C, inulin undergoes degradation. Therefore, it is preferable to use it in the production of food products that do not undergo prolonged thermal treatment during manufacturing. Thus, the application of Jerusalem artichoke juice in physiologically significant concentrations is most justified specifically in the production of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages. Moreover, the use of carbon dioxide, regarded as inert in the food industry, during their production will help preserve the quality of the finished product, as well as its microbiological stability and safety.

The taste and aroma of Jerusalem artichoke juice are faint, with an aftertaste reminiscent of raw potato. To improve the flavor and aromatic profile, we recommend incorporating natural lemon juice into the beverage formulation. We have determined its optimal dosage to be 5 liters per 100 decaliters of the finished product. Furthermore, to enhance the flavor of the non-alcoholic carbonated beverage, we propose the use of erythritol (E968) at 71.4 kg per 100 decaliters of the finished product. It is sweet (approximately 70% as sweet as sugar), contains zero calories, does not affect glucose or insulin levels, has a mild cooling effect, and does not cause dental caries, making it ideal for diabetics and those aiming to lose weight, and therefore suitable as an ingredient for non-alcoholic carbonated beverages with a functional focus.

The results of the organoleptic quality assessment using the widely accepted 25-point scale did not fully capture the differences in product quality. Therefore, to conduct the sensory evaluation, we developed criteria based on a five-point scale covering an expanded set of indicators, the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Results of the sensory evaluation of organoleptic quality indicators of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages containing Jerusalem artichoke juice

Mass fraction of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the beverage formulation, %	Organoleptic indicators						Overall assessment
	Appearance	Color	Clarity	Consistency	Taste	Smell (aroma)	
20 (control)	3,8±1,07	3,4±0,53	4,4±0,53	5,0±0,00	3,1±0,37	3,4±0,78	23,1
30	4,4±0,53	4,1±0,37	4,4±0,53	5,0±0,00	3,8±0,69	3,4±0,78	25,1
40	4,8±0,37	4,8±0,37	4,7 ±0,48	5,0±0,00	4,1±0,37	3,8±0,69	27,2
50	4,7±0,75	4,8±0,37	5,0±0,00	4,8±0,37	4,8±0,37	4,5±0,53	28,6
60	4,7±0,75	4,5±0,53	5,0±0,00	4,7±0,75	4,4±0,53	4,7 ±0,48	28,0

The beverages exhibited a brown color characteristic of caramelized sugar. The intensity of coloration increased with the rising concentration of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the finished beverage. A light brown color, as well as an excessively dark one, resulted in lower evaluation scores. Thus, the beverage in the control variant scored only 3.4±0.53 points, whereas the highest score, 4.8±0.37, was achieved in variants using Jerusalem artichoke juice at 40 and 50% of the finished product mass; further increases in juice concentration led to a decrease. Increasing the mass concentration of juice in the final product led to the formation of a slight sediment, which lowered the scores for consistency and appearance; however, the transparency of the beverage itself increased. The variant containing

Jerusalem artichoke juice at 50 % of the total mass of the finished product exhibited optimal taste and aroma. At lower concentrations, the beverages were perceived as more watery, whereas increasing the juice proportion to 60 % resulted in a distinct bitter aftertaste and aroma nuance. Thus, according to the results of the sensory evaluation, the optimal non-alcoholic carbonated beverage was that containing Jerusalem artichoke juice at 50 % of the total mass of the finished product. It received a score of 28.6 points out of a possible 30.

The results of the quality assessment of non-alcoholic carbonated beverages containing Jerusalem artichoke juice, based on physicochemical quality parameters, are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Physicochemical Quality Parameters of Non-Alcoholic Carbonated Beverages
with the use of Jerusalem artichoke juice

Indicator	Mass fraction of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the beverage formulation, %				
	20 (control)	30	40	50	60
Density, g/cm ³	1,032	1,036	1,040	1,048	1,056
pH	4,1	4,0	3,95	3,9	3,8
Titration acidity, g/L	1,8	2,0	2,4	2,8	3,2
Mass fraction of soluble solids, %	10,8	12,0	13,6	15,2	16,8
Fat content, g per 100 g	0,10	0,15	0,20	0,25	0,30
Protein content, g per 100 g	0,40	0,60	0,80	1,00	1,20
Carbohydrate content, g per 100 g	10,30	11,90	13,40	15,00	16,50
Energy value, kcal/kJ	43,70/182,67	51,35/ 214,64	58,60/244,95	66,30/252,05	73,50/307,23

As shown in the table, increasing the dosage of Jerusalem artichoke juice in the beverage resulted in increased density, soluble solids content, and product acidity. The energy value of the beverage is low. In the 50 % variant, recognized as the best based on sensory evaluation results, the energy value is 66.3 kcal or 252.05 kJ.

Therefore, in the production of a non-alcoholic carbonated inulin-containing beverage using Jerusalem artichoke juice, it is recommended to use it at 50 % of the total mass of the finished product. This will enable specialized enterprises to expand their product range and supply the population with a new, safe functional food product. The results of the economic efficiency analysis of producing this beverage indicate that profitability can be at least 35 %. This indicates that the production of this beverage is economically justified.

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MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF A HYBRID RENEWABLE ENERGY GENERATION SYSTEM

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Annotation. *This study is justified by the need to improve the energy efficiency of residential buildings that use energy from non-renewable sources. This approach creates significant environmental risks, including air and environmental pollution from greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, there is a threat to energy security caused by rising prices of traditional energy sources. Given the growing awareness of environmental and energy risks associated with the exploitation of non-renewable resources, it is becoming important to develop and implement modern innovative and sustainable methods of planning urban infrastructure and energy systems aimed at minimizing these threats. It is extremely important to develop a mathematical model for designing residential areas that fully operate on the basis of renewable and environmentally friendly energy sources.*

Modern solar energy, based on the world's leading technologies, is a viable alternative to conventional energy sources. Solar power is projected to dominate the green technology market by 2050, and by the end of the twenty-first century, it will be able to meet 75% to 90% of all global electricity needs.

Keywords: *mathematical models, renewable sources, solar energy, wind turbines, batteries, hybrid systems.*

The aim of this study is to develop a mathematical model of a hybrid energy supply system combining solar photovoltaic, wind and battery installations

that can meet the average energy needs of an urban residential area. As part of the work, a comprehensive assessment of the benefits, technical and economic feasibility of hybrid systems, as well as their role in the transition from fossil fuels to “green” energy sources in the context of creating a sustainable urban environment is planned.

The main objective of the study is to:

Development of a mathematical model as a basis for designing a hybrid renewable energy system, including solar photovoltaic and wind installations for a residential area.

The scientific and practical aspects of the research are focused on informing engineers, architects, environmental specialists and other stakeholders investing in the creation of environmentally sustainable urban settlements. The paper presents mathematical models of hybrid power systems, identifies potential problems and develops recommendations for their use in the design of sustainable residential areas. This study contributes to the scientific discourse on the development of photovoltaic and wind technologies. Moreover, the results contribute to raising awareness of the benefits of switching to renewable energy sources and allow us to assess their impact on the energy balance of urban areas.

The object of the study is mathematical models of a hybrid energy system combining solar photovoltaic and wind installations capable of supplying an average level of energy demand in a residential area. The territorial scope of research is not limited; the presented solutions and approaches are universal and can be applied in different regions of the world, provided that they meet the basic requirements for the resource base and energy needs.

Introduction. Scientific and technological progress acts as a key factor contributing to the development of production processes, which is manifested in a constant increase in electricity consumption. In the modern world, most energy systems are still based on traditional sources, such as fossil fuels-oil, coal, and natural gas-that have been stored in the Earth’s interior for millions of years [8]. Although the processes of formation of these resources continue under the influence of high temperatures and pressure, their use is carried out much faster than replenishment, which threatens to deplete resources and cause environmental problems [5].

Researchers emphasize that photovoltaic systems, along with wind installations that use solar radiation and wind resources to generate electricity, are becoming dominant in the context of development along with other sources of green energy [10]. Renewable energy sources (RES), which have a number of significant advantages, are increasingly being used to solve current energy and environmental problems. The main ones are inexhaustibility and a high level of environmental friendliness, which makes RES a viable alternative to traditional energy sources [6]. These technologies can simultaneously solve three global problems:

ensuring energy security, environmental protection, and food security [2]. Their development is supported by the introduction of modern technologies, such as meteorology, aerodynamics, heat and power engineering, which also contributes to increasing domestic demand for machine-building products and expanding the country's export opportunities [3].

Scientists identify several innovative areas in the electric power industry, due to recent technological advances. These innovations make it possible to integrate a variety of energy sources into a single power supply system, which contributes to the creation of sustainable energy solutions, such as small solar installations, wind systems and traditional large-scale generators [11].

The paper examines the technical characteristics and functional advantages of such systems in the context of their reliability, efficiency, and level of energy generation. The study discusses the benefits of implementing these systems for domestic consumers, and also develops recommendations aimed at identifying investment priorities and facilitating the transition from oil and gas-oriented technologies to sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions in the field of green energy that can ensure long-term energy security [9].

This study examines mathematical models and aspects of the use of renewable energy systems in residential buildings, with an emphasis on the role of solar photovoltaic installations as the main source of energy for households. The potential of small wind farms to provide autonomous electricity supply is also discussed. Special attention is paid to the integration of hybrid solutions that include solar photovoltaic modules and battery-based energy storage systems.

Mathematical Modeling of a Photovoltaic Grid

Mathematical modeling of photovoltaic arrays is an important tool in the field of renewable energy sources, helping to optimize the design and increase the efficiency of solar energy systems. Photovoltaic arrays made up of multiple solar panels convert solar energy into electrical energy, and their performance depends on various factors, including geographical conditions, panel orientation, and material structure.

One of the key tasks of mathematical modeling is to develop complex models that take into account the physical and chemical processes occurring in solar cell materials. This includes modeling photovoltaic processes, the transformation of light into electricity, and the dynamics of thermal processes. The use of differential equations and finite element models makes it possible to analyze the behavior of photovoltaic cells under various operating conditions. In addition, mathematical modeling helps optimize the arrangement of panels within the photovoltaic grid. Algorithms based on optimization theory use simulation results to determine the tilt angles and orientation of panels, which allows you to maximize solar insolation and, consequently, increase the overall efficiency of the system. This

is particularly relevant in the context of integrating photovoltaic solutions into existing infrastructure and in conditions of limited space.

Equation (1) expresses the output power of the photovoltaic array P_{pv} , which is a function of the area of the photovoltaic generator A_{pvg} , the efficiency of the photovoltaic generator μ_{pvg} , and the global radiation G_{irr} . G_{irr} — this is the energy received from the sun in the form of electromagnetic radiation.

$$P_{pvg} = \mu_{pvg} * A_{pvg} G_{irr} \quad (1)$$

where;

P_{pvg} — Output power of the photovoltaic grid

μ_{pvg} — Efficiency of the photovoltaic generator

A_{pvg} — Area of the photovoltaic generator

G_{irr} — Global solar radiation

Global solar radiation depends on the slope of the measured surface, the height of the sun above the Earth's surface, and atmospheric conditions.

The efficiency of converting solar energy into electrical energy in photovoltaic systems depends significantly on a number of factors, among which the slope of the measured surface, the height of the sun above the horizon and atmospheric conditions play a key role. These parameters determine both the amount of solar radiation reaching the surface and its quality, which directly affects the performance of solar panels.

The slope of the measured surface, i.e. the angle at which the solar panels are oriented relative to the horizon, is critical for maximizing the absorption of solar radiation. The optimal tilt angle allows you to minimize the reflection of sunlight and provide maximum insolation. Studies show that even small deviations from the optimal angle can lead to significant losses in productivity, especially in conditions of high solar activity. The angle of inclination must be adapted depending on the time of year and geographical location, which requires the use of tracking systems that allow you to monitor the movement of the sun in the sky.

The height of the sun above the Earth's surface, determined by the angle of its location above the horizon, also has a significant effect on the intensity of solar radiation reaching the surface. In the midday hours, when the sun is at its zenith, insolation reaches its maximum, while in the morning and evening hours, when the sun is low above the horizon, the light intensity decreases significantly. With this in mind, the design of photovoltaic systems should take into account the dynamics of changes in the height of the sun during the day and seasons, which allows optimizing their performance.

Atmospheric conditions such as cloud cover, air pollution, humidity, and the presence of aerosols also play an important role in the process of absorbing solar

radiation. Cloudy conditions can significantly reduce the level of available light, while air pollution can reduce the quality of solar radiation by changing its spectral composition. These factors can lead to significant fluctuations in the efficiency of solar panels even within a single day.

Equation (2) expresses the efficiency of the photovoltaic generator μ_{pv} , which is affected by the ambient temperature, as:

$$\mu_{pv} = \mu_{ref} * [1 - \varphi * (T_s - T_{ref})] \quad (2)$$

where;

μ_{pv} — Efficiency of the photovoltaic generator

μ_{ref} — reference efficiency of the photovoltaic module

φ — silicon elements with a constant temperature coefficient

T_c — Solar wind temperature

T_{ref} — reference temperature of the solar cell, i.e. 25°C

The efficiency of solar panels is tested at a temperature of 25°C. The nominal operating temperature of a cell is defined as the temperature of the solar panel based on the following four basic standard reference conditions:

- Solar panel power = 800 W / m².
- Wind speed = 1 m/s.
- Air temperature = 20 °C.
- Tilt angle (with open rack) = 45° from horizontal.

The variability between solar radiation temperature, ambient temperature, nominal operating temperature of photovoltaic cells, and global exposure level is a key aspect in evaluating the efficiency of solar power systems. These parameters are interrelated and have a significant impact on the performance of photovoltaic installations. The temperature of solar radiation is usually determined by the intensity of sunlight and the angle of incidence of sunlight. In conditions of high solar radiation, when the level of radiation reaches its maximum, the temperature of the solar cell also increases. This leads to an increase in thermal stress on the material from which it is made, which, in turn, can degrade its electrical characteristics. Studies show that with an increase in the temperature of a solar cell, its efficiency in converting solar energy into electrical energy decreases, in particular, due to an increase in the leakage current level and a decrease in the band gap of a semiconductor material.

Ambient temperature plays an important role in the dynamics of thermal processes. At high ambient temperatures, the efficiency of photovoltaic cells is further reduced, since they cannot effectively dissipate heat. This creates additional productivity losses, especially in hot climates. The nominal operating temperature (NW) of an element is usually set by the manufacturer and is defined as the temperature at which the elements must function with a given efficiency.

Comparing the NW with the actual operating temperature conditions allows you to predict possible deviations in performance.

The global level of exposure, which is the sum of direct and scattered solar radiation, also has a significant impact on the performance of photovoltaic systems. A high level of radiation exposure can compensate for some of the losses caused by the increased temperature of the sun, but only within the limits that do not exceed their thermal limits. At the same time, in conditions of increased cloud cover or atmospheric pollution, the level of radiation exposure can significantly decrease, which, in combination with high temperatures, leads to significant energy losses.

Equation (3) shows the relationship between the solar radiation temperature, the ambient temperature, the nominal operating temperature of the cell, and the global radiation level;

$$T_s = T_{amb} + \left(\frac{N_T - 20}{800} \right) G_{irr} \quad (3)$$

where;

T_c — Solar wind temperature

T_{amb} — Ambient temperature

N_T — rated operating temperature of the element (20 °C)

G_{irr} — Global solar illumination

Thus, a comprehensive study of the relationship between solar radiation temperature, ambient temperature, nominal operating temperature of elements, and global exposure level provides a deeper understanding of the mechanisms that affect the efficiency of photovoltaic systems. This knowledge is critical for developing methods for optimizing their operation, selecting suitable technologies and materials, and adapting systems to different climatic conditions, which ultimately contributes to more efficient use of solar energy. The dependence of the efficiency of solar systems on the slope of the measured surface, the height of the sun above the Earth's surface and atmospheric conditions emphasizes the need for an integrated approach to the design and operation of photovoltaic installations. Taking these factors into account can improve overall system performance, which is an important step towards more efficient use of solar energy in various climatic conditions.

Number of Photovoltaic Panels

Equation (4) is used to determine the number of photovoltaic panels required for an array.

$$N = \frac{C}{P} \quad (4)$$

where;

C is the total power of the solar photovoltaic system in watts (W)

P — Output power per panel in watts (W)

N — Required number of panels

Determining the size of the land plot needed to accommodate the system infrastructure is a necessary part of system design and analysis. The size of the photovoltaic panels, the distance between the panels, and the space for the control room, storage of batteries, inverters, and other auxiliary equipment are all determining factors that must be considered when calculating and allocating the site area.

In conclusion, mathematical modeling of photovoltaic arrays is an integral part of modern research in the field of solar energy. It provides an in-depth understanding of the processes that affect system efficiency and creates opportunities for further innovation in the design, operation and management of photovoltaic installations. Efficient models have the potential to significantly improve the overall efficiency of solar energy use, facilitating the transition to sustainable energy sources on a global scale.

Mathematical Modeling of a Wind Turbine

Mathematical modeling of wind turbines is an important tool in the field of renewable energy sources, playing a key role in optimizing the design, improving efficiency and ensuring the reliability of these devices. With the growing interest in sustainable energy solutions, the need for accurate and efficient wind turbine models is becoming more urgent than ever.

One of the main tasks of mathematical modeling is to analyze the aerodynamic characteristics of a wind turbine. Models based on the Navier-Stokes equations allow us to study the air flow around the turbine blades, taking into account such parameters as wind speed, angle of attack, and blade geometry. This makes it possible to predict the efficiency of converting kinetic wind energy into mechanical energy, and then into electrical energy. In addition, such models help to optimize the shape and size of the blades, which can lead to a significant increase in efficiency.

Mathematical modeling also makes it possible to evaluate the dynamic characteristics of wind turbines. For this purpose, models are used that take into account the interaction of various system components, such as the generator, gearbox, and control systems. Dynamic models help determine the behavior of the turbine under conditions of variable wind loads and different generator operation, which increases the reliability of the system and minimizes the risk of damage.

Another important aspect is the application of mathematical models to analyze the environmental impact of wind turbines. Models can be used to assess acoustic and visual effects, as well as the impact on ecosystems, which is key for conducting environmental assessments and obtaining permits for the installation of wind farms.

In addition, mathematical modeling of wind turbines plays an important role in predicting performance under real-world operating conditions. Using wind

data, models can predict energy production under different climatic conditions, enabling efficient operation planning and resource management.

The instantaneous output power $P_{wt}(t)$ from the wind turbine depends principally on wind speed v_w , which is dependent on weather conditions, and is expressed in Equation (5) as:

$$P_{wt}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } v_w < v_{ci} \\ \frac{1}{2}c_p(\alpha, \sigma)\rho_{air}A_{wt}v_w^3(t) & \text{if } v_{ci} \leq v_w \leq v_{rw} \\ P_{rated} & \text{if } v_{rw} < v_w < v_{co} \\ 0 & \text{if } v_w \geq v_{co} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where;

$P_{wt}(t)$ — Instantaneous power output

v_w — Wind velocity

v_{ci} — Cut-in wind velocity

C_p — Coefficient of power (related to)

α — Tip speed ratio

σ — Blade pitch angle

ρ_{air} — Air density

A_{wt} — Swept blade area

v_{rw} — the rated wind velocity

v_{co} — The cut-out wind velocity

If the wind speed exceeds the rated speed of 9 m/s, the wind turbine operates at a constant output power, however, when the wind speed is below 3 m/s or above 20 m/s, the wind turbine stops working.

Thus, mathematical modeling of wind turbines is an integral part of the modern approach to the development and operation of wind power systems. It provides a deep understanding of the processes that occur in these devices, and creates opportunities for their optimization and efficiency, which in turn contributes to the development of sustainable energy and reducing dependence on fossil energy sources.

Mathematical modeling of a hybrid generator

Mathematical modeling of hybrid generators consisting of a photovoltaic grid and a wind turbine is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of the transition to sustainable and renewable energy sources. Such systems make it possible to effectively combine the advantages of solar and wind energy, ensuring stable electricity generation in conditions of variable climatic and weather factors [9]. Modeling such systems involves several key aspects, each of which is critical for ensuring efficient operation and optimizing processes.

1. Modeling of energy processes

The first and most important aspect is modeling the energy processes occurring in each of the system components. For a photovoltaic grid, this includes analyzing

the dependence of power generation on the level of solar radiation, the angle of inclination of the panels, and temperature. Models based on equations describing photovoltaic processes allow us to predict electricity generation depending on these factors.

A wind turbine requires models that take into account the aerodynamic characteristics and dynamics of the air flow around the blades. According to the Navier-Stokes equations, which are used to analyze the interaction of wind with a turbine, which makes it possible to determine the efficiency of converting kinetic wind energy into mechanical and, subsequently, into electrical energy. This method is based on the use of an aerodynamic model. To solve the Navier-Stokes equations, it is necessary to determine the force field acting on air masses in the surface layer of the atmosphere, and also take into account parameters known as the barometric gradient.

2. System interaction

The second aspect is modeling the interaction between the components of a hybrid system. This includes creating integrated models that take into account both the electrical connection between the photovoltaic grid and the wind turbine, and their interaction with energy storage devices such as accumulators or capacitors. Analysis of energy flows in the system allows you to optimize the distribution of generated electricity, which is critical for improving overall efficiency.

3. Accounting of meteorological data

The third important aspect of modeling is the accounting of meteorological data. Since the performance of both solar and wind systems depends on external climatic conditions, the use of historical data on wind speed, solar radiation levels, temperature and humidity allows for a more accurate assessment of potential energy production. The use of statistical and probabilistic methods to analyze this data contributes to the creation of more reliable forecasts.

4. System optimization

The fourth aspect is to optimize the operation of the hybrid generator. This may include the use of control and optimization algorithms that allow you to adapt the system to changing conditions. Models can be used to develop management strategies aimed at maximizing overall energy production and minimizing losses, which is especially important in variable load conditions.

5. Environmental and economic factors

Finally, mathematical modeling should take into account environmental and economic factors. Environmental impact assessment, as well as the cost-effectiveness of installing a hybrid generator, are important aspects that influence decisions about its design and operation. Modeling can be used to analyze the life cycle of a system, including installation costs, operating costs, and possible environmental impacts.

The output energy of a hybrid generator is the sum of the energy generated by the photovoltaic grid and the wind turbine, adjusted for losses, which allows you to get a more accurate estimate of the total available energy for further use. This approach to calculating energy output helps optimize the design and operation of hybrid systems aimed at improving the efficiency of using renewable energy sources.

Equation (6) expresses the output energy of a hybrid generator consisting of a photovoltaic grid and a wind turbine in the form:

where;

$$E_{hyb}(t) = E_{pvg}(t) + E_{wt}(t) \quad (6)$$

$E_{hyb}(t)$ — output energy of the hybrid generator

$E_{pvg}(t)$ — output energy of the photovoltaic generator

$E_{wt}(t)$ — wind turbine power output

It is assumed that the battery is in the process of charging when the output energy of the generator $E_{hyb}(t)$ exceeds the power consumption of the load $E_{ld}(t)$.

This state of charge (SOC) at timet is expressed in equation (6) as:

$$SOC(t) = SOC(t-1) * (1-\theta) + \left[E_{hyb}(t) - \frac{E_{ld}(t)}{\mu_{inv}} \right] * \mu_{b,c} \quad (7)$$

where;

SOC-State of charge

θ — hourly self-discharge rate

$E_{hyb}(t)$ — output energy of the hybrid generator

$E_{ld}(t)$ — power consumption of the load

μ_{inv} — Efficiency of the inverter (0.93)

$\mu_{b,c}$ — Battery charging efficiency (0.65–0.85)

$SOC(t)$ and $SOC(t-1)$ represent the charge level at time t and t-1, respectively.

The battery is in the state of discharge, expressed by equation (8), when the output energy of the generator $E_{hyb}(t)$ is less than the power consumption of the load $E_{ld}(t)$. During this discharge process, its state of charge (SOC) at time t is given as:

$$SOC(t) = Soc(t-1) * (1-\theta) + \left[\frac{E_{ld}(t)}{\mu_{inv}} - E_{hyb}(t) \right] * \mu_{b,dis} \quad (8)$$

where;

SOC — State of charge

θ — hourly self-discharge rate (0.13% per day)

$E_{hyb}(t)$ — output energy of the hybrid generator

$E_{ld}(t)$ — power consumption of the load

μ_{inv} — Efficiency of the inverter (0.93)

$\mu_{b\ dis}$ — Battery discharge efficiency

The battery capacity C_{batt} modeled in equation (9), is required to maintain the FIELD for a certain number of days N_d . In this study N_d take for one day. The DoD represents the maximum reset depth, which is usually 70%.

$$C_{batt} = \frac{E_{ld}(t) * N_d}{DoD * \mu_{inv} * \mu_{b\ dis}} \quad (9)$$

where;

C_{batt} — Battery capacity

$E_{ld}(t)$ — power consumption of the load

N_d — Number of days

DoD — Reset depth

$FIELD$ — Electrical load consumed

μ_{inv} — Efficiency of the inverter (0.93)

$\mu_{b\ dis}$ — Battery discharge efficiency

Thus, mathematical modeling of a hybrid generator consisting of a photovoltaic grid and a wind turbine is a multi-faceted process that includes various aspects, from energy processes and system interaction to taking into account meteorological conditions and optimizing operation. These models play a key role in developing efficient and sustainable systems that support the transition to cleaner energy sources.

Technical Analysis of a Hybrid Power System with Photovoltaic and Wind Batteries

Technical analysis of a hybrid power system consisting of photovoltaic and wind batteries provides a number of significant advantages and opportunities for optimizing the operation of such systems. The main aspects that are provided by this analysis include: Interaction modeling; Performance evaluation; Design optimization; Sustainability and reliability analysis; Economic efficiency; and Environmental impact.

Technical analysis allows for a comprehensive assessment of system performance, which includes an analysis of energy generation from each component in different climatic and weather conditions. This allows you to identify optimal operating modes and predict total power generation based on historical meteorological data.

Equations (10) and (11) give the energy generated by the hybrid system in the form:

$$E_{hyb} = E_{pvg} + E_{wt} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} E_{pvg}(t) = P_{pvg}(t) * \Delta t \\ E_{wt}(t) = P_{wt}(t) * \Delta t \\ E_{ld}(t) = P_l(t) * \Delta t \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where;

E_{pvg} — Energy generated by the photovoltaic system

E_{wt} — Energy generated by a wind turbine

P_{pvg} — Power generated by the photovoltaic system

P_{wt} — Power generated by the wind turbine

E_{ld} — power consumption of the load

$P_{ld}(t)$ — load power consumption

Δt — simulation step time

It is necessary to take into account the maximum amount of energy that must be stored in the battery, known as the maximum state of charge (SOC_{max}), which is expressed in equation (12) below;

$$SOC(t) \leq SOC_{max} \quad (12)$$

The maximum allowable energy extracted from the battery is known as the minimum state of charge (SOC_{min}) and is expressed below in equation (13) as;

$$SOC(t) \geq SOC_{min} \quad (13)$$

For a battery system, if $SOC(t) \geq SOC_{min}$, then a certain percentage of the FIELD will not be fed. (13) The power loss (LPS) modeled in equation (14) below. A power supply loss (LPS) is an energy deficit that occurs when the energy generated by a renewable energy system and the energy stored in the battery system are insufficient to meet the electrical load requirement (ELD) [1].

$$LPS(t) = \frac{E_{ld}(t)}{\mu_{inv}} - E_{hyb}(t) - [SOC(t-1) * (1 - \theta) - SOC_{min}] * \mu_{b_dis} \quad (14)$$

in LPS, it is set as the ratio between 0 and 1 of all values. LPS refers to field consumption values for a specific time period. The probability of power source loss, LPSP, is a measure of the reliability of a power supply system. It quantifies the probability or frequency with which the power supply fails to meet the energy demand. Its function is given below in equation (15) as:

$$LPSP = \sum_{t=1}^T LPS(t) / \sum_t P_{ld}(t) \Delta t \quad (15),$$

An LPSP value of 0 indicates absolute reliability, while an LPSP value of 1 indicates complete unreliability.

Design optimization means that technical analysis can be used to determine the most effective configurations and parameters of system components. This includes choosing the optimal angle of inclination of photovoltaic panels and the installation height of wind turbines, as well as their dimensions and location. Design optimization helps maximize efficiency and reduce installation and operating costs.

The technical analysis makes it possible to simulate the interaction between photovoltaic and wind batteries, as well as to evaluate the effectiveness of their integration. This makes it possible to understand how one component can compensate for fluctuations in the power generation of another, which is especially important in conditions of variable load and unstable meteorological conditions.

Assessing the stability and reliability of a hybrid system is another important task of technical analysis. By analyzing various operational scenarios, it is possible to predict potential risks and failures in the system, which will allow us to develop measures to minimize them and improve overall reliability [7].

Technical analysis provides data for evaluating the economic efficiency of a hybrid power system. This includes payback periods, operating costs, and *потенциалы* decision-making potentials for project implementation [1].

It is also important to consider the environmental impact of a hybrid system. Technical analysis allows you to assess the carbon footprint, as well as possible environmental benefits associated with the use of renewable energy sources. This contributes to the formation of more sustainable solutions and improves the perception of projects on the part of society.

Thus, the technical analysis of a hybrid power system with photovoltaic and wind batteries contributes to a deeper understanding of the processes occurring in the system and provides the necessary tools for its optimization. This, in turn, contributes to improving the efficiency of the use of renewable energy sources, which is an important step towards sustainable development and reducing dependence on fossil fuels.

Economic Analysis of a Photovoltaic Wind Batteries Hybrid Energy System

The economic analysis of a hybrid energy system consisting of solar photovoltaic, wind and batteries systems is aimed at assessing the financial efficiency of implementing such systems and their long-term economic feasibility [11]. This analysis includes several key aspects that help determine not only the economic benefits, but also the optimal operating conditions for these renewable energy sources. The first element of economic analysis is the calculation of initial capital expenditures, which include the cost of purchasing and installing photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, and all related components such as inverters, control systems, batteries, and other equipment. Accounting for these costs

is necessary to estimate the total cost of the project at the start-up stage. Total operating costs for photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, and storage batteries are expressed in equations (16), (17), and (18), respectively. The total present value is the sum of the initial capital, operating and maintenance costs associated with each of the individual systems.

$$C^{pv} = C_{cap}^{pv} + C_{o\&m}^{pv} \tag{16}$$

$$C^{wt} = C_{cap}^{wt} + C_{o\&m}^{wt} \tag{17}$$

$$C^{bat} = C_{cap}^{bat} + C_{o\&m}^{bat} \tag{18}$$

where;

C^{pv} , C^{wt} , C^{bat} represent the total current cost of photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, and storage batteries, respectively.

C_{cap}^{pv} , C_{cap}^{wt} , C_{cap}^{bat} represent initial capital expenditures for photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, and battery systems, respectively.

$C_{o\&m}^{pv}$, $C_{o\&m}^{wt}$, $C_{o\&m}^{bat}$ represent the operating costs and maintenance of photovoltaic systems, wind turbines, and storage batteries, respectively. Operating expenses include the costs of maintaining and operating the system. In the case of a hybrid energy system consisting of photovoltaic and wind batteries, operating costs may include component health checks, equipment maintenance, and the cost of replacing elements that have a limited service life. In addition, it is important to take into account energy costs if the system uses auxiliary energy sources.

For a particular year, the total present value of the system components, TPV, which is the sum of the total present value for each of the individual system components (the cost depends on the specific country), is expressed in Equation (19) as follows:

$$TPV = C^{pv} + C^{wt} + C^{bat} \tag{19}$$

Equation (20) expresses the return on capital ratio, CRF, which allows you to convert initial investment costs into annual capital expenditures. The equation looks like this;

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1} \tag{20}$$

where;

t — economic assessment period

i — interest rate

Estimating the payback period of a project is an important element of economic analysis, which helps investors and system operators understand how long they will

be able to return their invested funds. The payback period depends on the initial capital investment, operating expenses, and revenue generated from generating and selling energy. The return on investment can be calculated using various financial indicators, such as the internal rate of return (IRR) and net present value (NPV), which allow you to assess the attractiveness of a project in the long term.

Equation (21) expresses the equalized cost of electricity (LCE). The equalized cost of electricity makes it easier to select the best system architecture from among the various possible hybrid system configurations based on the lowest energy cost, i.e. the lowest total investment cost in a possible renewable energy installation. LCE is expressed as;

$$LCE = \frac{TPV * CRI}{E_{hyb}} \quad (21)$$

In addition to the financial aspects, the economic analysis of a hybrid system should also take into account the potential environmental and social benefits. The use of renewable energy sources contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, which can lead to additional environmental bonuses.

A sensitivity analysis is performed to assess the project’s resilience to possible changes in external factors, such as fluctuations in equipment prices, energy carriers, and changes in electricity tariffs.

Modeling for Size Optimization

The main goal of size optimization is to minimize the probability of power loss (LPSP) and equalize the energy cost (LCE) of a hybrid photovoltaic and wind power system. Therefore, the two main objectives of the proposed function are:

- Improving the reliability of power supply (minimizing power consumption)
- Minimization of the cost of energy produced and directly the total current cost of PWH (minimization of LCE) [4].

Providing continuous power supply from a hybrid power system with photovoltaic wind batteries with losses of at least 10%, 7%, 5% and 3% during the year at SOC_{min} more than 20% is a limitation of size optimization [1]. The objective function to be minimized is expressed in equation (22) as follows:

$$\min(F) = \sum_{m=1}^{12} \sum_{d=1}^{HM} \sum_{h=1}^{24} (E_{hyb} * LCE_{m,d,h}) \quad (22)$$

where:

E_{hyb} — Energy generated by the hybrid system

LCE — Leveled Energy Cost

m, d, and h are the month number, day number, and hour, respectively.

Determining the most optimal design size and managing energy flows, which are: photovoltaic plant, wind turbine, and battery storage capacity, is the ultimate

goal of size optimization, but this optimization task faces limitations. Achieving the most optimal size prevents over sizing or under sizing the hybrid energy systems thereby minimizing economic or energy losses.

Conclusion

Finally, mathematical modeling of photovoltaic arrays is an important element of modern research in the field of solar energy. It contributes to an in-depth understanding of the processes that affect the efficiency of these systems, as well as opens up opportunities for innovation in the design, operation and management of photovoltaic installations. The use of efficient models can significantly increase the overall productivity of solar energy use, which, in turn, contributes to the transition to sustainable energy sources at the global level.

Thus, investments in renewable energy sources have a double advantage: they meet the growing demand for electricity in both urban and remote regions, while simultaneously contributing to the protection of natural resources and reducing the negative impact on the environment. The introduction and development of hybrid renewable energy systems forms the basis for a sustainable energy future that combines economic benefits with environmental responsibility. Technical and economic analysis is a necessary basis for further design of hybrid energy systems in the field of renewable energy.

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OPTIMISATION OF LOW-YIELD WELL CONTROL WITH SUBMERSIBLE ELECTRIC CENTRIFUGAL PUMPS IN PERIODIC OPERATION MODE

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Abstract: *Low-yield wells equipped with submersible electric centrifugal pump unit operate most efficiently in short-term periodic operation mode, but this requires the selection of parameters such as the duration of accumulation and pumping periods, as well as the operating power of the submersible electric motor. Adaptive control algorithms can solve this task of optimising energy consumption while meeting the planned flow rate target. One variant of such algorithms is considered in the article.*

Keywords: *low-yield well, submersible electric centrifugal pump, short-term periodic pumping, optimisation, energy consumption, flow rate*

Introduction

The current state of the oil industry in Russia and worldwide is marked by a steady trend towards an increase in the share of low-yield wells. Their exact number is difficult to determine due to the lack of a unified classification methodology and constantly changing data. The criteria for classifying wells as low-yield vary depending on the region, company and technological conditions. For example, in Russia, the range of low flow rates can be from 0.5 to 20 m³/day, and in some cases, wells with a flow rate of up to 5 m³/day are classified as low-yield under certain fluid lifting conditions [1].

Approximately 35–45% of all wells in Russia are low-yield wells. The following factors are among the reasons for the growth in the share of low-yield wells in Russia:

- depletion of old fields, especially in Western Siberia, where many fields are in the stage of declining production with water cut exceeding 90 %;
- decrease in reservoir pressure and deterioration of filtration and storage properties of the bottomhole zone of wells due to long-term operation;
- water cut of formations, formation of water cones and intensification of the capillary end effect;
- technological limitations, for example, when using submersible electric centrifugal pump units (SECPU), a decrease in flow leads to a sharp drop in efficiency, which makes operation less profitable;
- climatic and geological factors — unfavourable conditions, such as high oil viscosity and the presence of asphalt-resin-paraffin deposits, reduce well productivity;
- Economic factors: with high water cut and low oil prices, the operation of low-yield wells often becomes unprofitable, which can lead to their conservation or inactivity.

Global data on the number of low-yield wells is also lacking due to differences in national standards and accounting methodologies. However, the trend towards an increase in the share of low-yield wells is observed in many countries, especially in regions with long-term development fields.

The operation of low-yield wells is associated with high maintenance costs and risks of unprofitability. At the same time, with the decline in available oil reserves, there is growing interest in technologies to increase oil recovery and optimise the operation of such wells. Promising areas include automation and digitalisation of management processes, intensification of the bottomhole zone (hydraulic fracturing, acid treatment, etc.), and the use of specialised equipment for low-yield wells (special-purpose pumps, lightweight equipment).

In any case, the ‘resuscitation’ of low-yield wells is a more economically advantageous option than the development of new fields, so research related to the optimisation of production from such wells is relevant and in demand.

General characteristics of low-yield wells operation

To operate low-yield wells in Russian fields, they use Sucker rod pumping units (SRPU) or submersible electric centrifugal pump units (SECPU). SRPU is the most common method, but it has limitations on the depth to which submersible equipment can be lowered into the well (no more than 2000 m). SECPUs are adapted for lifting well production from deeper wells (up to 5000 m), but with a decrease in SECPU flow, the efficiency of the pumping unit is significantly reduced.

The operation of low-yield wells is associated with a number of complicating factors: paraffin, resin and asphaltene deposits, high water cut, the complexity of coordinating inflow and withdrawal regimes, the need for regular geological and

technical measures, optimisation of deep pumping equipment, as well as corrosion and oil preparation problems. Taken together, this leads to high operating costs for maintaining low-yield wells, and low yields make it critically important to improve the economic efficiency of their operation.

Various technological techniques can be used to increase the productivity of low-yield wells, such as the periodic 'accumulation-pumping' mode. In this case, fluid is removed from the well periodically rather than continuously, with the well being shut down during the rest of the time. Continuous fluid pumping is also implemented, ensuring that the productivity of the pumping unit matches the flow characteristics of the well.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this paper is to analyse the features of short-term periodic operation (STPO) of low-yield wells equipped with electric submersible pumps from the point of view of developing control algorithms that optimise this mode.

Results and their discussion

Analysis of the features of SPOP and known areas of optimisation

Periodic well operation is a method in which periods of fluid pumping alternate with periods of fluid accumulation at the bottom of the well. This mode is particularly relevant for low-yield wells, where continuous operation may be ineffective or impractical. It is applicable to both types of mechanised production, i. e. both wells with SRPU and wells with SECPU. Further analysis will be carried out for wells with SECPU.

In this case, short-term periodic operation of a well has both advantages and disadvantages in terms of interaction with SECPU operation [2].

The main advantage is energy savings. SECPUs used for periodic operation usually have a higher efficiency compared to medium-capacity units. In addition, short-term operation reduces overall energy consumption. Furthermore, it allows for rapid changes in fluid extraction, as periodic operation allows for flexible adjustment of productivity without replacing equipment, which is especially important when well parameters change. Due to the fact that short-term operation reduces the vibration level of the SECPU, the heating of the cable and the submersible electric motor (SEM) is reduced, and the service life of the equipment is significantly extended: under conditions of increased mechanical impurity removal, the inter-repair period (IRP) can increase by 1.5–2 times. The increase in the IRP is proportional to the ratio of the total operating period (pumping plus accumulation) to the actual operating time of the SECPU.

There is also a reduction in the influence of complicating factors, as the intensity of salt and asphalt-resin-paraffin (ARP) deposits is reduced due to the

higher fluid flow rate during pumping, which breaks off deposits from the internal surfaces of the equipment. Mechanical impurities in the fluid at high flow rates even 'polish' the surfaces, preventing new deposits from forming.

Another advantage is the increased efficiency of reagent use. During periodic operation, the fluid is pumped out mainly from the annular space, which improves the delivery of salt deposit, ARP and corrosion inhibitors to the necessary equipment components.

Periodic operation also has its drawbacks, and they are quite significant.

First and foremost, this reduces the service life of the SECPU components. Studies have shown [3] that the average failure-free operating time of hydraulic seals in intermittent mode is approximately three times lower than in continuous mode. Each time the electric motor is started, increased starting currents and peak power loads on the shaft and pump bearings occur, which accelerates the destruction of the winding insulation, the crushing of the keys and keyways of the impellers, and the accumulation of residual deformations of the shafts and bearings. Periodic start-up and shutdown cycles lead to wear of the shaft face seals, and vibration during transient modes (start-up and shutdown) can increase oil leakage through the face seals by 5–10 times. This can lead to formation fluid entering the oil system and failure of the hydraulic protection and electric submersible pump. During a long period of fluid accumulation and subsequent pumping out of the accumulated volume, the cooling efficiency of the electric submersible pump decreases due to the low flow rate.

Complications may also arise during operation. Mechanical impurities may settle in the column each time it is shut down, gas pockets may form, gas breakthroughs may occur when the withdrawal rate increases, and solid salt deposits may form on the surface of the unit and the production column.

It is often difficult to determine the water content of the product due to the wide range of values when measuring it, since the SECPU usually brings water to the surface at the beginning of the pumping cycle, and then a water-oil emulsion with a variable composition.

Thus, periodic operation of the SECPU has significant economic advantages, but requires careful control and consideration of technical risks. The effectiveness of the method depends on the specific conditions of the well and the quality of the equipment used.

The use of STPO allows optimising the operation of the SECPU according to various criteria [4–8]. Thus, in [4], it is shown that periodic operation of low-yield water-flooded wells has a number of features caused by gravitational segregation of fluids in the wellbore, which allows alternating periods of pumping and accumulation of production to reduce water cut and prevent the formation of stable water-oil emulsions. In [5], an algorithm was developed that allows, based

on incoming data from monitoring well operating parameters, to determine online the current degree of degradation of the energy and flow-pressure characteristics of the pump due to mechanical wear based on the measured electrical parameters of the submersible electric motor (SEM), using the passport characteristics of the SECPU as a reference. Study [6] also addresses issues related to diagnosing the operation of the SECPU and identifying its malfunctions, in particular, the leakage of the check valve. Works [7, 8] also consider the algorithm for monitoring the condition of the SECPU and its measuring channels.

All of the studies considered have in common that the object of optimisation is a single well, whereas it is not sufficient to optimise the operation of each well with a ECP at a cluster site separately. Taking into account their mutual influence through the formation (interference) is critically important, especially in periodic mode.

This is explained by the following reasons. If the formation is common, then when one well is stopped or started, the pressure differences around it change. This pressure is transmitted through the formation and affects the bottomhole pressures of neighbouring wells.

In periodic mode, wells rarely operate synchronously. When one well is stopped, the formation pressure around it recovers slightly. Starting up a neighbouring well can 'take away' this energy, preventing the first well from recovering. If two wells operate simultaneously, their depression funnels overlap, which can lead to lower than expected flow rates for each well if the modes are not coordinated.

In addition, starting an ECP is the most energy-intensive moment. If wells are started randomly, peak loads on the power grid are added up, but useful fluid extraction is not.

Thus, optimisation must be carried out for the entire well cluster.

Proposed algorithm for optimising the operation of a well cluster in STPO mode

The main goal is to minimise the total energy consumption of the cluster while ensuring the total planned flow rate of the cluster (rather than each well at each moment in time).

Additional technical restrictions:

- minimum permissible operating and shutdown times (to protect equipment);
- limit values for dynamic level or bottomhole pressure (to prevent gas breakthroughs and landslides);
- ECP motor temperature;
- accounting for peak electricity rates.

The algorithm is implemented in three stages (fig. 1). At the first stage, based on historical data and data obtained at the moments of change in the condition of the wells, a map of the mutual influence of wells for the cluster is compiled. Then, in the second stage, the monitoring system for the condition of each well and its SECPU is checked and, if necessary, adjusted. In essence, these stages

are preparatory for the third stage — the development of a management strategy, during which several key decisions must be made (fig. 2).

First, on the synchronisation or asynchronisation of well operating cycles, i.e. it is necessary to determine what is more profitable for a given cluster: to start the wells one after the other in order to minimise interference and reduce the peak load on the network (this solution is likely to be optimal), or it may be beneficial to operate simultaneously, but at a lower frequency, to give the formation more time to recover (for example, when the formation has very high permeability).

Secondly, it is necessary to optimise the parameters of each cycle for each well. Based on its individual characteristics, it is necessary to select the optimal values for the duration of operation (t_{pumping}) and downtime ($t_{\text{accumulation}}$). The pumping time is determined by the moment after which there is a sharp increase in specific energy consumption per tonne of fluid extracted. The downtime must be sufficient for a significant pressure recovery. It is also necessary to determine the frequency of the power supply (f_{power}) of SECPU: it may be worth operating not at the maximum frequency, but at the optimal frequency, which provides the required flow rate with the best overall efficiency.

Figure 1. Stages of developing an optimisation algorithm

Control strategy		
Optimisation of the well launch sequence in a well cluster	Optimise the parameters of each cycle for each well (selection t_{pumping} , $t_{\text{accumulation}}$, f_{power})	Optimise the number of simultaneously operating wells in a cluster

Figure 2. Control strategy tasks

Thirdly, it is necessary to determine the minimum number of active wells in the cluster required to achieve the specified planned daily flow rate for the cluster, since, from the point of view of minimising energy consumption and saving the SECPU resource, it may not be necessary for all wells to operate simultaneously.

The implementation of such an algorithm is a classic optimal control problem with several variables and constraints and can be solved using mathematical programming methods (non-linear optimisation, branch and bound method), genetic algorithms or solvers built into modern production management software packages (e.g. based on ROXAR, OLGA, or domestic equivalents such as Nedra Production, Nedra.FDP, etc.).

The minimum mathematical model for optimisation should include (fig. 3):

- an inflow equation for each well, taking into account pressure changes from the operation of neighbouring wells;
- curves of ECP operation (pressure-flow rate, power-flow rate) for recalculating energy consumption;
- the objective function $\sum_{i=1}^n (P_{cons.i} * dt) \rightarrow min$, $P_{cons.i}$ where is the power consumed by the i-th well in the cluster;
- the main limitation $\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{day.i} * dt) \rightarrow planned$ where $Q_{day.i}$ is the daily flow rate of the i-th well in the cluster.

Figure 3. Components of the mathematical model of the optimisation algorithm

Conclusion

The analysis showed that the number of low-yield wells both in the Russian Federation and abroad is steadily increasing. The most appropriate mode of

operation for such wells is short-term periodic operation. Its efficiency, according to one of the main indicators — specific energy consumption per tonne of fluid produced — depends on the correctly selected pumping time and oil accumulation time in the well, as well as on the operating frequency of the SECPU power supply. The optimisation of such wells should not be carried out for each of them individually, but for the cluster as a whole. Thus, optimising the operation of a cluster of wells with SECPU in periodic mode is a task of coordination, not individual adjustment. The solution lies in collecting big data, building a digital twin of the cluster (even if simplified) and applying optimisation methods.

The proposed approach can be implemented by introducing an additional group adaptive control subsystem into the cluster's automated process control system. Such subsystems (for example, based on the cluster PLC) can make real-time decisions about starting and stopping specific wells according to a given algorithm, taking into account the current readings from all wells in the cluster.

The economic effect of such work (reduction in specific energy consumption per tonne, fulfilment of the plan with fewer starts) can be very significant.

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DECISION-MAKING ALGORITHM IN A COGNITIVE DYNAMIC DIAGNOSTIC AND STABILIZATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Technologies for decision-making algorithm development in a cognitive dynamic system for diagnosis and stabilization are presented, aimed at diagnosing cognitive functions, correction, non-pharmaceutical self-regulation, and rehabilitation in real time (24/7). The system simulates the structure and computational mechanisms of the cognitive capabilities of the biological brain at multiple levels, including multicomponent neural architectures, various types of synaptic connections, as well as biochemical processes, depression, and distress. The objective of this study has been achieved — assessing the effectiveness of the compliance with the declared requirements in the software specification for the project titled ‘Development of theoretical foundations and computer intelligent technologies for diagnosing and non-pharmaceutical self-regulation of psychoemotional states of personality.’*

Keywords: *decision-making algorithm, dynamic system, cognitive monitoring, non-pharmaceutical self-regulation*

A unique non-pharmaceutical multimodal specialized system has been developed and is currently undergoing experimental testing, aimed at diagnosing cognitive functions, correction, non-pharmaceutical self-regulation, and rehabilitation in real time (24/7). This system simulates the structure and computational mechanisms of the cognitive capabilities of the biological brain at multiple levels, including multicomponent neural architectures, various types of synaptic connections, as well as biochemical processes, depression, and

distress. All of this is based on fundamental neurobiological, psychophysiological diagnostic, and cognitive research.

The developed program analyzes the results of various psychological tests for stress and anxiety, automatically interpreting the result status as: “Within normal range” (green); “Attention! Art therapy is recommended” (yellow); “Exceeds normal range” (red); visualizes interactive graphs with color coding, generates graphical speedometers for clear visualization of results, scales with ranges (normal, attention, deviation), and exports data: saving to professionally formatted Excel files; Color coding of lines according to status.

Supported tests: Spielberger Anxiety Scale (state and trait anxiety); Stress condition diagnostics (Prokhorov); Psychological Stress Measure PSM-25; Brief Resilience Scale (BRS).

Functionality of the Resilience Questionnaire (OPUS): automatic status determination; Generation of recommendations based on results; Saving graphs in PNG format; Support for two-parameter tests (such as Spielberger’s); Integration with the matplotlib, pandas, and openpyxl libraries. User interface: console menu in Russian; step-by-step data entry; informational prompts and test descriptions; automatic creation of a ‘charts’ folder for saving results; timestamps for all saved files; automatic formatting of Excel files.

The problem-solving algorithm and the outcome of implementing the psychological test interpreter include a preparatory phase (data collection and analysis of functional requirements); examination of the source website. Two accounts were created on the portal <http://psydiag.guide.ru/>: account No. 1 with results corresponding to the norm; account No. 2 with intentionally distorted responses demonstrating deviations. Key tests related to stress and anxiety were analyzed: the Spielberger Anxiety Scale (state and trait anxiety); stress condition diagnostics (Prokhorova methodology); Brief Resilience Scale (BRS); Psychological Stress Measure PSM-25; Resilience Questionnaire (OPUS).

The criteria for interpretation have been defined. For each test, the following have been established: value ranges (low/medium/high level); threshold values for classification; logic for determining the ‘norm’ (for some tests, high values correspond to the norm, while for others, they indicate deviation).

Architectural system design. Selection of the technology stack (programming language: Python 3.8+; visualization libraries: Matplotlib for creating complex graphs; data processing: NumPy for mathematical operations; export to Excel: Pandas and OpenPyXL for generating structured reports; styling: use of Matplotlib built-in styles (ggplot) to achieve a professional appearance of graphs).

Application class structure. SInterpreter (main class): management of all tests and their configurations; processing user input; coordination of the visualizer and

exporter; Visualizer (visualization class): generation of complex graphical reports; creation of speedometers and scales; management of color schemes and styles; ExcelExporter (export class): generation of structured Excel reports; application of conditional formatting; calculation of statistical metrics.

Implementation of interpretation logic. Test Processing Mechanism:

Pseudocode of the Interpretation Algorithm

INPUT: test_id, score1, score2 (optional)

IF test_id does not exist:

RETURN error "Test not found"

IF the test requires two values AND score2 is missing:

RETURN error "Two values required"

IF values exceed allowable limits:

RETURN error "Values out of range"

CALCULATE completion percentage

DETERMINE current range (low/medium/high)

SET status based on test type and range.

CREATE visualization.

SAVE result for export.

RETURN dictionary with results.

Logic for status determination.

For the Spielberger test: low level = normal.

For the Prokhorova test: high regulation = normal.

For KShSU and OPUS: high level = normal.

For PSM-25: low stress = normal.

Implementation of the visualization system. Creation of the composite graphical interface. Each graph consists of three main components: the top panel (informational): the test name; text status with color coding; description of the methodology; central panel (speedometer): a semicircular scale with gradient fill; a moving needle indicating the percentage of completion; a digital value at the center of the speedometer; scale markings at 25% intervals; bottom panel (linear scale): a horizontal scale with colored ranges; a vertical marker indicating the current result; range labels; Numerical value of the result.

Color Psychology:

Green (#4CAF50): normal, safety, calmness

Yellow (#FFC107): attention, warning

Red (#F44336): danger, deviation

Blue (#2196F3): primary interface color, neutrality

Implementation of the export system. Creation of the Excel report. Sheet "Results": a table containing all completed tests; automatic formatting based on status; adjustable column widths; filters for convenient navigation.

Sheet “Statistics”: total number of tests; distribution by status; average completion percentage; report generation date. Conditional formatting.

```
# Color coding logic in Excel
IF status = “MEETS THE STANDARD”:
background_color = light green
ELSE IF status = “REQUIRES ATTENTION”:
background_color = light yellow
ELSE:
background_color = light red
User interface. Console menu.
```

MAIN MENU: test analysis; information about tests; Export all results to Excel; exit. Test analysis process (selecting a test from the list; entering scores with validation; automatic generation of graphs; output of textual interpretation; saving results for subsequent export).

Outcome of the implemented functional capabilities. Comprehensive interpretation of psychological tests (support for various methodologies; automatic status determination based on entered data; context-dependent logic for each test type; generation of personalized recommendations). Professional visualization (interactive, high-resolution graphs at 300 DPI; adaptive design for varying data sizes; color-coded status differentiation; saving graphs with timestamps). Comprehensive reporting system (unified repository of all results; professionally formatted Excel files; automated statistical processing; ability to track the dynamics of changes).

Technical Specifications. Modularity and Extensibility (clear separation of responsibilities between classes; ease of adding new tests; flexible configuration system; component independence). Error Handling and Validation (verification of input data correctness; protection against out-of-range values; generation of clear error messages; proper handling of exceptional situations). Data Management (structured storage of results; automatic folder creation for saving; unique file names to prevent overwriting; support for PNG and XLSX formats).

Practical value.

For psychologists and specialists: rapid interpretation of test results; visual data presentation for clients; professional documentation; capability to monitor therapy progress. For researchers: standardization of the interpretation process; automation of routine tasks; structured data storage; specific recommendations; capability for self-monitoring.

System demonstration.

Usage scenario: ‘healthy individual.’ The user inputs the results of the Spielberg test: state anxiety — 25, trait anxiety — 28. The system determines the average score: 26.5; calculates the percentage: 33.1 %, sets the range as “Low

level,” assigns the status “Within normal limits,” and creates a gauge chart at 33%; issues the recommendation: “Keep it up!”

Use case scenario: “Deviation from regulatory standards.” The user inputs PSM-25 results: total score: 180. The system calculates the percentage: 90%; sets the range as “High stress.” assigns the status: “Exceeds the norm” and generates a chart with a red zone; issues the recommendation: “Consultation with a specialist recommended, comprehensive art therapy” (Figs. 1, 2). The program code fragment of the experimental studies is presented in Fig. 3.

Unique implementation features: adaptive charts (automatic scaling for different value ranges; intelligent element placement; preservation of readability across various values); intelligent recommendation system (context-dependent advice; gradation of recommendations ranging from prevention to referral to a specialist; consideration of the specifics of each test); comprehensive data approach (a unified database of all results; capability for comparative analysis; support for patient history).

Thus, an algorithm for decision-making in an intelligent dynamic system for diagnostics and stabilization has been developed, implemented, and validated, aimed at diagnosing cognitive functions, correction, non-pharmaceutical self-regulation, and rehabilitation in real time (<http://psydiag.guide.ru>). Advantages of the system: automation of the interpretation of cognitive monitoring and psychological test results; professional visualization at each stage of diagnosis and self-regulation; complex graphical representations implemented, combining aesthetics and informativeness; structured export (a report generation system in Excel format with automatic formatting has been developed); user interface: an intuitive console application with step-by-step guidance has been created.

The research was conducted using federal budget funding from the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation. (project No.FREN-2024-0003)

Program results:

Test	Results	Min. ST	Max. ST	Range	Status	Results description	Analysis date
Spielberger Anxiety Scale	ST: 40.0, LT: 40.0	40	50.0%	Moderate level	WARNING! RECOMMENDED RE-TREAT!	Yes	2020-01-05 10:59:20

Figure 1 — Results from fragment 1 of the program

```

=====
MAIN MENU:
=====
1. Analyze Test
2. Test Information
3. Export All Results to Excel
4. Exit

Your Choice: 1

=====
SELECT A TEST FOR ANALYSIS:
=====
1. Spielberger Anxiety Scale
2. Stress Condition Diagnostics (Prokhorov)
3. Brief Stress Resistance Scale (BSRS)
4. Psychological Stress Scale PSM-25
5. Stress Resistance Questionnaire (OPUS)
B. Back to Main Menu

Your Choice: 1

=====
ANALYSIS: Spielberger Anxiety Scale
=====

This test consists of two scales:
ST - State Anxiety (reaction to a situation)
LT - Trait Anxiety (stable characteristic)

Enter the score for STATE anxiety (20-80): 25
Enter the score for trait anxiety (20-80): 25

Generating chart...

=====
ANALYSIS RESULT
=====
Test: Spielberger Anxiety Scale
Your score: ST: 25.0, LT: 25.0
Completion percentage: 31.2%
Range: Low level
Status: WITHIN NORMAL RANGE
Recommendation: Keep up the good work! Your condition is normal.

Chart saved: charts/Spielberger_Anxiety_Scale_20260110_214358.png
Result added to the master Excel list (total: 1)
=====

Analyze another test? (yes/no): no
Export all results to Excel before exiting? (yes/no): yes
Results exported to Excel: charts/test_results_20260110_214409.xlsx

Goodbye!
    
```

Figure 2 — Results from fragment 2 of the program

```
status = "ATTENTION! ART THERAPY RECOMMENDED" status_color
= "#FFC107" else: # "High
level"
status = "OUT OF RANGE"
status_color = "#F44336"

elif test_name == "Stress State Diagnostics (Prokhorov)":
# For the Prokhorova test: High regulation norm
if clean_current_range == "High regulation" :
status = "COOTBETCTBYET HOPME"
status_color = "#4CAF50"

elif clean_current_range == "Moderate regulation" :
status = "ATTENTION! ART THERAPY RECOMMENDED"
status_color = "#FFC107"

else: status = "Low regulation"
status = "OUT OF RANGE"
status_color = "#F44336"

elif test_name in ["Brief Resilience Scale (BRS)", "Resilience Ques-
tionnaire (RQ)"] :
# For BRS and RQ: High level norm =
if clean_current_range == "High level" :
status = "CONFORMS TO THE STANDARD" status_
color = "#4CAF50" elif clean_current_range == "
Medium level":
status = "ATTENTION! ART THERAPY RECOMMENDED"
status_color = "#FFC107"
else: # "Low level"
status = "OUT OF RANGE"
status_color = "#F44336"

elif test_name == "Psychological Stress Scale PSM-25":
# For PSM-25: Low stress is normal
if clean_current_range == "Low stress":
status = "COOTBETCTBYET HOPME"
status_color = "#4CAF50"

elif clean_current_range == "Medium stress":
status = "ATTENTION! ART THERAPY RECOMMENDED"
status_color = "#FFC107"
else: # "High stress"
```

Fig. 3 — Program code (fragment) from experimental research

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THE CONCEPTUAL ESSENCE OF THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PARADIGM

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Abstract. *The author substantiates the fundamental patterns of sustainable development policies in the agro-industrial complex, the essence of which is disclosed through the attributes of the bio-socio-economic system 'nature — society — production' and objectively requires a fundamentally new resource- and nature-saving socio-ecological-economic policy. It has been proposed to consider this policy at all levels of government administration from the standpoint of its capacity to ensure the directions, methods, means, and effective mechanisms for reconciling the equivalence of environmental preservation and sustainable economic development.*

Keywords: *sustainable development, paradigm components, imperatives, state, sectors, regions, economy, society, environment, natural resource potential.*

The implementation of the principles equating sustainable development and social justice in the national strategies of leading countries globally 'enables businesses and governments to sustain stability without any fundamental alterations to their current trajectory,' and numerous regulatory documents from economically developed countries are based on the premise that development is linked to growth; hence, economic growth is considered part of the solution to the sustainable development issue [1, p. 35].

The interpretation of sustainable development reveals the conceptual essence of its primary objective within a unified vector approach and consists of the balanced provision of dynamic parameters of economic, social, and ecological imperatives at the global, macro-, and micro-levels. These are directed towards economic and scientific-technical progress, stimulation of productive labor, fulfillment of society's needs, and the sustainable equilibrium of the ecosystem for harmonious, inclusive growth in the present and future, contingent upon the preservation and phased renovation of environmental integrity [2, 3] (fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Components of the sustainable development paradigm

In our view, when selecting national approaches to a state’s sustainable development strategy, attention should be paid to global positive factors and their influence on the development of the internal system.

At the same time, it is essential to consider the methodology for the comprehensive formation of sustainable development in regions and sectors, as well as the establishment of factors and criteria for their development. A crucial aspect is the activation of efforts to ensure integration and coherence within national and sectoral policies, the implementation of adaptive measures by institutions, and the facilitation of effective partnerships involving multiple stakeholders to secure unity and coordination of actions among governments, international organizations, and civil society. It is advisable to consider conceptual approaches to the formation of a system of financial mechanisms ensuring resource and environmental security and sustainable development not only at the national level but also at the regional and sectoral levels.

Each level of the management system is characterized by a corresponding range of subjective interests. State interests are oriented towards achieving goals defined by the country’s domestic and international policies. Regional sustainable

development is considered in light of the established natural, economic, and social characteristics. The priority objective at the sectoral and corporate levels is the economic component of sustainable development (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 – System of Reciprocal Elements Forming Sustainable Development Policy

If environmental indicators account for all types of natural resource expenditures and the negative impacts of pollution on nature, as well as the extent of damage inflicted on nature, the economy, and society at all stages of production and consumption, in addition to all categories of environmental costs, then the economy and ecology will not exist in antagonistic relations.

In order to establish and ensure the foundational base for qualitatively new socio-economic and ecologically sustainable development, it is necessary to create financial, material-technical, intellectual, and normative-legal support for sustainable development, as well as for preserving favorable ecosystem conditions and an optimal natural resource base.

The current economic situation in the Russian Federation, together with the accumulated experience, determines the prerequisites for establishing the methodological foundations for forming the strategy and sustainable development policies of the country and its regions. To date, a number of steps have been taken towards sustainable development. During this period, despite the unconventional political and economic situation, the status of environmental protection authorities has significantly increased; broad access to environmental information has been established, and non-governmental environmental organizations and movements have formed and actively participated in the processes of social development. Overall, environmental issues have elicited broad public resonance, including at the international level.

At the state level, a series of laws have been enacted on environmental protection, public health safeguarding, and the regulation of resource use to improve the efficiency of the state governance system in environmental management and ensuring resource-ecological security; elements of the mechanism for environmental protection and rational natural resource use are currently in effect. An independent financing system for environmental protection activities has been established as a hierarchical structure of ecological funds. There are also several other positive developments in organizing the interaction between society, economic development, and the requirements of environmental protection legislation.

At the same time, it is entirely evident that modern society will not resolve the problems of sustainable development without altering its behavioral norms, worldview, and comprehension of the essence of these issues.

In our view, this situation is primarily attributable to the incapacity of the global market system, as a mechanism of economic relations, to respond adequately to environmental changes, as well as to the inertia of states in addressing these deficiencies of the market economy during the implementation of not only environmental but also socio-economic policies.

The specificity of the contemporary development situation in the Russian Federation also lies in the necessity of addressing complex issues on the path to

forming a sustainable development economy, including overcoming the turbulent state caused by sanctions, adverse external factors, strict constraints, and other challenges, while simultaneously shaping the trajectory of social development in alignment with global trends and international coexistence norms.

Therefore, overcoming this state necessitates a fundamental paradigm shift in established organizational and economic relations, alongside the formulation of a national strategic plan to establish conditions for transadaptation toward sustainable, ecologically oriented economic development, aimed at achieving the most significant political, economic, and social priorities in state-building and strengthening sovereignty, based on the harmonious utilization and functioning of natural resource potential.

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BUILDING A GREEN CORRIDOR: CHINA-TÜRKIYE PARTNERSHIP IN RENEWABLE ENERGY

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the development of Sino-Turkish cooperation in renewable energy (RE) against the background of contemporary energy and climate challenges. It examines prerequisites for this cooperation, including Türkiye's high dependence on energy imports, China's global dominance in solar and wind energy equipment manufacturing, and the existing bilateral treaty framework. Through an analysis of specific projects and investment data, the study identifies the key forms of Chinese participation: direct equipment supply, Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) contracts, the establishment of joint ventures with local production, as well as financing schemes involving Chinese policy banks and insurers (the EPC+F model). The conclusion highlights the positive impact of Sino-Turkish renewable energy cooperation, the growing diversification of the Turkish energy mix while simultaneously expanding China's export markets.*

Keywords: *China, Türkiye, Sino-Turkish energy cooperation, renewable energy, Belt and Road Initiative, Foreign Direct Investment, localization.*

Türkiye remains highly dependent on hydrocarbon imports — according to various estimates, about three quarters of the country's final energy consumption is generated by fuel imports [1; 2, p. 453]. The import dependence makes reducing energy vulnerability a priority for Ankara through the local deployment of low-cost renewable sources (solar and wind generation). As a result, Türkiye's energy policy focuses on a large-scale increase in renewable energy sources as a means of improving the balance of payments and increasing energy security.

Alongside the government's formally pragmatic course, European environmental and climate regulation (including indirect mechanisms such as CBAM), and the general dynamics of decarbonization of markets encourage Türkiye to consider the climatic requirements of partners and buyers, especially in export-oriented sectors [3, pp. 2–3]. This, in turn, creates an additional incentive

to grow renewable energy capacity and green the energy mix, driven by trade, political, and investment considerations.

Over the past decade, the cost of electricity from solar panels and wind has plummeted, making renewable energy economically competitive even in countries with cheap fossil fuels¹. For Türkiye, this means the opportunity to increase generating capacity quickly and at relatively low cost without long cycles of extraction and transportation of fuel. In addition, the modular nature of solar and wind installations simplifies the design, financing and localization of production.

China controls the vast majority of the global solar panel supply chain. According to estimates by the IEA, China's share of the total production stages exceeds 70–80% across a number of chain links, which provides Chinese manufacturers with a price advantage and access to massive volumes of modules and components [4, pp. 21–24]². For Türkiye, this means low-cost access to panels and the ability to quickly deploy large fleets. Chinese wind turbine manufacturers have substantially increased their global market shares, with several Chinese OEM companies among the largest suppliers in terms of installations³. This affords China a competitive advantage in both land-based and (future) offshore projects, as well as in the integration of local services and project warranty support.

China's production capacity for lithium-ion batteries and storage components far exceeds that of most countries: global capacity, expansion plans, and investments in battery factories ensure China's status as the world's "storage factory."⁴ This is crucial for the integration of renewable energy sources (grid balancing, peak load management, and energy storage in kWh terms), especially in grids with a high proportion of intermittent generation.

Major Chinese public and private contractors have experience in "turnkey" contracts — spanning design, equipment supply, and construction, often in conjunction with Chinese export banks and financing mechanisms (EPC plus

¹ Solar PV // International Energy Agency (IEA). URL: <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/renewables/solar-pv> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

² Solar PV Global Supply Chains: Executive Summary // International Energy Agency (IEA). URL: <https://www.iea.org/reports/solar-pv-global-supply-chains/executive-summary> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

³ Chinese Manufacturers Lead Global Wind Turbine Installations, BloombergNEF Report Shows // BloombergNEF. URL: <https://about.bnef.com/insights/clean-energy/chinese-manufacturers-lead-global-wind-turbine-installations-bloombergnef-report-shows/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

⁴ Global EV Outlook 2023: Trends in batteries // International Energy Agency (IEA). URL: <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-ev-outlook-2023/trends-in-batteries> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

loans) [5, p. 49]. This model reduces transaction barriers for recipient countries and enables faster implementation of large projects with reduced risk for local developers. The result is an accelerated spread of Chinese technologies and capital in renewable energy projects abroad [6, p. 5].

In 2009, China and Türkiye signed the Memorandum of Understanding on Cooperation in the Energy Sector (effective from 2014), which provides for cooperation in various energy sectors, including renewable energy (Article 3 of the Memorandum) [7, p. 215]. The document establishes a framework for energy cooperation between the two countries, but does not provide for specific “green” projects.

The total volume of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the Turkish energy sector from China in 2007–2024 amounted to just over \$ 11 billion (Fig. 1)¹. Most of this amount comes from companies that specialize in the production of energy equipment for thermal, nuclear, wind and hydroelectric power plants (哈电集团, Harbin Electric Corporation; 东方电气, Dongfang Electric Corporation), and China’s largest design and construction company, Power Construction Corporation of China (中国电力建设集团). However, Türkiye is not the main recipient of FDI in the energy sector from China, unlike Brazil (\$ 60 billion), Pakistan (\$ 50 billion), Canada (\$ 41.8 billion), Australia (\$ 40 billion), and Saudi Arabia (\$ 39 billion)².

Figure 1. Chinese FDI in Türkiye energy sector (in billion USD), 2007–2024. Note: Gaps indicate years with no recorded investment. Source: China Global Investment Tracker.

¹ China Global Investment Tracker // American Enterprise Institute (AEI). URL: <https://www.aei.org/china-global-investment-tracker/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

² *Ibid.*

The Belt and Road Initiative (“一帶一路”, BRI) was initially focused on transport and infrastructure projects, but in recent years China has reoriented its foreign economic policy toward green technologies and investments in low-carbon sectors as part of its BRI engagement. For Türkiye, this means that Chinese investments and contractors are increasingly offering “turnkey” models and financing that are equally suitable for renewable generation projects (solar and wind farms, energy storage facilities), although Türkiye’s share of total Chinese investment remains relatively small [8, pp. 807–808].

Geographically and institutionally, Türkiye is a key link in the Middle Corridor / Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, which connects China with Europe through Central Asia and the South Caucasus¹. The development of this corridor enhances Türkiye’s significance as a transit hub and streamlines the logistics for large-scale shipments (including energy technologies and components for renewable energy). Strengthening ties along the “middle corridor” makes Türkiye a convenient platform both for hosting industrial plants (localization of modules, components) and for implementing large-scale generation and energy storage projects with Chinese participation. The Middle Corridor is actively developing and is considered by both China and Türkiye as an alternative to the northern and sea routes, thereby boosting Ankara’s attractiveness as a logistics hub for the supply of renewable energy equipment.

A key factor that has enhanced Türkiye’s attractiveness to foreign investors in the field of “green” energy is the High-Tech Investment Incentive Program (HIT-30), launched in July 2024. This initiative seeks to stimulate investments totaling up to \$30 billion in strategically high-tech industries, including electric vehicles, battery systems, semiconductors and renewable energy [9, pp. 4–5]. The program particularly emphasizes the localization of the production of solar cells and components for wind power, which creates a favorable institutional environment for Chinese companies to participate in the development of Turkish renewable energy and Türkiye’s integration into trans-regional value chains.

Despite the absence of a standalone bilateral agreement on renewable energy cooperation, practical “green” energy cooperation between China and Türkiye continues to grow. This cooperation manifests in a set of specific investment and contract projects covering solar and wind energy, as well as localization of production facilities (Table 1).

Table 1. Joint Turkish-Chinese green energy projects. Source: Compiled by the author.

¹ Türkiye’s Connectivity and Multilateral Transportation Policy // Republic of Türkiye: Ministry of Foreign Affairs. URL: https://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkiye_s-multilateral-transportation-policy.en.mfa (accessed: 03.01.2026).

Project	Capacity	Chinese partners	Turkish partners	Form of participation	Financing / Support	Status
Turbine supplies & blade localization (İzmir) ¹	Supply contracts: ~143 MW, 43.2 MW	Goldwind (金風科技)	Dere Construction (Dere İnşaat) & other local developers	Equipment supply contracts; planned JV for blade manufacturing	Commercial contracts; potential EPC	Contracts executed; JV in planning stage
Proposed wind turbine manufacturing plant ²	~2 GW (proposed)	Dongfang Electric (东方电气)	Under negotiation with govt. & mfrs.	Planned JV / local manufacturing (negotiations ongoing)	Likely combo of commercial & policy support	Under negotiation
N-type cell factory ³	~5 GW	JTPV (捷泰新能源科技有限公司), Drinda (海南钧达新能源科技股份有限公司)	Schmid Pekintaş	JV / greenfield factory (cell & module production)	Financing announced (details pending)	Announced (June 2025); early planning
Kalyon (PV project) ⁴	~500 MW	China Electronics Technology Group Corporation (中国电科)	Kalyon Group (developer)	Equipment supply & EPC	Commercial financing	In development

¹ China-based Goldwind to build wind turbine blade factory in Turkey // Balkan Green Energy News. URL: <https://balkangreenenergynews.com/china-based-goldwind-to-build-wind-turbine-blade-factory-in-turkey/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

² Turkey discusses 2-GW wind turbine factory with China’s Dongfang // Renewables Now. URL: <https://renewablesnow.com/news/turkey-discusses-2-gw-wind-turbine-factory-with-chinas-dongfang-1282518/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

³ Chinese, Turkish firms to build 5 GW solar cell factory in Türkiye // Daily Sabah. URL: <https://www.dailysabah.com/business/energy/chinese-turkish-firms-to-build-5-gw-solar-cell-factory-in-turkiye> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

⁴ “一带一路”中土光伏太阳能项目合作获重大进展，中国新能源汽车准入门槛放宽 [Significant progress has been made in the cooperation of Sino-Turkish photovoltaic solar energy projects under the Belt and Road Initiative, and the entry threshold for China’s new energy vehicles has been lowered] // CEEP-BIT. URL: <https://ceep.bit.edu.cn/xwdt/mznyxw/9f77eb8ec3d648ed87a719f91f7b9535.htm> (accessed: 03.01.2026). In Chinese.

Project	Capacity	Chinese partners	Turkish partners	Form of participation	Financing / Support	Status
Isparta (PV project) ¹	~4.71 MW	Jiangsu Sumec Energy (江苏苏美达能源), and its subsidiary Phillun Solar	Local developers / operators; Sybac solar International (Germany)	JV (Global solar Co. Ltd.)	Commercial / local financing	Operational (grid-connected)
Ugurlular Tekstil Sazak ²	55 MW	Zhejiang Orient Engineering Co. (浙江国贸集团东方机电工程股份有限公司)	Ecogreen Co.	JV / green-field factory	Sinosure (中国信保) & DZ Bank (Germany)	Operational (grid-connected)
TOPCon solar cell factory ³	> 850 MW	CHINT Group (正泰电气), and its subsidiary Astronergy	N/A	JV (Astronergy Solar Turkey Enerji A.Ş.)	~\$500 million (estimated)	Announcement, planning stage
PV project ⁴	~395MW	CEEG (中国能建集团)	LIMAK Group; IC-TAS Group; Türkiye Diler Group	EPC contract	N/A	Contract signed; MOUs under negotiation
Rixos Hotel PV project ⁵	74 MW	CSCEC (中国建筑集团)	N/A	EPC contract	Commercial financing	Under construction

¹ 苏美达深挖“一带一路”合作潜力 土耳其4.71MW光伏电站竣工并网 [Sumec digs deep into the potential of “One Belt, One Road” cooperation. Türkiye’s 4.71MW photovoltaic power station was completed and connected to the grid] // Phono. URL: https://cn.phonosolar.com/?news_47%2F144.html (accessed: 03.01.2026). In Chinese.

² 中国信保承保首个土耳其光伏电站出口买方信贷保险项目 [Sinosure is a sponsor of the first Turkish project on credit insurance for export buyers of photovoltaic power plants] // AFCA-Asia. URL: <https://cn.afca-asia.org/Portal.do?contentID=3773&method=detail-View&returnChannelID=23> (accessed: 03.01.2026). In Chinese.

³ Astronergy to build \$500 million solar cell factory in Turkey // PV Magazine. URL: <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2025/04/02/astronergy-to-build-500-million-solar-cell-factory-in-turkey/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

⁴ 中国能建集团开展土耳其高端对接并签署395MW光伏项目 [CEEG has completed a high-end docking in Türkiye and signed a contract for the construction of a 395 MW photovoltaic plant] // Energy Trend. URL: <https://www.energytrend.cn/news/20250228-141092.html> (accessed: 03.01.2026). In Chinese.

⁵ 中国能建建筑集团中标土耳其74兆瓦酒店光伏EPC项目 [CSCEC has won the tender for the construction of EPC 74 MW photovoltaic panels for a hotel in Türkiye] // China Energy Engineering Corporation Limited. URL: https://www.ceec.net.cn/art/2024/3/26/art_11019_2530896.html (accessed: 03.01.2026). In Chinese.

Chinese involvement follows several distinct but consistent patterns:

- direct trade and supply contracts for modules and turbines;
- EPC contracts and integrated turnkey solutions that include design, equipment supply and construction;
- establishment of joint ventures and localization of assembly/production facilities in Türkiye;
- combined EPC plus Financing (EPC+F) schemes with the support of Chinese policy banks and export insurance (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. A typical model of China’s green development cooperation. Source: Adapted from China’s promotion of overseas green projects: Old models and new dynamics [10, p. 17].

The financing conditions for such projects shares characteristics typical of BRI initiatives and Chinese international lending. A common model involves: a Chinese SOE/contractor provides EPC services and facilitates securing financing from China Eximbank (中国进出口银行) or China Development Bank (国家开发银行), with risk insurance provided by Sinosure (中国信保); as a result, forming a bundled EPC+F “package” that mitigates commercial and transactional risks for the recipient¹. Empirical studies note that Chinese lending often features relatively low rates and long maturities for some projects (with rates in a broad sample ranging from 0.0 to 4.0% p.a., depending on the lending institution, and maturities of 9–20 years, sometimes with grace periods) [11, p. 27]. However, the final terms hinge on the structure of the transaction, collateral and the negotiating position of the receiving party.

Cooperation between the two countries yields clear mutual benefits. For Türkiye: (a) reduction of capital costs and accelerated expansion of installed capacities due to relatively cheap Chinese components and EPC solutions; (b) creation of industrial capacities and jobs through localization; (c) access to project financing and insurance tools, which is especially important amid constrained

¹ Bundles, Banks, and Builders: Inside China’s Finance Models for Power Projects in Africa // China Global South Project. URL: <https://chinglobalsouth.com/analysis/bundles-banks-and-builders-inside-chinas-finance-models-for-power-projects-in-africa/> (accessed: 03.01.2026).

domestic capital¹. For China: (a) expanding export markets and offloading idle production capacity to foreign markets; (b) strengthening the regional presence and optimizing logistics by locating production facilities in Türkiye; (c) promoting the EPC+F model and strengthening the role of Chinese political banks and insurance institutions as tools of economic influence².

These cooperative projects, however, face several limitations and risks: regulatory instability and changes in the conditions of state support for renewable energy, localization requirements, currency risks and geopolitical dynamics (including the impact of European climate regulations and potential trade disputes) can substantially alter project economics.

Cooperation between China and Türkiye in renewable energy represents a sustainable model of mutually beneficial partnership. For Türkiye, which aim is to reduce energy import dependency and meet the climate standards of key export markets, access to Chinese technology, capital, and integrated engineering solutions is an important factor in accelerating the energy transition. For China, this cooperation allows to optimize logistics via the “Middle Corridor”, provides an outlet for its production capacity in a new market, and offers a testing ground for the “EPC+F” model within an emerging economy. Despite the absence of a specialized bilateral green energy agreement and the presence of regulatory and geopolitical risks, practical cooperation continues to develop through investment and contractual projects. Further institutionalization of the partnership, including under Türkiye’s HIT-30 program, can significantly strengthen Türkiye’s position within global renewable energy value chains.

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CHANGES IN ECONOMIC BEHAVIOR IN THE FACE OF DECLINING INCOMES: BEHAVIORAL AND ADAPTATION ASPECTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes changes in the economic behavior of the population under conditions of declining incomes from the perspectives of behavioral economics and economic psychology. Various mechanisms of population adaptation to financial constraints were examined, along with transformations in saving and investment behaviors based on an analysis of the dynamics of real incomes and the structure of household expenditures from 2019 to 2024.*

Keywords: *economic behavior, behavioral economics, economic psychology, income reduction, adaptive strategies, investment behavior.*

Amidst the unstable socio-economic conditions prevailing globally, the analysis of the population's economic behavior gains particular scientific and practical significance. The reduction of available financial resources, the transformation of decision-making mechanisms, and changes in the motivational structure and value orientation system are the realities in which we currently live. In such an environment, the influence of behavioral factors inevitably intensifies, leading to the formation of adaptive strategies.

According to contemporary research in behavioral economics, income decline is directly linked to its effects on the cognitive and affective components of economic behavior, serving both as a quantitative constraint and as a source of financial stress [3]. This mechanism primarily manifests in the transformation of individual saving and investment behaviors, alterations in consumer attitudes, and the redistribution of priorities between current consumption and investment.

Individuals' reactions to deteriorating financial conditions are predominantly idiosyncratic, largely depending on their age, social characteristics, and expectations concerning their future financial situation.

Despite an extensive body of research devoted to economic behavior, the issue of its transformation under conditions of income decline necessitates further systematization, taking into account behavioral mechanisms and adaptation strategies. Particularly noteworthy is the analysis of how financial constraints influence the structure of economic decisions and which behavioral patterns emerge in response to increased uncertainty.

The aim of this article is to analyze changes in individual economic behavior amid declining incomes from the perspectives of economic psychology and behavioral economics.

It is important to note that the definition of individual economic behavior is interdisciplinary, located at the intersection of economics, psychology, and sociology. Owing to differences in research methodologies, multiple definitions of this concept are present in the academic literature. Economic behavior is generally defined as the totality of an individual's actions and decisions aimed at the utilization, allocation, and accumulation of economic resources under conditions of both scarcity and the availability of alternative choices.

From a sociological perspective, economic behavior is understood as a system of social actions aimed at obtaining material and non-material benefits, mediated by institutional norms [1]. The advantage of this approach lies in its capacity to consider the influence of the social environment, expectations, and norms on an individual's economic decisions; however, unlike other approaches, it less comprehensively reveals the internal psychological mechanisms underlying choice.

In economic psychology, the focus of analysis shifts toward subjective factors influencing an individual's economic behavior. The decision-making process may thus encompass three components: affective, cognitive, and motivational-volitional. The quality of economic information perception, the level of financial literacy, and the ability to evaluate alternatives are all reflected in the cognitive component. Emotional reactions such as anxiety, fear of loss, or uncertainty are associated with the affective component and tend to intensify as income decreases. The direction of an individual's economic activity is determined by the motivational-volitional component, which may involve a pursuit of stability and security or, alternatively, a search for new sources of income.

By highlighting the limitations of the assumption of full rationality of individuals, behavioral economics has substantially advanced the understanding of economic behavior. Behavioral biases — including loss aversion, consumption bias, and behavioral inertia — exert a stronger influence under conditions of

financial constraints and volatility. Consequently, individuals' economic decisions become adaptive and may diverge from models of optimal choice [2].

Therefore, analyzing individual economic behavior under conditions of declining incomes requires a comprehensive strategy that considers socio-economic and psychological factors. The mechanisms underlying the transformation of economic decisions can be identified through the application of theoretical concepts from behavioral economics and economic psychology. This establishes a methodological foundation for further analysis of changes in investment and saving behaviors, as well as adaptation strategies across different socio-demographic groups.

The reduction in individual income exerts a complex influence on economic behavior, contributing to financial stress and uncertainty, as well as serving as an objective constraint on financial resources. In such circumstances, behavioral mechanisms that determine how individuals adapt to the changing economic environment and develop new models of economic decision-making become increasingly important.

The propensity for loss aversion, which causes individuals to perceive potential losses as more significant than equivalent potential gains, constitutes one of the primary behavioral mechanisms. This effect results in a shift in economic behavior from a utility-maximizing approach to a risk-minimization strategy amid declining income. This manifests as a decrease in investment activity, avoidance of riskier financial decisions, and an emphasis on a more conservative approach to income management.

Dynamics of real disposable incomes of the population over the period 2019–2024. It reflects alternating phases of decline and partial recovery, which, in turn, created conditions for sustainable changes in the economic behavior of the population.

Table 1 — Dynamics of Population Incomes, % Compared to the Previous Year¹

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Real Monetary Incomes, as % Compared to the Previous Year	101,7	98,6	103,9	98,5	106,5	109,9
Real Disposable Monetary Incomes, as % Compared to the Previous Year	101,0	98,0	103,3	98,1	106,1	108,2

¹ Compiled by the author based on [4].

Data in Table 1 indicate that actual monetary and disposable incomes of the population exhibited uneven dynamics during the period from 2019 to 2024. The declines observed in 2020 and 2022 reflect the impact of external shocks and heightened economic uncertainty, whereas the subsequent recovery in 2023–2024 is non-linear and accompanied by changes in patterns of economic behavior. These trends demonstrate that a return to pre-crisis values does not necessarily entail a return to previous behavioral patterns.

Table 2 — Structure of Household Consumer Expenditures, %¹

Expenditure Category	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Monetary Income	62 235 779	63 691 954	70 547 560	83 425 195	94 063 201	112 160 153
purchase of goods and payment for services	50 301 065	48 231 433	56 627 649	62 930 438	72 384 271	83 537 293
payment of mandatory charges, contributions, and other expenses	9 522 467	9 696 269	10 918 862	13 305 041	13 888 700	17 777 914
increase (+), decrease (-) in savings	2 412 247	5 764 252	3 001 049	7 189 716	7 790 230	10 844 946

Analysis of the income allocation structure among the population reveals sustained changes in the priorities of economic decision-making (Table 2). The increase in mandatory payments and contributions, alongside the growth in total income, indicates a greater emphasis on fulfilling primary financial obligations and maintaining economic stability. Simultaneously, savings increase significantly, indicating the emergence of a conservative financial behavior model oriented towards accumulating reserves amidst persistent uncertainty.

Table 3 — Household Financial Assets, billion rubles²

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Financial assets, total	9 009	10 962	15 633	16 974
Cash currency	867	3 199	1 409	-286
Deposits	2 583	4 645	8 923	13 333
Funds in brokerage accounts	92	-415	-99	-139

¹ Compiled by the author based on [4].

² Compiled by the author based on [5].

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Debt securities	911	48	829	273
Loans	131	-232	168	113
Stocks and other forms of equity participation	1 780	2 167	2 073	1 436
Insurance and pension reserves and pension savings	283	15	72	844
Accounts receivable	504	543	713	846
Funds in escrow accounts	1 858	992	1 546	554

The analysis of household financial assets enables a more detailed characterization of the transformation in saving and investment behaviors. The total volume of financial assets has increased significantly over the period under review, indicating a greater emphasis on accumulation and liquidity preservation rather than on enhanced investment activity.

The shift in citizens' preferences toward the least risky and more transparent forms of fund allocation is most evident in the significant increase in deposit volumes, particularly during 2022–2024. Concurrently, there is a decline or negative trend in cash balances on brokerage accounts and volatility in investments in debt securities and equities, reflecting a diminished willingness of households to accept investment risk under conditions of increased uncertainty.

Behavioral strategies aimed at minimizing financial losses are evidenced by a decrease in the share of active financial instruments alongside an increase in deposits and cash savings. Thus, changes in the structure of financial assets indicate the formation of a protective savings behavior model, wherein priority is given to capital preservation rather than its augmentation.

Consequently, the observed dynamics of income and its utilization structure confirm behavioral mechanisms of loss avoidance. Individual economic behavior shifts toward prioritizing financial stability and risk reduction under conditions of income instability. This is followed by constraints on long-term investment decisions and a redistribution of resources favoring immediate security.

The identified changes reflect a process of population adaptation to heightened uncertainty and exhibit a persistent character. This enables the transformation of economic behavior to be viewed as the outcome of the development of new behavioral strategies influencing individual saving and investment behaviors, rather than merely a short-term reaction to declining incomes.

The analysis of changes in attitudes toward savings and investments is especially important, as adaptive responses to decreasing incomes and increased uncertainty are most evident in these areas of economic activity. A more

comprehensive understanding of the determinants of economic decisions can be achieved by analyzing the allocation of resources among current consumption, savings, and investments. This analysis also identifies differences in adaptive strategies employed by various socio-age groups.

One method of economic adaptation to income decline and forecasting uncertainty is saving and investing. The results of the previous section demonstrate that these changes are long-term in nature and represent a reorientation of economic decision-making towards risk reduction and the preservation of financial stability.

Changes in household structure and an increase in their aggregate financial assets indicate a transformation in saving motives. Savings primarily serve as a safeguard during periods of uncertainty, accumulating monetary reserves rather than generating income through investments. A noticeable increase in deposits and a decline in activity in more

This behavioral tendency is explained by loss aversion and responses to financial stress from the perspective of behavioral economics. Even when their real returns decline, individuals prefer instruments characterized by low volatility. Consequently, investment decisions involving delayed effects and elevated risk are supplanted by strategies focused on short-term financial security.

It is important to emphasize that the nature of saving and investment behavior is inherently subjective and contingent upon numerous factors. Adaptive strategies are frequently heterogeneous and vary among different social and age groups within the population. In conditions of pessimistic expectations, there is a heightened focus on accumulation and avoidance of risky investments, while relative confidence in income recovery may foster elements of investment activity.

The transformation of individual saving and investment behavior in the context of declining incomes is characterized by the predominance of protective strategies, an increase in liquid forms of savings, and the limitation of long-term investment planning. These changes reflect the population's adaptation to conditions of increased economic uncertainty and establish stable models of economic behavior that impact financial activity and the investment potential of households.

Thus, the transformation of individual economic behavior in conditions of declining incomes is adaptive rather than short-term in nature, reflecting the formation of stable patterns of saving and investment behavior. Consideration of the identified behavioral changes is of practical importance for the formulation of economic policy measures and financial education programs aimed at strengthening household financial resilience under conditions of economic uncertainty.

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APPROACHES TO THE MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES IN THE SPHERES OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The article draws attention to the positive impact of innovative technologies on economic development in modern fields of activity. The essence of the concepts of “innovation” and “innovation activity” is revealed. The importance of management for ensuring the effectiveness of innovation activities is substantiated. The principles of involving creative and innovative personalities in innovative activities are proposed. The main characteristics of creative and innovative individuals are listed. The effectiveness of the organization of innovation activities based on a team approach is emphasized. Approaches to the organization and management of innovation activities, the choice of methods, styles and management tools are considered. The factors underlying the effectiveness of innovation management are listed.*

Keywords: *innovation, innovation activity, innovation team, innovation management, innovation efficiency factors.*

Introduction. The economic relations and development concepts formed in the modern world require the creation and application of technologies, functioning mechanisms and management methods adequate to modern realities in order to achieve sustainable development of the national economic system, especially in priority economic activities. This condition highlights the expansion of innovation activity, which is one of the main challenges of the era, and the formation of an improved management system for more efficient use of the advantages created by innovation.

Currently, as a result of the widespread introduction of digital and innovative technologies, artificial intelligence in most areas of production and services, including the production and consumption of various goods and services, management, creation and development of trade and economic relations and other processes, achievements in the processes of economic development have

increased the possibilities of accelerating the transition to a qualitatively new stage of development in areas of economic activity.

Therefore, the implementation of systemic measures in the field of creation and implementation of innovative technologies that create the basis for expanding opportunities for economic development and managing this process should become one of the priorities of economic policy in our country.

It is also important to take into account that in order to achieve sustainable development, diversification, and balanced economic development in the country, it is advisable to use the possibilities of innovative technologies. In this regard, it is of interest to study the issues of expanding innovation in the agricultural sector, the widespread introduction of innovative technologies, the identification and search for ways to solve organizational, economic and managerial problems of innovation.

The relevance of the problem. In the modern world, it is impossible to imagine the development of any economic activity without the use of innovative technologies. The creation, application and dissemination of innovative and digital technologies are of exceptional importance for improving the efficiency of the use of production factors, increasing labor productivity in production areas, improving the quality of service in service areas, increasing the competitiveness of business entities, and achieving overall economic development and growth. One of the important tasks is to organize and effectively manage innovation activities in order to create positive effects from the use of innovative and digital technologies. The research is devoted to approaches to the organization and management of innovation activities and is notable for its relevance.

The purpose of the study. The purpose of the study is to propose approaches that create the basis for the organization and effective management of activities in the field of innovation and to propose management mechanisms taking into account the factors that determine the choice of optimal management methods and tools.

Material and methods of research. Research materials of domestic and foreign authors on the organization and management of innovation activities were used in the study.

The methodological basis of the study is a systematic and aspective approach to the issue.

The study used methods of analysis, comparison, synthesis and deduction.

Discussion. The term “innovation”, derived from the Latin word “innovatus”, “innovato”, is one of the most used expressions in scientific sources of recent decades. “Innovation” means the use of innovative technologies, methods, instruments and tools in production and service processes, in the management of economic, cultural, social and other activities and processes, as well as the presentation of new examples of cultural, tangible and intangible commodities created as a result of enterprising and creative activities, discoveries and inventions

of creative people, which are different from their previous analogues and are distinguished by high quality characteristics [1; 5].

Thus, innovative technologies are aimed at creating a new models, products, works and services that are qualitatively different from existing examples and have a relatively superior positive character, as well as new features of management methods in organizational and structural aspects.

Innovative technologies penetrate all areas of economic activity, represent the principles of comprehensive development, socio-economic relations, scientific, technical and technological integration in a new quality, and create the basis for more efficient use of existing resources and economic potential. All this plays an important role in improving the quality of life of people [2].

Innovation plays an important role among the main driving forces of modern development. The importance of using innovative technologies to increase the competitiveness of business entities, improve the quality of products and services offered on the consumer market, ensure consumer loyalty to the business entity and its products, form the image of the enterprise and its successful operation in the market, ensure financial stability and economic security, etc. is undeniable.

Experience shows that the use of innovative technologies plays an important role in achieving sustainable development, which is one of the concepts of economic development of the modern era. And in areas that play an important role in satisfaction society's needs for basic consumer commodities and services, including in the agricultural sector, sustainable development is ensured by more favorable conditions through the introduction of innovative technologies.

This factors involves close and mutual coordination of resources and innovative opportunities that can be used to create and apply innovations, with an enterprising, innovative and creative workforce that promotes the expansion and development of innovation in the economic activity spheres and carries out coordinated activities.

In such an environment, each participant has a specific interest in the development of innovative activities, and their cooperation is focused on common goals, which improves the organization and coordination of activities and facilitates management. It should be noted that this approach to management can be modified depending on the complexity of innovation activities, the required changes at the individual and team levels (changes in knowledge, relationships, experience, rules), as well as the degree of uncertainty that arises.

It is known from learning theories that people tend to acquire knowledge related to the field that they consider useful in order to earn money and live in conditions of high well-being [4]. At the present stage, innovation is considered attractive to many people in terms of making a profit and ensuring a comfortable life. Therefore, the creation of favorable conditions in innovation activities for realizing the creative potential of individuals, increasing their practical

knowledge and developing innovative abilities should be taken into account in management approaches.

However, it should be borne in mind that the number of people capable of engaging in innovative activities is limited. Practice shows that only 4–5% of people have the ability to be entrepreneurial, creative, and innovative. Innovativeness, creativity is the ability, knowledge and skills of an individual to invent, develop, assimilate and improve new ideas in order to effectively use available resources to create innovative technologies, product samples and services [3].

The following traits are also considered characteristic of innovative, creative individuals:

- possessing innovative understanding and thinking.
- the ability to think outside the group or individual box, unconventionally, distinctively;
- have a specific goal, motives, suggesting a partial or complete change in the structural, functional, institutional, regulatory indicators of an object.
- be able to present new ideas, elements in a different quality, combining them.

Creative, innovative-minded individuals should also be carriers of the following functional characteristics;

- assessment of the general situation in the field of innovation and the innovation environment through continuous analysis;
- setting goals for the implementation of new ideas;
- take risks and experiment;
- conducting tests of new samples with partners and team members;
- build relationships and alliances with other innovation centers and teams;
- be able to mobilize resources for innovation.

Taking into account the characteristics of creative people helps identify principles of innovation management and apply useful methods to improve management effectiveness. By considering the directions, goals, and types of innovation, as well as the innovations it encompasses in relationships, experiences, operating principles, and values, it becomes possible to predict which management methods and tools will be most effective in use.

One of the important tasks of innovation management in various fields of economic activity is to take into account the complexity of the innovation process, especially the diversity of the main driving and motivating factors of innovation at different levels. The following groups of driving and motivating factors of innovation activity can be distinguished:

- psychological factors;
- economic factors;
- cultural factors;
- demographic factors;

— technological factors.

The level of effectiveness of individuals or teams with high innovation potential depends on the overall accessibility and accessibility of the factors listed above. The presence of these factors makes it possible to more effectively organize and manage individual and group innovation activities.

Management at all stages of innovation activity in various fields of economic activity is important from the point of view of creating opportunities for individual and collective thinking, organizing the exchange of ideas, monitoring collective innovation activities, sharing experiences, dissemination and implementation of innovations. In particular, with the expansion of innovation activities and the development of innovative technologies, the need to improve management mechanisms is also increasing [6].

Such a need arises in connection with an increase in the efficiency of the use of innovations, an increase in the number of subjects involved in innovation activities, satisfaction of the interests of each of them, abuse of favorable conditions by individual participants in corporate interests, as well as the growth of other informal relations.

Continuous improvement of process management and the creation of flexible mechanisms ensure both the prevention of these abuses and the expansion of opportunities to achieve strategic management goals.

Conclusion. The development and expansion of innovation activities in various sectors of the economy and the improvement of their effectiveness directly depend on management approaches, styles and methods.

Therefore, in order to achieve the effective use of innovative opportunities and innovative potential in the organization and development of innovative activities, special attention should be paid to the creation of flexible and modern management mechanisms, the choice of methods and tools.

Another important issue is the involvement of creative and innovative individuals in innovative activities to achieve success in creating and applying innovations.

One of the important issues is to create the necessary favorable environment for the subjects of innovation activity, both individually and collectively, as well as to provide them with favorable and accessible psychological, cultural, technological, economic and demographic factors, which should be one of the goals of solving problems.

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MARKETING AS A TOOL FOR COMPETITIVE PRESSURE IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET AND A FACTOR IN PRICE REDUCTION

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Abstract. *This article examines marketing as an instrument of competitive pressure within the pharmaceutical market and as a factor contributing to the reduction of pharmaceutical product prices. Theoretical foundations of marketing are delineated not only as promotional tools but also as economic mechanisms that shape the competitive environment and affect price dynamics. Findings indicate that marketing approaches indirectly influence price levels by shaping demand's price sensitivity, lowering switching barriers among therapeutically equivalent products, and intensifying generic competition. The principal pathways and channels through which marketing exerts influence on competitive pressure — specifically by affecting consumer behavior, prescribing practices, and the assortment policies of pharmacy chains — are presented and systematically analyzed. The transformation of the pharmaceutical market is described through the prism of evolving marketing practices and industry digitalization. It has been established that the contemporary marketing toolkit, by optimizing communication and sales processes, contributes to restraining price increases and enhancing the accessibility of medicinal products. The study substantiates the theoretical significance of marketing as an instrument of competitive pressure, which complements administrative and institutional regulatory measures in the pharmaceutical market.*

Keywords: *marketing within the pharmaceutical market structure, marketing influence on the market, price competition, marketing optimization, competitive pressure in the market.*

The pharmaceutical market is one of the socially significant yet highly regulated sectors of the economy, where price dynamics associated with the final cost of drugs directly affect the accessibility of medical care and the condition of the healthcare system. Amid the transformation of the external economic environment, rising costs, and intensified competition, the issue of the high cost

of medicinal products becomes increasingly pronounced and extends beyond the scope of solely governmental regulation. Accordingly, the significance of market-based and internal management mechanisms aimed at amplifying competitive pressure increases; notably, contemporary literature highlights that these trends stem from the heightened role of marketing as a factor of indirect regulation. For example, I. Yu. Okolnishnikova and V. N. Bystrov emphasize that in the new context, marketing evolves into a tool for aligning companies with the competitive environment, affecting demand structure, distribution channels, and the behavior of market participants. Thus, marketing becomes a factor that indirectly influences the level of competition and, consequently, the price parameters of the pharmaceutical market [6].

At the same time, the issue regarding the adequacy of traditional instruments of state price regulation in ensuring the accessibility of medicinal products remains relevant. According to R. O. Obidova, direct price regulation, although effective in the short term, is accompanied by latent effects, including assortment reduction, decreased investment activity, and distortion of the market incentive structure due to the increased influence of the state on companies [4]. There is a growing need to develop additional mechanisms aimed at intensifying competition and fostering price sensitivity in the market without compromising its fundamental stability.

Accordingly, the relevance of this study is based on the necessity to theoretically conceptualize marketing not only as a tool for communication and promotion but also as a factor of competitive pressure that facilitates price reduction in the pharmaceutical market. The scientific problem stems from the insufficient representation in the literature of the mechanisms by which marketing approaches influence price dynamics and the competitive environment, which defines the aim and scope of this research.

The objective of this study is to examine marketing and its mechanisms as instruments of competitive pressure in the pharmaceutical market, as well as factors contributing to price reduction.

Traditionally, the role of marketing within the pharmaceutical market has been confined to promoting drugs and stimulating demand. However, in the current context, marketing assumes greater significance, functioning both as a medium of communication with consumers and as a tool influencing the competitive landscape and price dynamics. In other words, marketing can be defined as a set of management mechanisms designed to redistribute market power, reduce information asymmetry, and enhance price sensitivity among market participants.

From the standpoint of economic theory, price reductions in the pharmaceutical market become feasible under conditions of competitive pressure, which limit the capacity of producers and distributors to sustain monopolistically high prices. Previous research has highlighted that marketing within the pharmaceutical

industry functions to stimulate sales and foster conditions conducive to price competition through the promotion of generics, optimization of distribution channels, increased transparency of supply chains, and the reallocation of demand toward more affordable drugs. Consequently, marketing tools do not directly impact price but influence the factors that determine its level [3].

A fundamental component of the mechanism by which marketing affects market price levels is the development of demand price sensitivity, cultivated through informing physicians, pharmacy chains, and end consumers about the therapeutic equivalence of drugs, the availability of alternatives, and the economic rationale of the choice. Accordingly, marketing decreases switching barriers between branded and generic drugs, thereby intensifying pressure on original drug manufacturers, compelling them to adjust their pricing strategies or inevitably lose previously held market share. Therefore, marketing assumes the role of an instrument for indirect price regulation, grounded in market incentives and competitive pressure.

An additional aspect of this mechanism is the optimization of the supply structure, given that marketing decisions (such as revising the drug portfolio, reclassifying certain medicinal products from prescription-only to over-the-counter categories, and developing private labels for pharmacy chains and digital sales channels) contribute to reducing transaction costs and increasing competition among suppliers. We have previously emphasized that the integrated use of marketing and administrative instruments allows for the development of a hybrid model for reducing drug costs, in which marketing serves a system-forming role [3].

Moreover, analysis of international studies demonstrates that competition per se does not ensure price reductions; for instance, A. Sarpatwari, J. DeBello, M. Zakarian, M. Najafzadeh, and A. S. Kesselheim conclude that competition among branded drugs within a single therapeutic class fails to reduce prices without supplementary structural and marketing mechanisms. Moreover, active marketing promotion of new branded drugs may be accompanied by price increases within the class if it is not aimed at fostering price competition [10]. Thus, marketing exerts pressure specifically related to the competitive environment, and price reductions become feasible only when marketing strategies focus on expanding choices, intensifying competition through the introduction of generics, enhancing transparency of treatment cost information, and redistributing demand in favor of economically efficient solutions. All of the above constitute mechanisms that underlie the influence of marketing on the price level in the market.

Thus, broadly speaking, marketing in the pharmaceutical market should be regarded as an economic mechanism through which conditions of competitive pressure are formed, the structure of demand and supply is altered, and ultimately the prerequisites for reducing the prices of pharmaceutical products are established (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The mechanism of marketing's influence on competitive pressure and price reduction in the pharmaceutical market, compiled by the author.

Referring to Fig. 1, it is important to note that the influence of marketing on competitive pressure and price dynamics in the pharmaceutical market operates through a set of specific channels that mediate the behavior of participants within the 'manufacturer — physician — pharmacy — consumer' chain. The pharmaceutical sector is characterized by multi-level decision-making, which underscores the significant role of marketing tools as instruments for redistributing market power and shaping price sensitivity.

The primary pathways and channels through which marketing affects competitive pressure and prices in the pharmaceutical market are presented in Table 1:

It is evident that the primary channel of marketing influence remains the impact on the consumer behavior of both end patients and professional intermediaries. Marketing, as accurately noted by V. V. Berulya, primarily affects the formation of perceptions concerning the efficacy, safety, and accessibility of medicinal products, as well as through digital communication channels, which currently

facilitate greater awareness of alternatives [1]. Moreover, directing marketing efforts towards the comparative economic efficiency of treatments encourages an increased share of more affordable drugs in prescription practices, thereby intensifying competitive pressure on manufacturers of original medicinal products (notably, this approach is applied in engagement with the medical community) [8].

Table 1. Pathways and channels of marketing influence on competitive pressure and prices in the pharmaceutical market, compiled based on sources [1; 8].

Channel of Influence	Agents of Influence	Mechanism of Influence	Effect on Competition	Effect on Prices
Informational Influence on Consumers	Patients, end consumers	Enhancing awareness of therapeutic alternatives, drug efficacy, and cost	Reducing demand for specific brands and increasing drug substitutability	Containing price growth and promoting a shift toward more affordable analogues
Marketing influence on prescribing practices	Physicians and medical organizations	Shaping perceptions of clinical and economic effectiveness and treatment affordability	Altering prescription patterns in favor of generics	Intensification of price pressure on branded drugs.
Digital marketing channels and analytics.	Manufacturers, pharmacies, and patients.	Personalization of communications, comparative drug analysis, and digital platforms.	Expansion of competition and enhancement of market transparency.	Increase in demand price sensitivity.
Assortment policy of pharmacy chains.	Pharmacy chains and distributors.	Promotion of generics, private labels, and alternative brands.	Intensification of competition among pharmaceutical products.	Reduction in the average cost of treatment.
Price positioning and marketing mix.	Pharmaceutical manufacturers.	Emphasis on the price-quality ratio and market segmentation.	Limitation of market power held by major brands.	Adjustment of pricing strategies under competitive pressure.

It should be noted that ultimately marketing becomes a resource and catalyst for the development of the pharmaceutical market, intensifying competition, reducing entry barriers for new players, and expanding opportunities for the promotion of alternative, including more affordable, drugs [5]. From the perspective of long-term

market dynamics, marketing contributes to the formation of a more heterogeneous competitive environment, wherein the role of generics and alternative brands is strengthened. Specifically, the expansion of the competitive field resulting from the entry of generics leads to a structural shift towards price reduction; for instance, S. Hediger, L. Locher, and K. N. Fockinger, based on analyses of the US, German, and Swiss markets, demonstrate a correlation between an increase in the number of competitors and a decrease in prices for both generic and original drugs [9]. Furthermore, marketing plays a crucial role in facilitating the effective market introduction of generics and their acceptance by both consumers and physicians. The development of the pharmaceutical market through the prism of marketing consistently manifests as a transition from relatively closed and highly concentrated structures to more competitive and adaptable models of medicinal product provision. In this context, marketing serves as a mechanism that accelerates market transformation by influencing demand redistribution, alleviating price pressure on healthcare systems, and improving access to medicinal products. Viewing marketing as a factor in market development allows for a renewed evaluation of its role in ensuring the social efficiency of the pharmaceutical sector.

It is important to underscore that the final price of a pharmaceutical product is shaped by a combination of factors and depends on the state of government regulation, cost structure, level of competition, and demand. As D. F. Garifullina notes, within this system, marketing serves as a connecting function between production and market parameters, facilitating the development of pricing strategies aligned with the characteristics of specific segments and distribution channels [2]. The application of contemporary segmentation, positioning, and assortment differentiation tools particularly facilitates the realization of variability in price management and alleviates pressure on the end consumer. For this reason, according to Yu. V. Tarasov, solutions involving digital communications, packaging, and service support are increasingly employed in the pharmaceutical market, alongside exhibitions organized for the integrated promotion of new medicinal products, drugs, and their analogues [7].

Thus, marketing in the pharmaceutical sector fulfills a systemic function by influencing the structure of supply and demand, redistributing market power among participants, and lowering switching barriers between therapeutically equivalent drugs. By shaping consumer price sensitivity, altering prescribing practices, and stimulating generic competition, marketing tools create conditions under which maintaining monopolistically high prices becomes economically inefficient. Furthermore, marketing affects prices not directly but through the transformation of the market environment, allowing it to be regarded as an alternative or complement to administrative price regulation measures, as marketing mechanisms depend on market incentives and behavioral changes.

The theoretical significance of this study and its findings lies in establishing marketing as a tool of competitive pressure integrated within the system that ensures the accessibility of medicinal products. The findings expand the understanding of marketing functions in socially significant sectors and provide a foundation for further research focused on the development of pharmaceutical market regulation models.

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